

Habilitation Thesis

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Contributions to plant ecophysiology under heavy metals stress and to scaling for phytoremediation in contaminated areas

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and to scaling for phytoremediation in contaminated areas**

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I have devoted my time always working according to the scientific spirit that is characterized by holding off, being sure but not too sure, and being willing to surrender ideas when the evidence is against them. This decision was good after all, it always kept the way beyond open, always gave life, thought, affection, the whole man, a chance to try again after a mistake - after a wrong assumption (adapted after Walt Whitman).

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A1 Summary

The habilitation thesis with the title "Contributions to the ecophysiology of plants under heavy metal stress and to scaling for phytoremediation in contaminated areas" consists of an extensive synthesis of my scientific and didactic activity performed after obtaining the title of doctor in natural sciences (*rerum naturalium*, 1999) and contains the last chapter the evolution and development plan of the scientific and teaching career, as well as future perspectives.

The purpose of this thesis is to present the evolution of scientific research activities from the simple classic approach, which focused on a single objective (e.g., phytoextraction, phytoremediation, etc.), to a complex approach with a multi-objective focus (e.g., besides phytoremediation, the focus was also on several other ecosystem services).

If before the start of the doctoral program and during its development, the focus was on the field of the biogeochemical cycles of nitrogen and heavy metals, and only in the initial phase on the subfield of remediation of areas polluted with both organic and inorganic compounds, later I deepened the circulation of heavy metals and developed after an original, objective method, the remediation of metal-polluted areas making a valuable contribution also in the field of plant ecophysiology. This activity was carried out within the framework of two post-doctoral fellowships, three reintegration projects, and several international and national fundamental and applied research projects.

After a general description of the approach, the **working method** consisted in the presentation of the scientific activity in section B: Scientific achievements, which in turn are grouped into Theoretical Contributions, Methodological Contributions, Results obtained as a result of investigations directly in the field as well as in ex -situ and in-situ experiments, and the Technological Development subsection, Section C: Plans for the evolution and development of the scientific and didactic career with subsections C.1 Coordinates for the conduct of research activities carried out until now, and C2 Coordinates for the conduct of didactic activities conducted until now, the last section D being the references subchapter.

Methodological development started with simple pot-scale experiments in plant growth chambers or greenhouses, at ex-situ lysimeter scale with zero-tension or light-tension, up to plots experimental plot scale from 2x2 m x 35plots, up to 5x5 m x 10 plots. The proposal in the following application is at a scale of 25 x 25 m. The experimental design and the research hypotheses were formulated according to the scientific interest, both in fundamental and applied research.

In terms of basic research, a current area of interest of great complexity has been found in exploring how the amount and stoichiometry of elements in the soil and the temperature control the traits space of grassland plants, and then, in turn, some of these traits control the elemental fluxes by runoff and leaching, their stoichiometry, and in the long term the stocks and stoichiometry of elements in the soil. This research had three primary objectives: to test four hypotheses about the effects of heavy metals and time on the C:N:P stoichiometry in field conditions, to test six hypotheses about the effects of HMs and temperature on the C:N:P stoichiometry at the microcosm and mesocosm scales ex-situ, to test three hypotheses about the effects of HMs and temperature on the structure of traits space and to disentangle the significance of the results about the effects of complex stress on the production of ecosystem

services. This research was made possible within the exploratory research project no. 156 of 16/02/2021, PN-III-P4-ID-PCE-2020-0494) with the title: "Exploring the effects of metals and temperature on the functional traits of grassland plants, coupled to water-mediated element fluxes" - METTELFUX) (some findings can be found in the last part of chapter B2, Theoretical contributions, and more details in the article by Iordache and Neagoe 2023, published in the Journal of Environmental Management).

The significant conceptual advance is the link between the biogeochemical niche and ecological stoichiometry bodies of knowledge and the eco-hydrological one (extended with elemental fluxes) by key plant traits common to both fields. The methodology uses three heavy metal contaminated sites already intensively characterized and multi-scale experiments. This has immediate applications un bio(eco)-technologies used in environmental restoration/remediation. Its importance from a socio-economic or cultural point of view is by the concept of ecosystem services: it provides a deep understanding of the value of functional biodiversity for the production of regulation services inside, and especially outside of the protected area. It has the potential to improve the attitudes of the public towards biodiversity.

Regarding applied research, I briefly presented in subchapter B5 the transition methodology from TRL2 to TRL6, which has been possible until now in two stages: in 2014-2017, we went from TRL2 to TRL3 within the partnership project no. 98 of 01/07/2014 (PN-II-PT-PCCA-2013-4-2171) with the title "Tools for the integrated management of mining areas and rivers basins" - TIMMAR). During 2020-2022, we upscaled from the TRL3 to TRL4 in the experimental-demonstration research project no. 453 of 23/10/2020 (PN-III-P2-2.1-PED-2019-2584) with the title: "TRL4 Remediation eco-technology of tailing dams in function of geochemical, geomorphological and ecological setting" - TIMMAR- RESET)". The transition from TRL4 to TRL6 was proposed in the technology transfer project application PN-IV-P7-7.1-PTE-2024-0762 with the title: "TRL6 eco-technology for the remediation of tailings dams in function of geochemical, geomorphological and ecological settings" - TIMMAR 2-RESET". This application is under evaluation, the proposed eco-technology being of importance both globally as evidenced by the ecological stability standards recommended by the International Commission on Large Dams in Bulletin 153 on the sustainable design and post-closure performance of tailings dams (ICOLD Tailings Dam Committee 2013), as well as on a European and national level where two facts of high public visibility pointed out the importance of the technology proposed for maturation at the TRL6 stage: the first is the situation of supply chains with critical materials. The second is the consequence of the lack of correlation in public policies in the case of Roşia Montana gold mining project.

A2 Rezumat

Teza de abilitare cu titlul “Contribuții la ecofiziologia plantelor sub stresul metalelor grele și la scalarea pentru fitoremediere în zone contaminate” constă într-o sinteză extinsă a activității mele științifice și didactice derulate după obținerea titlului de doctor în științele naturii (1999) și conține în ultimul capitol planul de evoluție și dezvoltare a carierei științifice și didactice, precum și perspective de viitor.

Scopul acestei teze este de a prezenta modul de evoluție a activităților de cercetare științifică de la abordarea clasică simplă cu focalizare pe un singur obiectiv de (ex. fitoextracție, fitoremediere etc.), la o abordare complexă cu focalizare multi-obiectiv (de ex. pe lângă fitoremediere, concentrarea a fost și pe câteva alte servicii ecosistemice).

Dacă înainte de începerea programului doctoral și în timpul derulării acestuia accentul a fost pe domeniul circuite biogeochimice ale azotului și metalelor grele, și doar în fază incipientă pe subdomeniul remedierii zonelor poluate atât cu compuși organici cât și anorganici, ulterior am aprofundat circuitele metalelor grele și am dezvoltat după o metodă originală, obiectivă, bioremedierea zonelor poluate cu metale aducând contribuții valoroase și în domeniul ecofiziologiei vegetale. Această activitate s-a derulat în cadrul a două burse post-doctorale, trei proiecte de reintegrare și a mai multor proiecte de cercetare fundamentală și aplicativă atât internaționale cât și naționale.

După o descriere generală a modului de abordare, **metoda de lucru** a constat în prezentarea activității științifice în secțiunile B: Realizări științifice care la rândul ei se grupează în Contribuții teoretice, Contribuții metodologice, Rezultate obținute în urma investigațiilor direct în teren precum și în experimente ex-situ și in-situ și subsecțiunea Dezvoltare tehnologică, Secțiunea C: Planuri de evoluție și dezvoltare a carierei științifice și didactice cu subsecțiunile C.1 Coordonatele de desfășurare a activităților de cercetare derulate până în prezent și C2 Coordonatele de desfășurare a activităților didactice derulate până în prezent, ultima secțiune D fiind subcapitolul de referințe bibliografice.

Dezvoltarea metodologică a început cu experimente simple la scară de vase de vegetație în camere de creștere a plantelor sau în seră, la scară de lizimetre ex-situ cu tensiune zero sau tensiune ușoară, până la scară de parcele experimentale de la dimensiunea de 2x2 m x 35 parcele, la 5x5 m x 10 parcele, propunerea în următoarea aplicație fiind la scară de 25 x 25 m. Designul experimental și ipotezele de cercetare au fost formulate în funcție de interesul științific, care a fost deopotrivă în cercetare fundamentală, și/ sau aplicativă.

În ceea ce privește cercetarea fundamentală, un domeniu de interes actual de mare complexitate a constat în explorarea modului în care cantitatea de elemente din sol și stoechiometria lor, precum și temperatura, controlează spațiul trăsăturilor funcționale ale plantelor din pajiști, iar unele trăsături vor controla fluxurile elementelor și stoechiometria din apa de scurgere și percolare, și pe termen lung, stocurile și stoechiometria elementelor din sol. Această cercetare a avut la bază trei obiective majore: testarea a patru ipoteze despre efectul metalelor grele și timpului asupra stoechiometriei C:N:P în condiții de teren, despre testarea a șase ipoteze despre efectele metalelor grele și temperaturii asupra stoechiometriei C:N:P la scară de microcosm și mezocosm, ex-situ și despre testarea a trei ipoteze despre efectele metalelor grele și temperaturii asupra structurii spațiului trăsăturilor și clarificării semnificației

rezultatelor despre efectele stresului complex asupra producției serviciilor ecosistemice. Această cercetare a fost posibilă în cadrul proiectului de cercetare exploratorie nr.156 din 16/02/2021, PN-III-P4-ID-PCE-2020-0494) cu titlul: „Explorarea efectelor metalelor grele și temperaturii asupra trăsăturilor funcționale ale plantelor cuplate cu fluxurile de elemente mediate hidrologic” - METTELFLUX) (câteva constatări pot fi găsite în ultima parte a capitolului B2 Contribuții teoretice, iar mai multe în articolul Iordache și Neagoe 2023, publicat în Journal of Environmental Management).

Progresul major conceptual constă în legătura dintre nișa biogeochimică și corpul de cunoaștere stoichiometrică ecologică și eco-hidrologică (extins prin fluxuri de elemente) prin trăsături cheie ale plantelor comune ambelor domenii. Metodologia a utilizat trei situri contaminate cu metale grele deja caracterizate intens, și experimente la multi-scară. Această cercetare a avut aplicații imediate în bio(eco)tehnologiile utilizate în refacerea/remedierea mediului, iar relevanța din punct de vedere socio-economic sau cultural prin conceptul de servicii ecosistemice constă în oferirea unei înțelegeri profunde a valorii biodiversității funcționale pentru producerea de servicii de reglementare în interiorul, și mai ales în afara ariilor protejate și are potențialul de a îmbunătăți atitudinea publicului față de biodiversitate.

În ce privește cercetarea aplicativă, am prezentat succint în subcapitolul B5 metodologia de tranziție de la TRL2 la TRL6, care a fost posibilă până în prezent în două etape: în perioada 2014-2017 am trecut de la TRL2 la TRL3 în cadrul proiectului de parteneriate nr. 98 din 01/07/2014 (PN-II-PT-PCCA-2013-4-2171) cu titlul „Servicii și ecotehnologii inovative de mediu pentru managementul integrat al zonelor miniere și bazinelor hidrografice” - TIMMAR). În perioada 2020-2022 am făcut saltul de la TRL3 la TRL4 în proiectul de cercetare experimental-demonstrativă nr. 453 din 23/10/2020 (PN-III-P2-2.1-PED-2019-2584), cu titlul: „Eco-tehnologie TRL4 de remediere a iazurilor de decantare în funcție de condițiile biogeochimice, geomorfologice și ecologice” - TIMMAR-RESET). Tranziția de la TRL4 la TRL6 a fost propusă în aplicația de proiect de tip transfer tehnologic PN-IV-P7-7.1-PTE-2024-0762 cu titlul: „Eco-tehnologie TRL6 de remediere a iazurilor de decantare în funcție de condițiile geochimice, geomorfologice și ecologice” - TIMMAR 2-RESET). Această aplicație este în curs de evaluare, eco-tehnologia propusă având importanță atât pe plan global evidențiată de standardele de stabilitate ecologică recomandate de Comisia internațională pentru baraje mari în Buletinul 153 despre proiectarea durabilă și performanța post închidere a iazurilor de decantare (ICOLD Tailings Dam Committee 2013), cât și pe plan european și național unde două fapte de mare vizibilitate publică evidențiază importanța tehnologiei propuse pentru maturizare la stadiu TRL6: primul este situația lanțurilor de aprovizionare cu materiale critice, iar al doilea este consecința lipsei de corelare în politici publice în cazul proiectului de exploatare a aurului de la Roșia Montana.

B Scientific and professional achievements

B1 Introduction

I will present theoretical, methodological, empirical, and knowledge transfer contributions following studies performed on areas polluted with heavy metals in Germany, where I carried out part of my research activity, and later on similar areas in Romania, where I have been reintegrated since 2005.

The general problem of phytoremediation of heavy metal-polluted sites has evolved in our group from a classic single-objective approach (e.g. phytostabilization or phytoextraction) to a more ecological multi-objective approach (for instance, several other ecosystem services besides phytostabilization). This had consequences on the basic scientific questions that need to be answered and on the management objectives. For instance, for simple phytostabilization, the dependent variable of plants in experiments can be limited to aboveground and belowground biomass, concentrations of heavy metals, and oxidative stress. If one is interested in objectives such as habitats and microhabitats for mobile species using the remediated sites or in hydrological and erosion control services to minimize the export of pollutants, functional traits of plants from an individual to site scale should also be measured, together with the relevant independent variables.

As a result of this spectrum of problems, I had to develop innovative conceptual approaches (subchapter B2), methodologies, and experimental settings (subchapter B3) to address the cross-scale research question. The main conceptual innovation is a stoichiometric approach relating the heavy metals as stressors and functional traits of plants, with their consequences for hydrological and erosion control services. The main methodological innovation is the integrated coupling of experiments from pot to lysimeter to field plots to support the upscaling of the knowledge about the function of soil-plant systems up to the site (ecosystem) scale. Many decisions about the feasibility of remediation have been taken only based on pot experiments, which engage a high risk of failure at a large scale. I have coordinated the development of technology up to TRL4.¹ with much fewer risks because of the demonstration up to the scale of 10x25 m (subchapter B5).

As expected, most of the basic science questions related to functional traits are addressed only at the pot experimental scale due to the lower costs and the possibility of having many experimental variants within a reasonable budget. Overall, the increase in complexity of my research has three sources:

- By increasing the spatial scale of the experiment. To produce a reliable and scientifically sound field plot experiment is much more complicated than a growth chamber experiment.
- By addressing the same and complementary research questions in coupled multi-scale experiments (pots and lysimeters, or pots and lysimeters and field plots). This can

¹ TRL - technology readiness level (technology maturity).

usually be done in at least two coupled research projects because of the longer time required to monitor the results in larger-scale experiments.

- By more complex research questions at the same experimental scale, for instance moving to a more extensive set of dependent variables (including functional traits, as explained) and a larger set of independent variables (from two-variate up to four-variate experiments).

To sum up, throughout my career developed after the defense of my doctoral thesis, I focused my research activities on performing experiments carried out at different spatial scales, which were run following the objectives and hypotheses formulated in several fundamental or applied research projects in which I was involved, or that I coordinated. Therefore, all findings presented in this habilitation thesis are derived from these experiments which had as study area either mining sites (Sorge Settendorf and Gessenwiese mine tailing dams from Wismut area, Germany, Valea Mică from Zlatna, Alba county, and Valea Mealu from Certeju de Sus, Hunedoara county also both mine tailing dams) or the former industrial sites (Neferal Pantelimon located in the eastern part of Bucharest, Carbosin, and Sometra industrial platforms from Copsa Mica, Sibiu county, Valea lui Paul near Zlatna, and Meteş, both sites located in Alba county, polluted by atmospheric deposition from the old Zlatna factory, and the Ampelum Zlatna chemical factory, and Alro industrial platform from Slatina, Olt county) all of these being historically polluted with heavy metals.

In chapter B4.2 (Experimental investigations) the findings are grouped as follows:

- Pot experiments
 - A commercial arbuscular mycorrhizal inoculum alleviated the effects of acid water on *Lupinus angustifolius* L. grown in a sterilized mining dump. This was a pot experiment using inoculum with arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) *Glomus radices* and one plant species (*Lupinus angustifolius* L.).
 - Hairy roots mutants of *Nicotiana tabacum* L. resisted better in contaminated soil than the normal plants and had a very strong interaction with mycorrhizal fungi. These results were obtained from a pot experiment using inoculum with AMF (*Rhizophagus irregularis*) and one genetically modified plant species (*Nicotiana tabacum* L.).
 - The effect of AMF inoculation on plants grown in contaminated soil was species- and metal-specific, although plant growth was generally enhanced. Findings from a pot experiment using amendment (expanded clay), AMF inoculum (*Glomus intraradices*), fertilizer (ammonium nitrate) and four plant species (*Phacelia tanacetifolia* Benth., *Sinapis alba* L., *Trifolium pratense* L., and *Helianthus annuus* L.).
 - A pot experiment testing the effects of plant community structure and heavy metals contamination on the leaching of elements and functional traits of plants. Conclusions reached by running a pot experiment with three polluted soils each of them presenting a minimum and a maximum concentration of heavy metals in which were sowed one plant species (*Agrostis capillaris* L.) or two species (*Agrostis capillaris* L. and *Melilotus albus* Medik.). The aim was to test the effects of heavy metals and temperature on the role of grassland plants in producing several biogeochemical services.

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- Lysimeter experiments
 - The extra inoculation of the repacked contaminated soil with *Streptomyces* species reversed the effect of mycorrhization by increasing metal concentrations in the leachate from lysimeters and increased the metals exported by plants by stimulating plant growth.
 - One lysimeter experiment was carried out using amendments (municipal compost, top soil and expanded clay), inoculum with AMF (*Glomus intraradices*), and a mixture of two *Streptomyces* species (*Streptomyces tendae* and *Streptomyces acidiscabies*) and two plant species (*Festuca rubra* L. and *Melilotus albus* Medik.).
 - A second lysimeter experiment was performed without inoculum, with AMF (*Glomus intraradices*) inoculum, and with AMF and *Streptomyces* species (two *Streptomyces* species (*Streptomyces tendae* and *Streptomyces acidiscabies*) and two plant species (the plant crops consisted of 4 alternating successions of *Secale cereale* L. and *Helianthus annuus* L.).
 - Field experiment
 - The effect of soil amendments on plant performance in areas affected by acid drainage. A field plot experiment was run with various amendments (municipal compost, top soil, lime, and fertilization with urea) and two plant species (*Secale cereale* L. single, or mixed with *Lupinus angustifolius* L.).
 - Coupled pot-lysimeter experiment
 - A system *A. capillaris* - compost - PGPB² selected from the rhizosphere of the tailing dam native plants can be an option for the phytostabilisation of tailing dams. Pot and lysimeter scales experiments were performed using amendments (natural commercially available compost), site-specific microbial consortium (PGPB) and six plant species (*Euphorbia pythiusa* L., *Helianthus annuus* L., *Verbascum Thapsus* L., *Deschampsia flexuosa* L., *Agrostis capillaris* L. and *Festuca rubra* L.).
 - Coupled pot-lysimeter-field plot experiments
 - Effects of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi on *Agrostis capillaris* L. grown on amended mine tailing substrate at pot, lysimeter, and field plot scales. Pot, lysimeter and field plot scales experiments were conducted using amendments (top soil, limestone and natural zeolite), 1% and 7% AMF inoculum (mixture of *Glomus intraradices*, *Glomus etunicatum*, and *Glomus claroideum*) and one plant species (*Agrostis capillaris* L.).
 - Two methodological rules for phytostabilization: to account for the spatial geochemical variability of tailings, and cover the broadest possible range of time scales by experiments. Pot, lysimeter, and field plot scales experiments were performed using amendments (top soil, limestone, natural zeolite, and green fertilizer as *Trifolium pratense* L. and *Trifolium repens* L.), and one plant species (*Agrostis capillaris* L.).
 - Optimizing a remediation method on a mine tailing dam. Pot, lysimeter and field plot scales experiments were carried out using amendments (top soil, green fertilizer as *Trifolium pratense* and *Trifolium repens* and expanded clay), 1%, 2% and 7% AMF

² PGPB - plant growth promoting bacteria

inoculum (*Glomus intraradices*), and one plant species (*Agrostis capillaris* L.).

In Part C of the habilitation thesis, I will present plans for the evolution and development of the scientific and didactic career, and Part D includes the references.

All the findings presented in this habilitation thesis, both theoretical and experimental, are partially or fully taken from personally published works, without being processed, or sometimes only slightly modified, thus trying to ensure a good understanding of the scientific research activity carried out in the last 24 years that have passed since the defense of my doctoral thesis. The references cited in the chapters and articles from which I have taken the text included here have not been retained in this thesis to not excessively increase the references list.

The thesis is complementary to other habilitation theses of my colleagues from the University of Bucharest and other research institutions. For processes occurring at spatial scales larger than plot scale and predictive models of dependent variables (especially concentrations of heavy metals), the thesis is complementary to that of Dr. Virgil Iordache, and for details on the plant cover development in the field and the structure of vegetation from contaminated sites is complementary to Dr. Marilena Onete's thesis. This occurred naturally as a result of the interdisciplinary nature of the problem of remediation and management of ecosystem services in heavy metals-contaminated areas

My focus was, first, on demonstrating the basic facts about the analyzed phenomena as a necessary condition for further explanation and decision support. Simply rejecting the null hypothesis about the differences between the average values of the dependent variables in complex soil-plant systems is not trivial, especially as the scale of the experiment is rising from pots to lysimeters and field plots. Even at the pot scale under controlled conditions, the homogeneity of the substrate is never perfect, and the biological response of the plant individuals is, to some extent, variable, so proving an objective response of the system to various amendments and inoculation with fungi or bacteria is a challenge. More complex processing, interpretation, and safe knowledge transfer can be performed only on this solid background of statistically proven scientific facts.

B2 Theoretical contributions

The theoretical contributions evolved from a classing one-element monography (Neagoe 2004) to monographs dedicated to the role of a group of organisms or key variables (organic carbon and fungi, Neagoe et al. 2012, 2013) in the mobility of heavy metals at various scales, and finally to a complex approach of the stress due to heavy metals on plants from individual to site scale (Iordache and Neagoe 2023).

The first theoretical contribution was a monographic synthesis on the chemical element bismuth. It was published in 2004 in the *chapter 5 of the completely revised and enlarged edition of the book „Element and their compounds in the environment edited by E. Merian, M. Anke, M. Ihnat and M. Stoepler, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA.*

The scientific interest in this element came due to my involvement in research in Wismut (which in English means bismuth) area in eastern Germany and from the desire to understand what was the reason why this mining area is named after the chemical element. Thus, I took advantage of the invitation to participate with a monographic chapter in the prestigious book mentioned above, to elucidate what seemed to me at the time a mystery. I thus learned that although the chemical element was officially discovered in 1753 by the French scientist Geoffrey, in reality it is documented that it was first found in Saxony in the 15th century in Metallic Mountains (eastern Germany). This element was first described in 1527 by the alchemist physicist Paracelsus (1493-1541), and the atomic symbol Bi was proposed by Berzelius in 1914. Bismuth was only classified in the 16th century by the mineralogist and metallurgist Georgius Agricola, who recognized the element as a metal. However, it was interesting to discover that although Wismut area was named after the element Bi discovered in that region, the name was chosen strategically, masking the real mining exploitation not of Bi, but of uranium (U). Although this region was named strategically, there is still a connection between the name Bi, and the element U, because Bi is used in the preparation and recycling of nuclear fuel with U. During the communist time, this aspect was a big secret.

Next, I will briefly describe the content of each subchapter I wrote. This chapter is structured into seven subchapters. The first *5.1 Introduction* contains information about the spread of the chemical element in nature, as well as the form in which it is found, both in native and in minerals forms such as bismuthite (bismuth sulfide) and bismite (bismuth oxide). Its primary use in pharmaceutical products is as far as its melting point allows. In principle, Bi was classified as a non-toxic element, but it may have low toxicity to humans.

The second subchapter *5.2 Physical and Chemical Properties, and Analytical Methods* point out the element's place in the periodic table, but also its metallic properties with similarities to lead, arsenic and antimony. Its specific chemical properties have been reviewed, noting that it is the most diamagnetic of all metals and has the lowest thermal conductivity, except mercury. The valence states, the stability of Bi in solution according to their pH were specified, stating that it is stable only at pH ~ 1. The metallic Bi element burns in air with a blue flame, forming yellow vapors of the oxide (BiO₂ - bismite). Other chemical properties were presented, such as its reaction with chloride under warm conditions, as well as with bromide, iodine, sulfur, selenium and tellurite. With sulphuric acid and nitric acid forms salts. Analytical measurement methods were also presented with the detection limits and specific interferences of the commonly used instruments in those years. At the end of this subchapter was also mentioned

the common technique today, namely inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS).

In the next subchapter 5.3 *Sources, Production, Important Compounds, Uses, Waste Products, Recycling* the ores from which metallic Bi is obtained were presented, respectively those sulfide ores of lead and copper, and tin dioxide. It has been stated that most compounds with Bi have an oxidation number 3, but there also are binary compounds such as with halogens (known as halides - BiF₃, BiF₅, BiCl₂, BiBr, BiI₂, BiI₃), with oxygen (known as oxides Bi₂O₃, Bi₂O₅), and with hydrogen (known as hydrides -BiH₃). Many organic compounds of Bi were unknown at that time. From a technological and toxicological point of view, bismuth sulfide, bismuth oxychloride, and salts of inorganic oxoacids (carbonate, nitrate, sulfate) and of organics acids (salicylate, triglycolate, bismuth citrate, gallate, lactate or camphorate) have been identified as of interest. Details about Bi salts are reported in the next paragraph of this subchapter, such as their form, stability and solubility. Further, the applications in which Bi is used are reviewed, specifying that of the world production, approximately 64.5% was used in United States. Of this total, 46% was used in that time, in the pharmaceutical industry and the cosmetics industries, 26% in engineering, and 27% in various metalurgical industries. With other metals such as tin and cadmium, Bi forms low-melting point alloys that are still widely used today for safety devices in fire detection and extinguishing systems. Bismuth is also used as noted, as noted, in the preparation and recycling of uranium nuclear fuel and has found application as a carrier for ²³⁵U or ²³³U fuel in nuclear reactors. By the 1980's, Merck Index listed a total of 27 Bi compounds, of which 18 have pharmaceutical uses. Some of these compounds are medically used to treat stomach or intestinal disorders (i.e. gastric ulcers) in combination with antibiotics. Bismuth compounds (eg bismuth oxide) are used in medicated creams to treat infectious diseases (especially syphilis). Bismuth salicylate subcarbonates, subcitrate, subnitrate, glycobiasol and other salts are used to treat reflux esophagitis, gastritis, indigestion, diarrhea and other gastrointestinal disturbances. Several organometallic compounds of Bi have been used as bactericides and fungicides, as well as dusting powders, astringents and radioopaque agents in X-radiographic diagnosis (now replaced by barium sulfate).

Subchapter 5.4 *Distribution in the Environment, in Foods, and in Living Organisms*. Bismuth is one of the rarest elements, comprising only about 2 10⁻⁵ % of the Earth's crust. It is found in clay sediments, coals and graphite shales. The origin of Bi in most soils is from the parental rock.

- *Bismuth content in plants* was not intensively studied at the level of the 70-90's. However, it has been reported in some *Lycopodium* species, Rocky Mountains trees, in terrestrial plants and in the edible parts of vegetables.
- *Bismuth concentrations in air* have been reported to be lower in rural areas compared to cities. Annually, worldwide, 14 tonnes of Bi were released into the environment as a result of coals combustion, and 190 tonnes through hydrological events.
- *Regarding the human population*, high concentration of Bi in tissues has not been reported, although it has been detected in some foods such as rice flour, wheat flour, spinach and other orchard leaves, corns, potatoes, and soybeans. However, in the the 1990s small amount of Bi excreted in the urine (indicating some gastrointestinal problems), but also in blood were reported. Even lower concentrations of Bi have been detected in terrestrial and

marine animals.

- Although Bi was not detectable in *drinking or river water*, it has been detected in seawater at low concentrations, but also in *rain and lake water*.

Subchapter 5.5 *Uptake, Absorption, Transport and Distribution, Metabolism and Elimination in Plant, Animals, and Humans*. As already mentioned, it was concluded that the toxicity of Bi in an industrial setting was considered non-existent. The exposure of the human population to Bi was and, still is possible through its use for therapeutic purposes and through cosmetic products, finding that it is very well tolerated. Absorption of Bi compounds is slight to moderate by inhalation and through the gastrointestinal tract, depending on its solubility, and can also be absorbed in ionic form. Cutaneous absorption of Bi has also been investigated as cosmetic products containing Bi are used. Minimal toxic symptoms of Bi intolerance have been sporadically reported in the human population. The investigation of Bi absorption was considered necessary in all human body tissues, but this element's storage mechanism was not very clear. The distribution followed by storage of Bi was reported in the metaphyses of children's bones; the highest concentrations were reported in the kidney, followed by the liver, brain, spleen, small intestine, colon, lung etc. Bismuth was found to be able to cross the blood-brain barrier. However, it was concluded that the investigated animals administered Bi compounds by injection showed no apparent signs of neurotoxicity. At higher concentrations, however, Bi compounds induced signs of neurotoxicity. As a detoxification mechanism, Bi can be eliminated by binding to proteins. High concentrations of Bi lead to changes in mitochondrial membranes and activities of enzymes with sulfhydryl functional groups in liver and renal proximal tubular cells. Therefore, Bi toxicity effects were detected in liver and kidney. Excretion of Bi has been reported to be quite fast and its main route of elimination is urinary excretion within 24 h of administration. Elimination of Bi is also possible via bile/feces, but only half of what can be excreted via urine.

Subchapter 5.6 *Effects on Plants, Animals and Humans*. The effect of various Bi compounds on the human population has been tested, and low blood levels have been found. When the "alert" values were exceeded for a short time, no toxic consequences were recorded. Lethal and oral LD₅₀³ doses have been discussed for animals such as rats, as well as for the human population. Toxic effects have only been recorded after intramuscular use of Bi involving kidneys (sometimes extending to necrosis according to, liver and skin as well as epithelial surfaces in intimate contact with bodily fluids. Toxic effects of Bi are strikingly similar to those of Pb, with the few exceptions of peripheral neuropathy and encephalopathy associated only with lead toxicity. There appears to be no relationship between blood level, age, duration, and amount of ingested Bi and the severity of clinical symptoms. Depending on the route of administration and the nature of Bi compounds, various other possible diseases of the human population were analysed. These include intense irritation of the skin or upper respiratory tract and eyes, the "bismuth line" which develops as bluish discoloration of the gums caused by the deposition of Bi sulphide in the fibrous tissue, leads to a permanent generalized discoloration of the skin, ulcerative stomatitis and/or ulcerative colitis, liver degeneration, bone lesions including osteoporosis, encephalopathy with typical symptoms of confusion, hallucinations,

³ LD50 - the dose of a toxic, chemical, radioactive or pathogenic element, capable of killing half of the members of a tested population, in a specific time interval determined.

inability to concentrate, tremors, inability to walk, clumsiness, ataxia and in severe cases coma, epilepsy and death or exfoliative dermatitis. There was no evidence in carcinogenicity, mutagenicity and/or teratogenicity of Bi compounds. Bismuth toxicity in the adult human population was completely reversible when Bi use was stopped in time, while deaths from nephropathy were recorded in children as a results of delayed diagnosis. Bismuth has an adverse effect on microorganisms, making it useful for therapeutic purposes in gastrointestinal disorders, including the reduction of fecal odor in colostomy patients and treatment of peptic ulcer. Various Bi compounds applied to the skin of rats and rabbits lead to intense inflammation and edema, up to local necrosis. Inhalation effects of Bi compounds consisting of pulmonary edema, sometimes eyes irritation or ataxia, restlessness, convulsive seizures, or depression have also been reported in rats, cats and dogs. Rat kidneys are also affected by intramuscular injection of some Bi compounds, sometimes resulting in varying degrees of nephritis or blood pressure of dogs without any significant change in heart rhythm, arrhythmia or hearth block.

Subchapter 5.7 *Hazard evaluation and Limiting Concentrations*. This subchapter specifies the safety limits available in the literature regarding the concentration of Bi in human blood or tissue reported by various authors. When blood Bi levels are between 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, the human population should be treated more carefully. However, few data are available regarding the safe limits of exposure to bismuth metal or any of its compounds.

The second theoretical contribution was a review article published in **2012 in the chapter no. 31 entiteled “The Role of Organic Matter in the Mobility of Metals in Contaminated Sites in Soil Biology” in Kothe E, Varma A (Eds), Bio-Geo Interactions in Metal-Contaminated Soils, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg.**

The aim of this review was “to emphasize the role of a small-scale simple environmental object, the presence of organic matter (OM) in the processes supporting the mobility of metals in a large-scale complex environmental object, i.e., a catchment”. This chapter was very well received by the scientific community (30 citations on Google Scholar in August 2024, which is rare for a chapter) because it addressed all the interdisciplinary literature from all scales relevant to biogeochemical processes.

One of the major conclusions of this review points out that “the number of pseudo-hierarchical levels needed to understand the influence of OC metal mobility in catchments varies with the complexity of the catchments and includes: soil aggregates and other small-scale soil subsystems, soil layer, soil column, site, slope area, elementary catchments, higher order catchments with transversal buffer zones (riparian areas), higher order catchments with longitudinal buffer zones (floodplains)”.

In the table 1 was presented a synthesis of existing knowledge on the role of organic carbon and microorganisms in the mobility of metals and its effects on fluxes in contaminated sites soil layer scale. For organic carbon, whose particle forms are much larger than microorganisms, there is available information also its effects on fluxes occurring site scale, categorized by the type of contaminated sites existing in a contaminated mining area, and at the catchment scale (table 2). Further information can be found in the original chapter.

The third theoretical contribution consisted of a monographic synthesis on arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) and heavy metals, this being published in **2013 in the chapter number 13 entiteled “Upscaling the Biogeochemical Role of Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi in Metal Mobility”**, in *E.M. Goltapeh et al. (eds.), Fungi as Bioremediators, Soil Biology 32, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg*.

My contribution to this chapter was conducting a literature review on AMF. Thus, the recent secondary literature for that period (type of review and meta-analyses) directly and indirectly relevant to assessing the biogeochemical role of AMF was surveyed and summarized in table 3. Comprehensive reviews from taxonomic to structural and functional aspects are available in this table. The focus of our interest in this chapter was on the influence of AMF on plants growing in metal-contaminated areas in the context of phytoremediation studies. Thus, review articles and book chapters on these issues were found in large numbers and also listed in table 3. As our interest also focused on biogeochemical studies at the ecosystem (holistic) scale, we identified articles on the role of AMF in the biogeochemistry of metals, searched by the keyword “arbuscular”, in the journals *Biogeochemistry* and *Ecosystems*. Summing up, we can say that there were 24 primary literature articles dealing with AMF in the entire *Biogeochemistry* collection. These were grouped as follows: 12 related to nitrogen, 3 to organic matter and carbon, 4 to carbon and nitrogen, one to organic matter and minerals, 1 to carbon and phosphorous, 2 to carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus, and one to nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulphur. In the *Ecosystems* journal, I found 15 articles, most of them dealing with nitrogen and carbon, and several with disturbances unrelated to metals contamination. Complementarily, I searched for the same key term in two ecotoxicological journal, *Ecotoxicology*, and *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*.

Table 1 Roles of microorganisms and organic matter observable at soil aggregate scale and their effects on fluxes of metals from soil layers (Neagoe et al. 2012).

Soil layer	Roles	Role by immobilization metals	Role by mobilization of metals	Role by supporting the mobilization or immobilization of metals	Effects on mobility at larger scale
(Aggregates in) Soil layer relevant for plants	Microorganisms	K1 Biosorption, intracellular accumulation, biomineral formation, redox immobilization, metals sorption to biogenic minerals	K1 Chemolithotrophic leaching, chemoorganotrophic leaching, bioweathering, redox mobilization, methylation	K2 Organic matter decomposition, organic acid and siderophores exudates	K3 Transfer of metals to plants, and to lower soil layers
	Organic matter	K1 Immobilization in litter, immobilization in soil aggregates, chelates in fine pores	K1 Organochemical weathering, soluble chelates, organocolloids, free enzymatic degradation of immobile organic carbon	K1 Energy source for microorganisms, buffering of soil solution	
(Aggregates and particles in) Lower soil layers	Microorganisms	K2 Same as in upper layer	K2 Same as in upper layer	K2 Same as in upper layer	K4 Transfer of metals to lower soil layer or to subsoil
	Organic matter	K2 Immobilization in soil aggregates, chelates in fine pores	K2 Same as in upper layer	K2 Same as in upper layer	

Legend of the extent and coherence of existing knowledge: K1 = max to K5 = min

Table 2 Effects of organic matter on fluxes of metals observable at scales ranging from sites and buffer zones to catchments (Neagoe et al. 2012).

Type of entity/effect	Immobilization	Mobilization	Effect at larger scale
Site with contaminated soil in the slope area	K2 Immobilization in litter, immobilization in soil aggregates	K3 Soluble chelates, organocolloids	K4 Transfer to subsoil and groundwater and then to surface water, transfer to surface water by lateral types of flows, transfer to floodplains, volatilization
Mining dump or tailing dam	K3 None, or same as above only in case of organic amendments		
Contaminated soil in the floodplain, contaminated stream ecotone	K3 Immobilization in litter, immobilization in soil aggregates		K4 Transfer to surface water during floods, transfer to groundwater, volatilization
Catchments	K5 Complex influence resulted from mixture of hydrological fluxes and from the retention and turnover of dissolved and particulated organic matter		K5 Export to higher order catchments

I found only 8 articles in the first journal and 13 in the second, about half of which dealt with metals, usually in an experimental setting. I could conclude that information on the role of AMF in holistic approaches to metal biogeochemistry was lacking in the publications of that time, despite the apparent high interest in their use in phytoremediation of contaminated areas, most of the information found was at small-scale.

In table 4 I synthetically grouped the roles of AMF in the mobility of heavy metals, interpreted based of the investigated literature. I could observe at the time that it was a problem to identify AMF individuals, populations and communities, this fact affected the practice of an ecosystemic approach regarding the role of AMF in phytoremediation.

Also, there was no methodology for scaling up information from small-scale functions to large-scale functions. In other words, there was no methodological approach to the spatial delineation of physiological individuals of AMF in real terrestrial ecosystems, and therefore no real estimates could be made of the number of individuals in the populations and the numerical and biomass abundances of the communities to characterize successive changes as might be done for aboveground communities. Thus, discussions of AMF succession and the influence of AMF on plant succession were conducted with these constraints in mind, despite the fact that soil pH, nutrients and organic matter, as well as structural changes in the plant community were considered to be the most important factors of AMF succession. The role of AMF in particular in primary succession have been proven, but was not clear at that time to what extent these statements hold in real systems.

Table 3 Reviews and chapters relevant for the biogeochemical role of AMFs (sources about the use of AMF in agriculture and organic farming not included) The references mentioned in this table can be found in the original chapter, (Neagoe et al.2013).

Topic	Review or chapter
<i>Basic issues</i>	
Species, individuals, populations and communities, hyphal networks of AMF	Taylor et al. (2000), Glass et al. (2004), Rosendahl (2008), Young (2009)
Evolutionary ecology of AMF, selection	Cairney (2000), Mehard and Cairney (2000), Helgason and Fitter (2009), Hartman et al. (2009)
Succession of AMF	Hart et al. (2001), Piotrowski and Rillig (2008)
<i>Interaction with other environmental objects</i>	
Interactions with bacteria	Boer et al. (2005), Bonfante and Anca (2009)
Interactions with rocks and minerals	Hoffland et al. (2004), Gadd (2007, 2010), Rosling et al. (2009), Martino and Perotto (2010)
Influence on aboveground consumers	Moore et al. (2003), Gehring and Bennet (2009), Koricheva et al. (2009)
Interaction with genetically modified plants	Liu (2010)
Use of AMF for induced phytoextraction of metals	Lebeau et al. (2008, 2011)
<i>Effects on ecological processes</i>	
Processes and functions of AMF in ecosystems	Allen et al. (2003), Rillig (2004), Simard and Durall (2004), Goltapeh et al. (2008), Garg and Chandel (2011)
Role of AMF in water circulation	Auge (2001), Allen (2007, 2009, 2010)
Role of AMF in phosphorous cycling	Jansa (2011)
Effect of AMF on plant root systems	Berta et al. (2002), Hodge et al. (2009)
Effect of AMF on soil structure, glomalin	Rillig and Mammey (2006), Treseder and Turner (2007)
<i>Scale and modelling</i>	
Scale of AMF, heterogeneity in space, and modeling	Miller and Kling (2000), Johnson et al. (2006), Chaudary et al. (2008), Wolfe et al. (2009), Johnson (2010)
<i>Biogeochemistry of trace elements, ecotoxicology, management of contaminated sites</i>	
Effects of metals on AMF	Pawlowska and Charvat (2004), Gadd (2005)
Effect of AMF on translocation of metals from soil to plants	Audet and Charest (2007a, 2007b, 2008)
Effect of AMF on improving trace elements deficiency	Cavagnaro (2008)
Effect of AMF on heavy metal tolerance of plants, use in phytoremediation	McGrath et al. (2001), Khan (2005, 2006), Hullebusch et al. (2005), Gohre and Paskovski (2006), Hildrebrandt et al. (2007), Mathur et al. (2007), Giasson et al. (2008), Gamalero et al. (2009), Khan et al. (2009), Wenzel (2009), Smith et al. (2010), Vameralli et al. (2010), Turnau et al. (2010)
Effect of AMF on organic pollutants, use in phytoremediation	Leyval et al. (2002), Brar et al. 2006, Joner and Leyval (2009)

In the following subsections I presented in detail a) the influence of AM fungi on the bioaccumulation of heavy metals in plants, as well as b) the special effects of AM fungi on various HMs and c) the effects of polymetallic pollution on HMs uptake in plants inoculated with AMF and the combination to other microbial communities, there was at that time a vast literature on these topics.

Table 4 Examples of direct roles of AMF and organic matter observable at microscales and of indirect roles observable at scales ranging from pot to lysimeter and to field plot (adapted from Neagoe et al. 2012).

Soil layer	Roles	Direct role by immobilization of metals	Direct role by mobilization of metals	Direct role by supporting the mobilization or immobilization of metals	Indirect roles
Soil layer relevant for plants	AMF	Biosorption, Intracellular accumulation	Chemoorganotrophic leaching, bioweathering	Organic matter decomposition, organic acid and glomalin production	Transfer of metals to plants, and to lower soil layers
	Organic matter	Immobilization in soil aggregates, chelates in fine pores	Organochemical weathering, soluble chelates, organocolloids, free enzymatic degradation of immobile organic carbon	Energy source for microorganisms, buffering of soil solution	

In the fourth theoretical contribution entitled "*Conceptual methodological framework for the resilience of biogeochemical services to heavy metal stress*" published in *Journal of Environmental Management* 325 (2023), 116401 I developed a conceptual model to solve the questions about stoichiometry of elements, functional traits, and biogeochemical services.

The analysis focused on heavy metals (HMs) and temperature as coupled stressors, their effect on root hydro-erosion functional traits, and their consequences on water-mediated elemental fluxes in grasslands. The question was how the amount and stoichiometry of elements in the soil and the temperature control the traits' space of grassland plants. Then, in turn, some of these traits control the elemental fluxes by runoff and leaching, their stoichiometry, and in the long term, the stocks and stoichiometry of elements in the soil (figure 1).

Figure 1 Conceptual model to solve the questions about stoichiometry of elements, functional traits, and biogeochemical services. In red (font and arrows), critical problems are indicated.

We found that integrated frameworks are still not disciplinary robust and refer mainly to large scales. The effects of plant growth conditions, particularly stress factors on the trait's spaces, are approached either by stoichiometry or other functional traits and very seldom on both. The effects of polluting HMs are almost not tackled, although there is some prior indirect knowledge about their effects on C, N, and P biogeochemistry, stoichiometry, and other functional traits.

The trait space theory is more settled, with several complementary approaches. Still, in terms of fitness, the discussion is mainly ecological, lacking a conceptual framework for the relationship between some traits and specific biogeochemical fluxes. Symbiotic traits are very well studied, even their potential mediation of the various stressors' effect on plant variables, but explicit consequences on runoff and leaching are missing. The knowledge about biogeochemical and stoichiometric traits (theoretical and experimental) is young and with many gaps. An even newer area, limited mainly by the considerable investments in infrastructure needed, is the relationship between the elementome and metabolome of organisms. There is a good body of knowledge about the effects of stoichiometric traits on some biogeochemical processes, but little information about the impact on hydro-geomorphological processes. The explicit relation between stoichiometric traits and other functional traits is rarely studied. The body of knowledge about upscaling plant traits to site scale is mostly ecological, with little attention to the local scale effects on water-mediated elemental fluxes. However, there is a complementary field of ecohydrology, geomorphology, and ecological engineering knowledge about the effects of some plant traits on water fluxes, not integrated with the ecological knowledge, as well as a rich general discussion about the impact of plant traits on ecosystem services, but mostly in qualitative and semi-quantitative terms. The information about long-term feedback loops is scarce, not referring to stoichiometry's role in abiotic fluxes. In this context, several coupled hypotheses to be tested in this focused area of research can be formulated (table 5).

Table 5 New hypotheses structured by the conceptual model from figure 1 (from Iordache and Neagoe 2023).

Cause-effect chain / Types of variables	Hypotheses	Rationale
1_2_4	H1a. The increase of temperature leads to higher C:N and C:P ratios in roots and aboveground parts of plant grown in soils contaminated with HMs at pot scale H1b. The relative increase of C:N and C:P ratios due to temperature is positively correlated with the concentrations of HMs concentrations in plant parts at pot scale	As in Sardans and Peñuelas (2012) with the extra stress due to HM.
1_2_4	H2. The increase of temperature leads to a larger amount of N and P exported by leaching after flooding with a fixed amount of water. The relative increase due to temperature in the exported amount of N and P is positively correlated with the HMs concentrations in plants at pot scale	As in Sardans and Peñuelas (2014, figure 3) extrapolated from runoff from plots covered by vegetation to leaching from pots and with the extra effect of HMs.
1_2_4	H3. The effects hypothesized in H1a,b and H2 will be smaller in the case of multispecies pots than in the case of mono-species pots.	The aggregated functional traits at pot scale will be more favorable to nutrients retention in the case of multiple plant species by mechanisms of

Cause-effect chain / Types of variables	Hypotheses	Rationale
1_2_4	H4. The increase in the concentration of metals in soil decrease the retention time of the percolating water and increase the N:P ratio in the seepage water from slope lysimeters	plant interactions. As in Sardans and Penuelas (2014, figure 3) extrapolated from runoff from plots covered by vegetation to leaching from such plots, and developed with the extra effect on plants development due to HMs.
1_2_4	H5. The effects hypothesized in H4a will be smaller when the simulated rain occurs on multispecies lysimeters than in the case of mono-species lysimeters.	It is expected that the multispecies vegetation will resist better to the metal stress
1_2_3_4	H6a. The concentration of HMs in soil is positively correlated with the slope of the positive relationship between the N:P ratios in water and the amount of precipitation produced for erosion plots with 100% plant cover. H6b. The concentration of HMs in soil is positively correlated with the slope of the negative relationship between the N:P ratios in water and the amount of precipitation produced for erosion plots with small plant cover (large area relative cover of bare soil).	As in Sardans and Peñuelas (2014) developed with extra effect on plants development due to HM.
1_2	H7a. The increase of temperature and HMs in soil is inversely correlated with the variability of the physiologically relevant stoichiometric traits in a plant species and with the hypervolume occupied by their nutrients elementome. H7b. The increase of temperature and HMs in soil leads to a stronger discrimination (segregation) between the hypervolumes occupied by the nutrients elementome (the biogeochemical niches) of each plant species.	As in He et al. (2019) and Penuelas et al. (2019) tested for the stress due only to HMs, or in combination with temperature.
1_2	H8. The plant samples scores on the factors extracted from the functional traits space of a plant species are significantly correlated with their stoichiometric traits, with the scores of the factors extracted from their nutrients elementome, and with the scores extracted from their toxic elements elementome.	General multivariate physiological causation (with biogeochemical consequences by the functional traits indirectly controlling the hydrological fluxes and the associated elemental fluxes).
2_3_4_1	H9. The ratios of C:P and N:P in the soil (0-20 cm) contaminated with HMs (HMs) increased more at the time scale of 8 years than at the time scale of 5 years in long term monitored field plots	Ecological succession after the end of disturbance by pollution would lead to accumulation of C and N in the top of soil.
2_3_4_1	H10. The increase of C:P and N:P ratios in the soil (0-20 cm) contaminated with HMs is positively correlated with the aggregated effect traits at the scale of grassland plots and negatively correlated with the bare soil relative cover in long term monitored field plots	Vegetation recovery after disturbance by pollution is associated with response traits facilitating re-colonization, and presumably with a decrease in the bare soil surface

A conceptual advance after testing such hypotheses is the link between the biogeochemical niche and ecological stoichiometry bodies of knowledge and the eco-hydrological one

(extended with elemental transported fluxes) by key plant traits common to both fields. This has consequences for the complex problem approached in this article. The research strategy is different from classic biogeochemical research: instead of reducing the complexity to chemical and physical variables only, understanding the relationship between such variables and biological ones like morphometric and physiological traits controlling water and elemental fluxes (e.g., root length density, stomatal conductance, etc.) is now at stake. This has immediate applications in bio(eco)-agriculture technologies and environmental restoration/remediation. The concept of ecosystem services expresses its importance from a socio-economic and cultural point of view: it provides a deep understanding of the value of functional biodiversity to produce regulation services inside and especially outside of the protected areas and has the potential to improve the attitudes of the public towards biodiversity.

With this last theoretical contribution, the connection with the habilitation theses of my research partners is fully visible, in the interdisciplinarity of the research program dealing with understanding the mechanisms of production and managing the biogeochemical services.

B3 Methodological contributions

In this section I will present in chronological order, the way of organizing at multiple spatial scales, the ecophysiology experiments of plants in the context of phytoremediation of areas contaminated with heavy metals.

My concern for this topic started during a Marie Curie fellowship, research of this type taking place within the „*Influence of Microflora on Heavy Metal Cycles and Water Quality*” (**MIRACLE**) project, contract no: *EVK1-CT-2001-56001*. The key area of expertise I developed as a two-year fellow in a major work package of the mentioned project was "the influence of different microbes on plant uptake of heavy metals/radioisotopes".

To test the goals of the individual Project as a Fellow (FP), I first delineated the context of the problem I was going to address, namely how phyto- and myco-remediation and monitoring could be optimally coupled in highly polluted sites. In this project we were involved three post doctoral fellows (FP 1 - applied geology, me as FP2- applied botany, and FP3 - applied microbiology) together with senior researchers, one from each mentioned fields.

The context of the problem

In a highly polluted site plants are usually used to stabilize the soil surface and thereby mitigate the export of metals through runoff and soil erosion. Another technique is to couple phytoremediation with the use of microorganisms, which are believed to reduce plant stress by immobilizing metals in the soil to some extent. The fine roots of plants influence the availability and uptake of metals from the soil by small changes in soil conditions in the rhizosphere: slightly lower pH and increased amount of different organic molecules in this exudation zone.

Dissolved organic carbon in soil plays a key role in the understanding the processes occurring in the rhizosphere, as well as of the mechanisms of metal mobility or immobilisation. Both the rhizosphere population and most mycorrhizal fungi have been found to depend on carbon input provided by current or recent photosynthesis by the host plant, rather than carbonaceous detritus from litterfall or dead roots. High-affinity iron-binding molecules called siderophores have been identified in soil, produced by some rhizosphere bacteria, soil fungi, and some mycorrhizal fungi. Such a compound may also have some function in protecting both fungi and plants from metal toxicity. Another resistance mechanism is the binding of metals to hyphal cells, decreasing the concentration of metals in the soil solution surrounding the roots. It must be pointed out, however, that organic chelates have also been used to make soil metals more available for plant uptake in the event of micronutrient deficiency. Ectomycorrhizas envelop the roots and can provide protection against metals, but AMF can either decrease metal concentrations in the plant at high metal concentrations, or increase it at low concentrations. Indirect effects of AMF on metal uptake can occur through more intensive plant development as a result of increased uptake of macronutrients by AMF. Many mycorrhizal species show marked sensitivity to soil metals, but there is some evidence of the evolution of metal-tolerant mycorrhizal fungi in contaminated soils. It is important to note that resistance of microorganism strains (and probably fungi) to heavy metals can be associated with increased production of organic molecules. For example, yields of white and red clover were shown to be decreased by high concentration of Zn and Cu in the soil, but the effect was not due to direct phytotoxicity of the metals; nitrogen fixation appears to be affected. Streams of *Rhizobium* in metal-contaminated sites usually have a non-specific metal tolerance, such as increased excretion of

extracellular polysaccharides, rather than a metal-specific mechanism. The pH of soil solution has a very important effect in controlling both passive and active uptake mechanisms. Analogous to the dissociation that occurs on the hydroxyl groups on the surfaces of soil clay, the increased pH of the micelles causes the dissociation of carboxylic and phenolic groups on the cell walls, increasing the cation exchange capacity of the cell wall. However, not all metals are expected to mobilise, and generally in heavily polluted soils, metals tend to remain in the upper soil horizon. The microflora on the surface of soil particles limit the metal ion exchange process, which leads to the accelerated leaching of metals. In conclusion, mycorrhizal fungi and bacteria, as well as plant roots, all contribute organic molecules to the rhizosphere. These molecules can make metals less available or more available to plants, depending on the types of molecules and soil conditions. In addition, soil fungi and bacteria can facilitate metal leaching, either by blocking exchange sites on the surface of soil particles or by producing low-mass organic molecules, depending on other soil conditions. However, the possibilities of using different mycorrhizal fungi as biofilters in a combined phyto-mycoremediation were not established until early 2003. I also found at that time that plant biology could be used as an additional parameter in the combination with the microbiological criteria for optimizing the stress indications of a specific ecosystem.

Objectives

In this context, the problem to be solved was to answer the following questions for the specific case of polluted soils of Wismut:

- What is the optimal level of soil microorganism populations to decrease the toxicity of soil metals to plants, but not facilitate leaching of metals to groundwater?
- How is this optimum level influenced by rainfall quality (especially pH)?
- How could the effects of acid precipitation on metal mobility be counteracted?

Based on the problem formulated above, our *purpose as follows (FPs)* was to evaluate the influence of different microbes on plant uptake of heavy metals/radioisotopes.

To achieve this goal we have identified three operational objectives:

1. In situ monitoring of key soil, water, microbial and plant parameters.
2. Laboratory-scale assessment of the influence of plants, microorganisms and precipitation pH on metal immobilization and leaching.
3. Field-scale experiment to evaluate the influence of microorganisms and vegetation on the immobilization and mobilization of metals.

Objective 1 considered the characterization of the current leaching of metal in the soil profile (link to FP3 - applied geology), the presence of microbes typical of the rhizosphere (link to FP1 - microbiology), the transfer of heavy metals to plants and the response to plant stress (link to FP2 applied botany). The laboratory experiment performed by me as FP2 under objective 2 focused in particular on developing knowledge about the relationships between microorganisms and plants and how they influence the immobilization/mobilization of metals. The results of objective 2 were directly relevant to FP3 (applied geology) and aimed at explaining the leaching rates observed in the field (objective 1). The results of objective 2 together with the results of the first year of monitoring (objective 1) allowed the correct design of the field experiment carried out within objective 3, which aimed in particular to establish the optimal myco-phytoremediation solution for the Wismut site.

Innovation

As a FP2, I contributed to the development of the standardized assessment of metal toxicity in contaminated soils and to the development and long-term monitoring of *in-situ* contaminated soils. Different technologies have been combined for a purpose at the interface of microbiology, botany and geology. Combined plant-microbial effects on metal mobilization and immobilization in a uranium mining area were assessed for the first time.

This research combined different methods such as column leachate studies, *in-situ* field studies, down profile soil sampling, followed by chemical extraction of metals with a study on the influence of vegetation and microorganisms found in the experimental soil.

The proposed work packages (WPs) were formulated to correspond to the expertise of the three FPs who were involved in this research project, and were:

We formulated the proposed work packages (WPs) to match the expertise of us, the three FPs involved in this research project and were:

- WP1: Field monitoring - consisted of *in-situ* monitoring of chemical, microbiological and plant variables.
- WP2: Laboratory experiments - included the design and running of the laboratory experiments to assess the effect of microorganisms to both, plants (metals accumulation and stress) and leachate.
- WP3: Mezocosm and field experiments - included a zero-tension lysimeter experiment to prove the success of the laboratory experiment and obtain information on leachate, and a field plot experiments was conducted to obtain key findings for the best myco- and phytoremediation and monitoring practices at the Wismut polluted area.

At that time, I did not make the connection between the absolute necessity of running the three types of experiments in succession, before making the final decision to move to a larger experimental scale. The experiments were based on the use of biotechnological methods available at the time with the intention for implementing the results in large-scale field investigations. All three work packages had specific deliverables. The results consisted in data, reports, and scientific articles available to researchers, public and end-users, according to their specificity. The structure of fellows' project, the flow of information within the project (solid arrows) and the connections with other fellow's projects (dashed arrows) are presented in figure 2.

Next, I will briefly describe what was proposed and performed in each work package.

WP1: field monitoring

My personal contribution as FP2 was to identify the dominant plant species in the Wismut polluted area (figure 3), and to conduct a literature review to identify which defence mechanisms against heavy metals have been reported to be the most important for plant species (subcellular compartmentalisation, exudation of organic ligands from roots and phytochelatines). I proposed a screening of soil macro and micronutrients in the investigated area (Gessenwiese from Wismut area) (in cooperation with FP 3 - applied geology), in order to identify possible cases of deficiency or toxicity levels, that could influence the processes occurring after microbial enrichment (plant uptake facilitation due to the production of organic

chelates). I sampled soil in the study area for the laboratory experiments and characterized it for the key properties likely to influence the reaction, mobility and transformation of metals (in cooperation with FP3). It was proposed to establish microbial community characterization techniques by FP1 (microbiology). Microorganisms were analysed in cooperation with FP1 (microbiology) during overlapping fellowship periods.

Figure 2 The structure of fellows' project, the flow of information within the project (solid arrows) and the connections with other fellow's projects (dashed arrows)

The variables measured to assess contamination and stress in plants were: aboveground biomass, metals concentrations in shoots, enzymes activity in shoots (superoxide dismutase, peroxidase), lipid peroxidase (LP) in shoots, chlorophyll and carotenoid content. The plant species analysed were those found to be dominant (in terms of above ground biomass) on the site: clover species (*Trifolium pratense* L., *Trifolium repens* L., *Melilotus albus* L., *Anthyllis vulneraria* L., *Medicago lupulina*); burdock species (*Tussilago farfara* L.), camomile species (*Maticaria inodora* L.), bush vetch (*Vicia sepium* L.), species and birch tree (*Betula pendula* L.). The hydrological variables were analysed and assessed by FP3 (applied geology). The set of hydrological variables was complemented by down-profile soil sampling followed by chemical extraction of metals to obtain additional information to explain the leaching in different soil layers.

WP2: laboratory experiments

I proposed and subsequently performed an experimental unit consisting of two pot-scale experiments using several soil types, cultivated with different plant species and incubated with microorganisms. In the case of the first laboratory experiment I used a single type of soil and four plant species to assess the influence of microorganisms (AMF - *Glomus intraradiceae*, currently *Rhizophagus irregularis*) on plant species grown on a soil contaminated with heavy metals. I used the following plant species: phacelia (*Phacelia tanacetifolia* Benth.), sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.), clover (*Trifolium pratense* L.) and mustard (*Sinapis alba* L.). I proposed and carried out a second laboratory experiment in which I used three soil types, two

plant species (lupins - *Lupinus angustifolius* L. and sunflower - *Helianthus annuus* L.), and two types of water supply (neutral and acidic pH), some of the treatments were incubated with microorganisms. For this experiment, I sampled soil from different points to capture the heterogeneity of the contaminated area.

Figure 3 Left: Overview of the entire Wismut mining area area polluted with heavy metals (source: Wismut GmbH); right: Gessenhade (or Gessenwiese) characterized by strong acid mine drainage (source: Erik Carlsson) (Neagoe et al. 2011).

Both laboratory experiments were later published, the first with the title “Patterns of *Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi* effects on plants grown in contaminated soil” in *Journal of Plant Nutrition and Soil Science* (2013) 176, 273-286, DOI: [10.1002/jpln.201200079](https://doi.org/10.1002/jpln.201200079), and the second one with the title “A Commercial Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Inoculum Alleviated the Effects of Acid Water on *Lupinus angustifolius* Grown in a Sterilized Mining Dump” in *Plants* (2023) 12(10), 1983, doi.org/10.3390/plants12101983. These publications are presented in detail in the section B4.2.1

WP3: lysimeter and field plot experiments

For the proposed mezocosm-scale experiment, I included a quantitative assessment of leachate and simulated rainfall in the field (similar pH and intensity). This research was published as „The effect of bioremediation methods involving different degrees of soil disturbance on the export of metals by leaching and by plant uptake” in *Geochemistry* (2009), 69, 57-73, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemer.2008.01.002> and described in section B4.2.2.

In this experiment I assessed influence of the dimension of microbial inoculum on the plant accumulation / stress and on the metals leaching. The type of inoculum have been set based on the results of the laboratory experiments. Plants, soil, and leachate have been characterized by the same variables as in the laboratory experiments.

The first field-scale experiment was designed, conducted later published as "Effect of soil amendments on plant performance in an area affected by acid mine drainage", in *Geochemistry* (2005) 65, 115-129, <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemer.2005.06.009> and presented in section B4.2.3.

On this background, in chapter Neagoe et al. (2013) we have summarized our main past experimental findings and proposed an integrate multi-scale experimental approach (methods and extended results can be found in the sources mentioned in table 6: (1) plants response to inoculation is species specific, but there is a general pattern of positive response in terms of biomass increase and decrease of oxidative stress; (2) plant-specific response depends on environmental conditions and plant community structure; plants classified as non-host may benefit from inoculation in highly contaminated soils; (3) large-scale (field plot) response to artificial inoculation and monospecific cultivation is modulated by seed bank and natural inoculation from clean soil amendment; (4) inoculation may increase the relative importance of plants compared to leachate in the export of metals, but this depends on the rhizosphere microbial community structure (bacteria co-inoculated with AMF influenced the dynamics of soil redox potential and metal toxicity) and on soil variable heterogeneities at meter scale.

Next, we outlined a research opportunity provided by the challenge of myco-phytoremediation of contaminated areas using selected plants and commercial inoculums. Operationally, we developed a multi-scale (pot, lysimeter, field plot) experimental approach to the biogeochemical role of AMF in metal mobilities that addresses scale-specific issues, which can be further generalized for other problems relevant to the mobility of heavy metals.

Table 6 Experimental approach at three scales for the study of AMF roles in metal mobility. The references from this table can be found in the cited chapter), (Neagoe et al. 2013 adapted from Iordache et al. 2012).

Name of the system and usual scales	Environmental complex system studied at these scales	Patterns studied / control variables	Reference for detailed methodology
Pot 10^{-2} m^2	Soil + plants + AMF	Exploration by root, bioaccumulation/ organic carbon, other microorganisms, level and spatial structure of amendments	Neagoe et al. (2004), Iordache et al. (2004), Stancu et al. (2010).
Lysimeter $10^{-1} - 10^0 \text{ m}^2$	Soil + plants + AMF + small scale hydro-system	Same as in pots + leaching, internal redistribution, net outputs / same as in pots + soil structure, hydraulic conductivity, humidity, redox potential in soil profile	Neagoe et al. (2006), Iordache et al. (2006), Visan et al. (2008), Neagoe et al. (2009), Nicoara et al. (2010).
Plot $4 \times 10^0 - 10^2 \text{ m}^2$	Soil + plants + AMF + other organisms	Same as in pots + heterogeneity in space, margin effects, other effects due to external entities (natural seed bank, consumers) / same as in pots + variables for external entities.	Neagoe et al. (2005, 2010).

B4 Field and experimental results

B4.1 Field investigations

Response of oxidative stress variables, proteins and chlorophyll in several plant species caused by moderate soil pollution with toxic elements

This research was published by *Păun et al. 2015* with me as corresponding author, *in the Polish Journal of Environmental Studies, Vol. 24, No. 3, 1219-1234*, in an article with the same title as of this subchapter, (<https://doi10.15244/pjoes/30935>).

The study that I will present here is part of a larger research that, after investigating the area to obtain information related to the degree of heavy metal pollution, was completed with proposed solutions for phytoremediation, formulated following experiments carried out on the pot- scale. The experimental results were separately published and will not be presented here, as is similar to other pot-scale experiments that will be discussed in the following sections.

The objective of the research reported here was to describe how the biochemical variables selected to be analyzed varied in three plant parts of three plant species sampled from two areas with different levels of pollution. It started from the idea that an early detection of metabolic changes in plants can help to assess the possibility of using them as bioindicators of heavy metals in soil. We hoped that following this study, the obtained results would allow the researchers to focus on establishing and implementing of a coherent program of remediation of metal-polluted industrial areas, a program supported by a permanent monitoring of oxidative stress variables. We were interested in finding out to what extent the patterns of biochemical variables affected by pollution can differ depending on the plant species and plant parts analyzed.

Field conditions, sampling design and measured variables

For this research, three plant species were selected from the spontaneous flora, thus two of them are herbaceous plants, dandelion (*Taraxacum officinale* L.) and plantain (*Plantago major* L.), and the third, a clover, is a legume (*Lotus corniculatus* L.). These species were selected according to the criterion of dominance in the area and to their relatively high tolerance to heavy metal pollution. Both soil and plant samples were sampled from two different areas located near the pollution source: an area approximately 250 m away, coded A, and another one, on the same side as the pollution source, 2 km away from it, in a supposedly unpolluted meadow, coded B. Additionally, soil samples were sampled from the rhizosphere by shaking the plants directly in polyethylene bags, from all the plant species sampled, totaling a number of 54 samples of which 27 from area A and 27 from area B. The source of pollution was the largest aluminum producing company in Central and Eastern Europe (except for Russia) located in Romania (geographic coordinates: 44° 26' 13" N, 24 ° 22' 12" E in the WGS84 system). Documents were found claiming that those industrial activities led to fluoride and heavy metal pollution that affected crops, pastures, and spontaneous vegetation in the vicinity of the aluminum plant, contaminating surface and groundwater, and consequently, on the food chain, they affected both animal and human populations. All soil samples were sampled from a depth of 0-10 cm, in a representative amount for A1 and A which are small sub-areas located around the polluted source. After homogenization, six replicates were used for each sub-area. From area B (coded B1 in the mirror with A1 and A2), a number of 50 samples were sampled directly from the field, to verify the assumption of an unpolluted area. Seven replicates of *Taraxacum officinale* L., ten replicates of *Lotus corniculatus* L. and also ten replicates of *Plantago major* L. were

sampled from each investigated area. They were separated into the roots and above-ground part of the plants (the stem together with the leaves, and the inflorescence separately). These were hereafter referred to as species 1, species 2 and species 3.

Variables measured from soil samples

The following variables were measured: pH, humidity (H), electrical conductivity (EC), ammonium (N-NH₄⁺), nitrate (N-NO₃⁻), nitrite (N-NO₂⁻), phosphate (P-PO₄³⁻), pseudo-total content of elements and the bioavailable fraction content of elements.

Variables measured from plant samples

The following variables were measured: element content after wet digestion, protein content, enzyme activity such as superoxide dismutase (SOD) and peroxidase (POD), lipid peroxidase (LP) and, photosynthetic pigments (chlorophyll a and b and carotenoids).

Selected findings

It can be seen in table 7 that the soil samples were different, thus in A1 and B1 the pH was acid, while in A2 it was neutral according to the INRA classification. Regarding the nitrogen content, in A1 and A2 there was a very low level in all measured samples, while in B1 the concentration was higher, which could be considered sufficient for the development of many plants. The available phosphorus showed in all the measured samples high concentrations considered optimal values for the development of many plant species. Electrical conductivity (EC) recorded low values, corresponding to the non-saline soil class (0-2 mS cm⁻¹). In all investigated areas, as can be seen in table 7, the pseudo total content of As, Cr, Mn and Ni elements was detected above acceptable values for plant growth in soil. On the other hand, Pb and Zn were found in acceptable concentrations for plant growth in soil. The bioavailable fraction of the elements can be seen in table 8.

Variables measured from the rhizosphere soil were reported in table 9 and showed that the soils were acidic for all the samples both in A, and in area B areas, only for the dandelion rhizosphere, in the other two rhizospheres it was neutral. Both the investigated sub-areas A1 and A2 and area B1 belong to the category of non-saline soils. In sub-areas A1 and A2 all rhizospheric soils contained a low level of N concentration (values below 20 µg g⁻¹ d.w.), while in B area, the concentration of mineral nitrogen was ranged between 61-100 µg g⁻¹ d.w., which is characteristic of soils with a high supply level. Phosphate content showed a similar pattern to mineral nitrogen, with lower values in A area, and higher values in B area. In A area, pseudo-total concentrations of As, Cr, Mn and Ni were found in the acceptable range for plants that can be used by the human population. A deficit level was recorded for Cu. Mobile forms of elements were found in rhizosphere soil similar to those found in soil samples from sub-areas A1, A2 and area B1 (see table 9). It is known that to minimize the availability of toxic metals, soil pH should be maintained around 6.5. As expected in our studies, the mobilization of elements except P increased as a result of acidic soil pH, as can be seen in table 9.

Further, all data were analyzed using 2-way ANOVA and a transformation (either log response or 1/response) was applied to the response variable when required. Data normalization was requested; the assumption of normality was checked by plotting the data on a Q-Q plot and checking whether the points followed the line of equality. If they did, the assumption of normality was satisfied. p-values and 75% confidence intervals were also calculated using the

adjusted values. If $p > 0.05$ means there was no interaction factor, in which case it was removed. Pairwise confidence intervals were calculated and Pearson's correlation was also performed between the concentration of elements in the soil and their concentrations in different parts of the plant. For all cases where data were adjusted, p values and 95% confidence intervals were calculated using the adjusted values.

Table 7 Physico-chemical characterization of soils from investigated area. * n = number of replicates; ** BDL = Below Detection Limit ($< 2\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$ N-NO₂⁻) (adapted after Păun et al. 2015)

	Variable unit	pH	EC	H	N-NH ₄ ⁺	N-NO ₃ ⁻	N-NO ₂ ⁻	P-PO ₄ ³⁻
		H ₂ O	[$\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$]	[%]	[$\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ d.w.]			
A ₁	\bar{x}	5.84	35.33	14.38	6.156	3.587	BDL	30.16
($n^* = 6$)	s	0.06	8.164	1.920	0.229	1.228	-	13.08
A ₂	\bar{x}	6.63	54.66	15.94	6.826	4.661	BDL	50.58
($n = 6$)	s	0.27	19.32	5.48	0.244	3.01	-	30.40
B1	\bar{x}	5.27	16.74	9.678	9.908	36.32	0.560	53.27
($n=50$)	s	0.338	9.448	1.023	1.807	22.86	0.405	26.94

Table 8 Element content (pseudo-total digested in *aqua-regia*) (adapted after Păun et al. 2015).

	Variable unit	As	Cu	Cr	Mn	Ni	Pb	Zn
		[$\mu\text{g}/\text{g}^{-1}$ d.w.]						
A ₁	\bar{x}	13.77	16.90	130.9	841.3	72.67	22.89	76.65
($n^* = 6$)	s	0.42	1.38	12.14	71.5	46.96	0.82	2.29
A ₂	\bar{x}	12.95	16.33	109.9	998.2	52.88	20.52	72.63
($n = 6$)	s	1.291	0.501	2.02	2.069	6.26	11.19	6.59
B1	\bar{x}	7.880	18.52	28.31	440.2	50.98	26.43	77.22
($n=50$)	s	2.228	3.43	6.935	105.0	25.66	4.99	29.63

Table 9 Element content (bioavailable fraction extracted in NH₄NO₃ 1M) (adapted after Păun et al. 2015).

	Variable unit	As	Cu	Cr	Mn	Ni	P	Pb	Zn
		[$\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ d.w.]							
A1	\bar{x}	0.022	0.2449	0.946	22.18	0.852	6.509	0.104	1.683
($n = 6$)	S	0.003	0.158	0.166	0.117	0.117	0.430	0.029	0.360
A2	\bar{x}	0.016	1.690	0.752	18.37	0.689	9.980	0.077	1.820
($n = 6$)	S	0.000	0.138	0.070	1.987	0.075	0.777	0.003	0.171
B1	\bar{x}	0.010	2.630	0.145	13.71	0.514	10.68	0.047	1.440
($n=6$)	S	0.002	0.579	0.579	3.018	0.113	1.397	0.019	0.264

If the p -value of the interaction factor was greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$), it means that there was no interaction factor, in which case it was removed. Subsequently, p -values of species and polluted areas were calculated without considering the p -value of the interaction factor. In addition, to compare each 2 species (1-2, 1-3, 2-3), we used the Tukey-all pairs approach (data not shown here for space reason). Confidence intervals allowed us to assess the practical significance of differences between means in addition to statistical significance. If the confidence interval did not contain the value zero, it means that there was no difference between the means. The results of the ANOVA test and the Tukey comparison may conflict. For example, it is possible for ANOVA to reject the hypothesis that there are no differences between

level means and yet all Tukey-pairwise confidence intervals contain the value zero. Considering the issues highlighted above, we could observe that there were statistically significant differences between species in the case of N-NO₂⁻, P-PO₄³⁻, Mn and Pb (table 10). Furthermore, for most variables, there were statistically significant differences between polluted areas. In other words, the contents of N-NO₃⁻, N-NO₂⁻, P-PO₄³⁻, Mn and Cr were different in the two polluted areas. Each two species were then compared to see where they differed. This was done by calculating 95% confidence intervals for the means of the soil variables. We could see that in the case of N-NO₂⁻ and Pb, there was a difference between species 1 and 2, and 1 and 3. In addition, the content of P-PO₄³⁻ was different between species 1 and 2. For all others no there was sufficient evidence of a difference between plant species, as the 95% confidence interval did not contain the value zero. We can see that the two-way ANOVA provided a difference between species for Mn (a p value = 0.015 < 0.05), the Tukey comparison that there was no evidence for a difference, which still demonstrated since these two sometimes be in conflict.

Table 10 Soil variables and the elements content in the the three plants rhizospheres (adapted after Păun et al. 2015).

Soil variables	Units	Area (A)			Area (B)		
		Dandelion	Clover	Plantain	Dandelion	Clover	Plantain
pH		5.24±50.154	7.60±0.193	7.50±0.186	5.03±0.100	6.05±0.127	5.74±0.106
EC	[μS cm ⁻¹]	30.71±3.302	102.5±15.11	125.9±14.18	92.00±13.12	110.7±22.23	102.2±13.45
H	[%]	16.23±6.106	13.37±3.458	12.12±3.821	4.424±0.679	7.877±1.770	7.223±0.803
N-NH ₄ ⁺		1.360±0.762	1.674±0.489	1.931±0.413	10.70±5.802	12.05±4.373	8.711±2.014
N-NO ₃ ⁻		10.56±5.462	9.480±8.071	5.702±6.452	48.28±36.19	97.34±79.50	77.02±41.79
N-NO ₂ ⁻		0.110±0.039	0.295±0.095	0.274±0.076	0.439±0.133	0.789±0.339	0.645±0.252
P-PO ₄ ³⁻		14.75±4.679	18.77±3.984	16.42±8.680	18.39±2.407	35.53±5.820	22.54±2.027
As ^a		<u>8.652±1.850</u>	<u>8.683±1.533</u>	<u>10.13±1.548</u>	4.387±0.478	4.278±0.779	3.931±0.111
As ^b		0.010±0.004	0.007±0.002	0.008±0.001	0.008±0.002	0.004±0.001	0.003±0.001
Cr ^a		<u>95.88±6.238</u>	<u>102.7±9.410</u>	<u>119.5±8.701</u>	25.83±3.035	22.66±2.992	24.68±4.507
Cr ^b		0.798±0.112	<u>0.583±0.050</u>	0.571±0.114	0.269±0.036	0.175±0.026	0.213±0.409
Cu ^a		30.29±7.824	26.30±5.893	25.26±5.186	27.52±8.766	27.44±5.674	29.51±3.487
Cu ^b		2.098±0.605	1.161±0.246	1.058±0.210	1.777±0.479	1.200±0.294	1.427±0.203
Mn ^a		<u>851.3±147.1</u>	<u>655.7±123.9</u>	<u>735.6±131.4</u>	352.7±64.29	323.8±44.01	321.9±61.45
Mn ^b		17.15±2.577	11.48±2.007	13.78±2.489	15.06±2.565	11.17±1.585	12.17±2.432
Ni ^a		<u>69.80±15.50</u>	<u>89.27±20.54</u>	<u>98.71±16.91</u>	29.16±4.637	36.73±6.020	29.79±4.507
Ni ^b		<u>1.760±0.320</u>	<u>1.470±0.326</u>	<u>1.552±0.233</u>	1.266±0.201	1.103±0.181	1.171±0.204
P ^a		655.0±77.40	744.5±51.26	699.1±58.69	681.9±40.92	798.6±72.48	741.0±45.77
P ^b		10.94±0.727	13.01±0.781	11.68±0.809	12.01±1.201	13.50±1.382	12.99±0.716
Pb ^a		16.18±3.346	11.57±3.739	11.84±2.467	19.73±7.001	11.88±4.011	11.13±2.867
Pb ^b		0.084±0.015	0.043±0.027	0.053±0.022	0.068±0.024	0.044±0.008	0.058±0.010
Zn ^a		67.31±13.26	76.93±8.335	73.24±8.231	101.4±33.28	113.2±48.84	69.71±5.352
Zn ^b		2.12±0.360	1.51±0.322	1.82±0.254	2.533±0.831	1.883±0.813	2.074±0.098

Legend: underlined values exceed the acceptable level in soil for the plants used by human population already presented above. a -aqua regia, b -ammonium nitrate.

Table 11 shows the concentrations of the elements measured in all parts of the plants sampled both from the investigated areas A and B. Although the plants developed vigorously, a level of pollution was recorded. It can be seen that the roots had a higher metal content than the aboveground parts of plants.

Table 11 Element concentration in plants (average and standard deviations) (adapted after Păun et al. 2015).

Plant parts	Elements	Unit	Area (A)			Area (B)		
			Dandelion	Clover	Plantain	Dandelion	Clover	Plantain
Roots	As	$\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ d.w.	0.593±0.063	0.517±0.110	0.689±0.218	0.423±0.053	0.422±0.059	0.378±0.099
	Cr		7.643±2.299	7.204±2.705	7.684±2.690	1.340±0.577	1.039±0.589	1.507±0.741
	Cu		13.31±1.605	11.18±3.421	12.70±1.012	13.33±3.301	15.25±3.381	16.99±3.543
	Mn		131.1±64.86	31.68±24.58	37.50±11.94	40.09±10.17	44.76±11.78	47.89±13.09
	Ni		13.86±3.118	9.113±5.066	5.221±1.050	1.973±1.206	2.028±1.149	3.706±1.689
	Pb		4.430±1.754	3.896±2.828	4.498±1.571	8.441±5.275	4.482±4.653	6.803±2.375
	Zn		59.74±27.48	38.41±18.44	80.00±23.62	72.63±11.86	64.26±26.38	92.29±19.81
	P		937.5±166.8	923.2±108.9	2611±210.0	1684±621.5	2019±865.9	3199±996.2
Aboveground	As	0.446±0.109	0.449±0.078	0.445±0.058	0.399±0.042	0.359±0.020	0.329±0.139	
	Cr	5.634±2.466	3.864±1.454	6.929±5.328	0.798±0.249	0.864±0.521	0.835±0.363	
	Cu	4.122±0.839	7.582±1.276	5.417±1.126	6.597±2.585	7.205±0.085	6.269±0.623	
	Mn	80.45±16.40	34.20±7.503	37.97±27.85	38.00±10.06	41.47±9.562	45.09±12.40	
	Ni	7.636±4.524	4.196±1.523	4.570±4.025	0.628±0.713	0.822±0.465	1.057±0.358	
	Pb	2.916±0.947	3.305±1.265	4.271±2.190	6.796±1.059	3.996±1.196	5.901±1.116	
	Zn	14.79±4.705	20.46±5.130	24.58±11.26	27.52±13.17	28.74±27.58	32.20±24.19	
	P	733.0±207.8	1315±246.9	2686±212.3	623.1±565.7	1331±510.8	3077±501.8	
Inflorescence	As	0.419±0.037	0.449±0.116	0.362±0.057	0.247±0.019	0.242±0.030	0.239±0.256	
	Cr	4.200±0.965	6.856±4.597	2.446±1.443	0.630±0.218	0.572±0.289	0.557±0.221	
	Cu	9.479±1.326	9.368±1.276	6.452±1.687	5.094±0.997	5.993±0.961	5.120±1.451	
	Mn	108.0±17.97	25.99±5.136	24.38±12.92	51.88±15.56	85.33±61.19	66.55±48.03	
	Ni	11.63±1.379	9.510±2.078	2.309±0.957	0.354±0.357	0.671±0.146	0.596±0.486	
	Pb	3.971±1.603	3.706±1.613	2.645±1.494	6.034±4.108	7.039±4.054	5.996±2.521	
	Zn	33.56±4.440	34.04±5.615	28.56±13.35	44.45±11.95	48.05±22.12	31.43±11.91	
	P	1290±328.7	1364±525.6	1845±712.3	1502±301.6	1953±410.0	2826±540.6	

In the case of clover and plantain, Mn concentrations were even higher in their inflorescence in area B as a result of increased mobility probably due to the decreased of soil pH. This was confirmed in the case of dandelion, for which soil pH had almost similar values. In this case the Mn concentration did not increase in the plants sampled from area B. It was actually lower in all part plants as a consequence of concentration alleviation in soil. We mentioned that both Cr and Ni registered excessive or toxic values in almost all plant parts for both areas ($> 0.1 - 0.5 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ Cr and $> 0.5 - 1 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ Ni). The other element presented into the table 11 did not exceed the acceptable level in plants. After advanced statistical data processing (can be found in the original article) the content of both P and toxic element in plant parts was significantly different in the A and B polluted areas. In roots, there seemed to be no evidence of a difference for Mn and Pb between areas, whereas in the aboveground parts there was no evidence of a difference in the Mn content between the two areas. The plots from figure 4 show that not all elements and pseudo-total contents of P in soil are correlated with the concentrations found in the three

parts of the plants from the A and B areas.

Figure 4 Correlations between the concentrations of heavy metals and P in soil and plant parts (Păun et al. 2015).

Also, the diagram from figure 5 shows the distribution of toxic elements and P in plant parts and soil. This was done by considering each polluted area separately, in order to spot the differences between the two areas. Thus, it could be observed that the As, Cr, Mn and Ni content in soil was higher in A area, than in B area. The higher concentrations in the case of clover and plantain in A area could also be caused by the fact that the pH increases As solubilization and the potential bioaccumulation of this element into the food chain, depending of course, on their speciation which exist in soils. Similar patterns of variation sown in figures 4 and 5 were found in the case of element concertation in the bioavailable forms (data not shown).

Figure 5 Histograms showing the distribution of heavy metals and P in plant parts (Păun et al. 2015).

Next, I will present the enzymatic and non-enzymatic measured variables in plants. The values of SOD and POD activities of all three plant species grown in A and B areas can be seen in table 12. Moreover, it could be observed that when the pollution was stronger (A area), the protein content decreased significantly in all three parts of the plant ($p < 0.05$). This protein content consequently led to an increase in enzymatic activities, so SOD and POD activity was more intense in the roots, followed by inflorescence and then the aboveground part of the plants. The same pattern of variation was noticed for POD activities. For biochemical variables,

statistically significant differences were recorded between polluted area A and B in most parts of the three plant species. The content of proteins, SOD, and POD in roots and in florescence was statistically different between areas. Also, in the aboveground parts, the content of proteins, SOD, POD, carotenoids, chlorophyll a and b were statistically different between areas. A statistical analysis on LP could not be performed because it was below the detection limit for the plantain species. More details about statistically interpretation can be found in the original article. It could thus be concluded that the physiology of plants has a great influence on their response to stress induced by the presence of toxic elements. Even if the plants were sampled in the same vegetation period, but in area with different degrees of pollution (A and B), they had different growth conditions, which were influenced by temperatures, different level of humidity, shading, different nutrients content, etc. In Neagoe et al. (2013) reported that P content of plants is a decisive factor in reducing the oxidative stress caused by the presence of metals. In the present study, there were statistically significant differences between the P concentration in A area and the P concentration in B area, as indicated by the statistical analysis performed (see original article). Plants in A area showed, on average, lower P concentrations in the whole plant (all three species and parts of plants) compared to B area (table 11). It should be noted that P recorded a value below the recommended limit in area A, whereas the concentrations in area B fluctuated in the sufficiency range of 2000-5000 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$. The results of the biochemical variables measured in this study helped us to support the idea that after further investigation, they could be included in the monitoring program. Using these biochemical variables as bioindicators, the early detection of changes in the structure and function of biological systems could be possible, as we believed that a timely reaction by governments would prevent the irreversible damaging of the ecosystems. The advantage of using such bioindicators instead of instrument monitoring is that they have the capacity to offer a response to the combined effect of various pollutants, as in the case with our research area, where there are polymetallic pollutants.

Conclusions

The three plant species responded to the change in soil pollution with toxic elements in a similarly way, showing an increase in protein concentrations in all species and plant parts with the decrease in SOD and POD activity. In addition, polymetallic pollution had a clear stimulating effect on photosynthetic pigments when there was a higher concentration of both pseudo-total and bioavailable forms of potentially toxic elements with. However, these results were inferred by changes in soil phosphorus availability. The three plant species that were investigated proved to be good bio-indicators of oxidative stress, but to support the idea that they may be used as a tool for early warning detection of metabolic alteration, it is necessary to continue research on a greater number of plants and on the most varied areas of pollution gradients. It is desired that in the future permanent monitoring be established, with a focus on the integrated effects multiple stress factors, including the oxidative stress variables. These stressors could help to identify alterations in plant metabolism in a timely manner without destroying the crop or pasture. Moreover, it is necessary to consider climate changes both seasonally and throughout the year, since seasonal sampling is not sufficient to assess pollution levels. Before making recommendations on the use of plant biochemical variables in monitoring, it is necessary to clarify how available major nutrients (N, P) modulate the bioaccumulation of toxic elements and the effects they might have on plant biochemical variables, in particular on oxidative stress.

Table 12 Biochemical variables of the three species of plants (na - not analyzed (not relevant for the part of plant); BDL - below detection limit (< 0.02 μM MDA) (after Păun et al. 2015).

Area	Roots	Proteins [mg g ⁻¹]	SOD [mU mg ⁻¹ prot.]	POD [μU mg ⁻¹ prot.]	Chl a [mg g ⁻¹]	Chl b [mg g ⁻¹]	Carotenoids [mg g ⁻¹]	LP [μM MDA g ⁻¹]
A	Dandelion	1.788±0.319	9.809±1.839	2.235±0.418	na	na	na	17.45±7.041
	Clover	2.057±0.300	13.60±2.650	3.745±0.999	na	na	na	22.03±3.744
	Plantain	1.616±0.067	15.04±3.475	2.015±0.359	na	na	na	BDL
B	Dandelion	32.87±8.449	0.769±0.187	0.020±0.013	na	na	na	0.215±0.047
	Clover	33.30±13.39	0.892±0.328	0.029±0.013	na	na	na	0.318±0.089
	Plantain	28.56±3.068	0.963±0.228	0.039±0.009	na	na	na	BLD
Area	Aboveground	Proteins [mg g ⁻¹]	SOD [mU mg ⁻¹ prot.]	POD [μU mg ⁻¹ prot.]	Chl a [mg g ⁻¹]	Chl b [mg g ⁻¹]	Carotenoids [mg g ⁻¹]	LP [μM MDA g ⁻¹]
A	Dandelion	5.138±9.350	3.276±0.413	0.563±0.098	1.329±0.248	0.470±0.092	0.071±0.010	15.26±2.271
	Clover	6.096±0.496	3.516±0.996	0.577±0.124	2.747±0.941	0.938±0.295	0.144±0.046	18.61±2.717
	Plantain	2.184±0.139	2.840±0.703	1.166±0.306	1.419±0.463	0.620±0.176	0.087±0.023	BLD
B	Dandelion	33.05±3.785	0.576±0.094	0.018±0.009	1.043±0.274	0.347±0.087	0.064±0.016	0.245±0.034
	Clover	26.76±5.278	0.733±0.038	0.019±0.008	2.612±0.478	0.797±0.140	0.132±0.016	0.283±0.113
	Plantain	27.71±3.731	0.733±0.204	0.034±0.007	0.648±0.084	0.215±0.033	0.050±0.005	BDL
Area	Inflorescence	Proteins [mg g ⁻¹]	SOD [mU mg ⁻¹ prot.]	POD [μU mg ⁻¹ prot.]	Chl a [mg g ⁻¹]	Chl b [mg g ⁻¹]	Carotenoids [mg g ⁻¹]	LP [μM MDA g ⁻¹]
A	Dandelion	0.881±213.9	7.554±2.657	1.446±0.522	na	na	na	21.37±6.240
	Clover	1.180±0.153	1.513±0.663	1.236±0.243	na	na	na	59.82±3.351
	Plantain	0.578±0.163	10.98±9.263	2.754±7.358	na	na	na	BDL
B	Dandelion	34.46±3.928	0.526±0.148	0.017±0.009	na	na	na	0.247±0.030
	Clover	32.48±8.816	0.507±0.151	0.013±0.005	na	na	na	0.795±0.074
	Plantain	32.48±8.761	0.614±0.167	0.023±0.006	na	na	na	BDL

B4.2 Experimental investigations

B4.2.1 Pot experiments

A commercial arbuscular mycorrhizal inoculum alleviated the effects of acid water on *Lupinus angustifolius* grown in a sterilized mining dump

This research was published as I mentioned in section B3, by *Neagoe and Iordache 2023*, in the journal *Plants 12(10)*, 1983 (<https://doi.org/10.3390/plants12101983>), the title of the article is identical to the title of this subchapter.

The results presented in this article are part of a more complex database that was built after running a experiment at the pot-scale experiment were I used two plan species (*Lupinus angustifolius* L. and *Helianthus annuus* L.) and several treatments, including other contaminated substrates from minig areas. The treatments in which I used sunflower were not reported here because this plant species did not survive more than two weeks under this experimental conditions. Thus, the database was completed with the results obtained from a lysimeter-scale experiment in which sunflower was replaced with rye (*Secale cereale* L.). Although I tested all hypotheses regarding the effect of a commercial inoculum of AMF on *Lupinus angustifolius* L., in this article I presented only a part of the results at pot scale with lupine and with two types of water supply (neutral and acid). the pH). The other results will be published in other manuscripts.

This research highlights the existence of gaps still present in basic scientific knowledge related to the potential positive effects of AMF on lupine resistance to acid water stress in mine waste environments. However, I want to point out that the significance of this work was largely related to the gaps in applied science in the field of myco-phytoremediation of mining dumps. As lupine is a good plant when using crop rotation to accelerate secondary succession during remediation, I explored the possibility of mixing a commercial AMF inoculum with the mine tailings before starting the first crop for the purpose of the actual remediation. Mycorrhizal fungi could colonize a second host crop if they would survive during the first crop through interactions with the non-host lupine under high stress conditions. The **aim** of this study was to reveal the existence of such positive interactions and to provide preliminary data for a mine tailings myco-phytoremediation technology using *Lupinus angustifolius* L., as a first crop.

Consequently, the objective of this study was to test the hypothesis that the AMF inoculation of a dump material under neutral and acid water conditions would improve the growth of *Lupinus angustifolius* L. and decrease the oxidative stress. The estimated variables were selected according to previous work in mining areas, which demonstrated their efficiency and effectiveness in monitoring plant development during phytoremediation of mining areas.

Experimental conditions, design and measured variables

To test the above formulated hypothesis, a bivariate pot-scale experiment was performed with *Lupinus angustifolius* L. grown in a mining dump soil inoculated and not inoculated with AMF and watered with acidic and neutral water. I added two more treatments with *Lupinus angustifolius* L. growing on uncontaminated soil to have a reference for a general comparison of results. The dump material used for this experiment (brown podzolic) was sampled from Gessenwiese uranium dump, located in the Ronneburg mining area about 6 km SW of Seelingstädt (50° 44' 0" N, 12° 13' 0" E), Thuringia, Germany. This soil was sampled from the

20 cm upper surface, in 20 sub-samples to cover the heterogeneity of the contaminated area. Sub-samples were manually homogenized and brought together into a single composite sample. The reference soil was sampled from Miesitz (50° 44' 0" N, 11° 50' 0" E), Saale-Orla Kreis, Thuringia, Germany. These two soils were analyzed from a physico-chemical point of view, and the results of the measured variables are presented in table 13 in which averages are for eight pots with the same type of substrate.

Table 13 Physico-chemical variables measured for soil characterization (Neagoe and Iordache 2023)

Soil Variables	R		D		DF	
	Average	SD	Average	SD	Average	SD
Soil texture	Loamy sand		Sandy loam soil (10–30% loam)			
pH (H ₂ O)	6.58 (composite)		4.88 (composite)			
N-NH ₄ ⁺ [mg kg ⁻¹]	38.7 (composite)		4.58	2.69	7.03	3.46
N-NO ₃ ⁻ [mg kg ⁻¹]	48.4 (composite)		0.27	0.12	0.30	0.16
LOI [%]	2.08	0.33	2.48 *	0.20	2.57	0.13
Elements [mg kg ⁻¹]						
Al	6908	265.1	11193 *	177.7	12,443 #	93.06
As	13.12	1.29	19.36 *	1.26	20.37	1.64
Ba	35.15	2.21	92.79 *	3.10	95.94	5.69
Ca	1810	88.49	2021 *	152.0	1986	283.7
Cd	1.75	0.48	3.24 *	0.20	3.05	0.45
Co	4.06	0.42	15.17 *	0.49	14.77	0.38
Cr	14.74	0.54	32.42 *	2.53	30.81	1.16
Cu	21.36	1.30	46.89 *	0.75	46.02	1.30
Fe	7152	253.3	42272 *	732.9	41549	730.5
K	1042	64.51	1261 *	41.49	1417 #	173.9
Mg	1395	51.29	3077 *	43.61	2959 #	29.35
Mn	246.4	5.94	713.7 *	10.13	712.3	16.30
Mo	0.41	0.11	2.05 *	0.26	2.17	0.24
Ni	8.55	1.01	46.06 *	1.73	44.08 #	1.48
P	376.8	10.01	489.5 *	12.98	491.4	7.16
Pb	27.91	8.38	24.27	7.47	20.62	4.38
Sr	21.61	0.75	18.94 *	1.05	19.35	1.06
Ti	159.1	9.18	410.3 *	9.49	416.8	16.33
V	16.70	0.49	40.55 *	0.86	41.11	1.02
Zn	93.15	26.29	77.56	4.94	60.75 #	3.07

LOI = loss on ignition.

The symbol * shows that the average in D pots is significantly different than the average in R pots (*t*-test for independent groups). The symbol # shows that the average in DF pots is significantly different than the average in D pots (*t*-test).

The acidic water was prepared in the laboratory by diluting a concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl 37% p.a. Merck) at a concentration of 10⁻³ M. The mine dump soil already had an acidic pH (4.58), so I needed slightly acidic water to lower the pH of the mining substrate. I did germination tests in the laboratory where I used three different concentrations of acidic water for irrigation, namely, 0.1 M, 0.01 M, and 0.001 M. The one that allowed the plant to grow was the acid water with a concentration of 0.001 M.

The two homogeneous composite soils were sterilized (2.2 bar, 121° C, 30 min x 2 times) before being used to fill each 400 mL polyethylene pot. Six experimental treatments were prepared with four replicates each, as can be seen in table 14. Reference soil (R) and dump material were used, inoculated (DF) or not (D), with arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) *Glomus intraradices* species (current name *Rhizophagus irregularis*) sequestered in expanded clay, provided by Institute für Pflanzenschutz, Hannover University, Germany. The purchased product AMF 510 contained 115 spores/g substrate, and 10% was used in each pot. The quality of the AMF inoculum in accordance with the Committee of Mycorrhiza Application, Germany (CMAG, 12/1997). The use of expanded clay is a widespread practice for the preservation and transport of AMF. The addition of the commercial inoculum slightly changed the chemical variables of the dump substrate due to the expanded clay (table 13).

Table 14 Experimental treatments and their preparation (Neagoe and Iordache 2023).

Soil Type	Soil Code	Water Type	Number of Pots	Amount of Soil [g]	Amount of Clay Plus Fungi [g]
Reference	R	Neutral	4	355	0
	R	Acidic	4	355	0
Dump material without fungi	D	Neutral	4	355	0
	D	Acidic	4	355	0
Dump material with fungi	DF	Neutral	4	320	35
	DF	Acidic	4	320	35

Soils for each treatment were carefully fertilized to avoid the inhibition of mycorrhizal symbiosis, using 0.1 g per pot, as NH_4NO_3 x 2 times (at sowing and after 15 days) and watered with 60 mL distilled water per pot at the time of installation. Irrigation was carried out twice a day to maintain soil moisture, with neutral or acidic water, depending on the type of treatment. After preliminary germination tests, six seeds of *Lupinus angustifolius* L. cv Bordako were sown per pot. The experiment was carried out for one month (lupine plants grow very quickly) in a growth chamber under fully controlled conditions: 70% relative humidity and a light/dark cycle regime of 16 hours light / 22 °C and eight hours night / 16 °C with Sylvania cool white incandescent lamps, 11 W m⁻².

Measurement of soil variables

Before the start, and at the end of the experiment, the following soil variables were measured: soil moisture, soil pH, loss on ignition (LOI), nitrate (N-NO_3^-), ammonium (N-NH_4^+), and elements concentration.

Measurement of plant variables

After harvesting, the plants were washed, divided into roots and aboveground parts, and weighed to determine fresh weight (f.w.). For histochemical staining, 10 root fragments from each pot were preserved in a fixing solution, and later microscopically visualized at x 40 magnification. All above- and underground biomass material was lyophilized for dry weight (d.w.), ground in a stainless steel mill and stored at -20 °C until processing. Other variables were measured such as: photosynthetic pigments (chlorophyll a and b and carotenoids), protein content, superoxide dismutase (SOD), peroxidase (POD) and lipid peroxides (LP) as a malondialdehyde (MDA) content.

Selected findings

Root mycorrhizal colonization

From the microscopic visualization of all root fragments, it was observed that there was no mycorrhization under the described experimental conditions (neither vesicles nor arbuscules were observed).

Phosphorus, Potassium, and other elements

Following the interpretation of the data, we discovered that there were differences between many elements in roots and leaves of the plants grown both in the reference soil and in the dump material. Thus, in figure 6 it can be seen that the use of acidic water for non-inoculated substrates increased the concentration of potassium (K) in roots and decrease in leaves. The same pattern of variation was also present in the VAM-inoculated treatment. On the other hand, inoculation significantly increased the concentration of phosphorus (P) in roots and leaves in both neutral and acidic water treatments.

Figure 6 Phosphorus and potassium concentrations in roots (down) and leaves (up) (Neagoe and Iordache 2023).

Figure legend (valid for all figures in this subchapter, except for the last symbol #): the treatments with neutral water are represented by white columns, and in black are those with acid water. The black stars (*) indicate that the differences due to the acid water on R, D, or DF substrates are statistically significant (ANOVA). The symbol □ indicates that the differences between D and R treatments are statistically significant. The symbol # indicates that the addition of commercial AMF inoculum to the D substrate led to a significant increase in P concentrations in roots and leaves.

Superoxid dismutase (SOD), peroxidase (POD), lipid peroxidase (LP), protein, assimilating pigments (chlorophyll and carotenoids).

LP and POD in leaves increased significantly from the reference soil to the dump material (figures 7a and 7b). Acidic water significantly increased SOD activity in leaves (figure 7b), both in plants grown on reference soil and in dump material. POD activity increased in acidic water dump material compared to with neutral water dump material. On the other hand, SOD and POD activities decreased in leaves as a result of inoculation (figure 7b). Leaf protein concentration decreased in acidic water treatments and increased when dump material was inoculated (figure 7a). In roots, protein concentration was decreased by inoculation.

Decreases in chlorophyll and carotenoid concentrations were also observed as a result of treatment with acidic water, and increases following inoculation with AMF. The values of these elements can be found in the raw data set available in the Supplementary Materials at: <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/plants12101983/s1>.

Figure 7a Protein concentrations and LP in roots (down) and leaves (up). The symbol # indicates that the average value of a variable in DF substrate is different from its average value in D (Neagoe and Iordache 2023).

Plant Biomass

In figure 8 it can be seen that the fresh weight and dry weight of the roots decreased significantly from the reference soil to the dump material, and acidic water further reduced the dry weight of

the roots in both treatments. Height, fresh weight and stem dry weight were lower when plants were grown on the littered substrate compared to the reference soil, and stem fresh weight was further reduced with acid water. A similar decline in biomass due to contamination and acidic water occurred for leaves. The effect of AMF inoculation can also be seen in figure 8. The fresh weight of stems and leaves of plants in acid water treatments increased due to soil inoculation, while shoot height decreased. No significant effect of AMF on dry weight was observed (mean increased at a p-level of 0.17).

Figure 7b SOD activity and POD activity in roots (down) and leaves/ The symbol # indicates that the addition of commercial AMF inoculum to the D substrate caused a significant decrease in SOD and POD in leaves (Neagoe and Iordache 2023).

Principal Component Analysis of plant variables

Preliminary correlation matrixes revealed the significantly correlated variables in roots and leaves. The two significant extracted factors accounted for 55.58% of the variability in roots and 66.44% in leaves (figure 9). Root oxidative stress variables were negatively correlated with P concentration and fresh-weight biomass. In leaves, the same pattern holds for SOD and POD activities. Lipid peroxidation in leaves was positively correlated with the concentrations of a cluster of elements mobilized from the dump material (Ni, Cu, Zn, and Fe) and negatively correlated with leaves fresh weight, assimilating pigments concentrations, and protein concentration. From the perspective of the experimental treatments, one can notice the clear separation between location of the sample loadings in the multivariate space, confirming the

ANOVA results. The effect of acid water is more evident in the case of the dump material and more prominent in roots than in leaves. AMF inoculation separated the samples (pots) based on leaf variables. A correlation matrix analysis restricted to leaf variables of plants grown in dump material ($n = 16$, not inserted) demonstrated a significant negative correlation between peroxidase activity and the concentrations of P ($R = -0.63$, $p = 0.009$). The separation of the experimental treatments corresponds to the statistically significant differences proved for these variables with ANOVA.

Figure 8 Fresh weight and dry weight of leaves (up), of stems (middle), and of roots (down). The symbol # indicates that the average value of a variable in DF substrate is different from its average value in D (Neagoe and Iordache 2023).

Figure 9 Left Biplots resulted from principal component analysis of plant variables in roots (down left) and leaves (up left), representing correlations between variables and the extracted factors. (Right) Scatterplots of loadings of all samples (pots) on factors 1 and 2 extracted by PCA. R, D, and DF in the (up right) legend stand for the treatments with neutral water, and RA, DA, and DFA for those with acid water (Neagoe and Iordache 2023).

Substrate variables at the end of the experiment

Nitrate and ammonium increased significantly from the beginning to the end of the experiment. There were many cases with a significant decrease in the concentration of elements in the substrate at the end of the experiment (see table 15).

Table 15 Ratios between the concentrations of elements in the soil of the experimental treatment at the end and at the start of the experiment (Neagoe and Iordache 2023).

Treatments	Al	As	Ca	Cr	Cu	K	Mg	Mn	P	Sr	Zn
R				0.95	0.26	0.85	0.89	0.95	0.93	0.92	0.26
RA					0.27	0.80	0.86	0.93	0.90	0.88	0.36
D			0.84		0.74	0.87	0.93		0.94		0.66
DA					0.73	0.86	0.92	0.96	0.92	0.90	0.72
DF	0.97				0.81		0.94		0.93		0.88
DFA	0.97	0.87			0.78		0.93		0.92		0.85

Only the ratios for statistically significant differences between means (one-way ANOVA) are presented. Fe and Ni concentrations did not change in any treatment. The acid water significantly decreased the pH and increased the nitrate concentration in the substrate both in

the reference soil and the dump material. The inoculation increased the ammonium concentration in the dump material under neutral and acid water conditions.

To test whether changes in dump material chemistry as a result of the addition of expanded clay by the commercial AMF inoculum at the start of the experiment influenced the chemical variables of substrate and plants at the end of the experiment, we compared the corresponding trends (table 16). The trends in the substrate due to the addition of expanded clay by the commercial inoculum at the start of the experiment were also found at the end of the experiment, except for Zn. The trends in roots and leaves did not follow those existing in the substrate at the start of the experiment. One can see that the trends for Al, K (increase) and Ni and Mg (decrease) in the substrate are similar at the end compared with the start of the experiment (table 16). This did not occur for Zn, whose concentration in the substrate of the pots strongly decreased by the end of the experiment. When one looks at the concentrations of these elements in roots and leaves, one can see that they mirror the pattern found in the substrate. The addition of the commercial AMF inoculum did not change Al, Mg, K, or Ni in plants but only increased the concentrations of P, Sr, and Zn.

Table 16 Changes in the concentrations of several elements in the DF treatments compared with D treatments (t-test) at the start and the end of the experiment (Neagoe and Iordache 2023).

	Start	Substrate	End of the Experiment	
	Substrate		Plants	Leaves
			Roots	
Al	Increase	Increase		
Cu		Increase		
K	Increase	Increase		
Mg	Decrease	Decrease		
Ni	Decrease	Decrease		
P			Increase	Increase
Sr		Increase	Increase	
Zn	Decrease		Increase	

The original article details discussions and research directions. Due to a lack of space, I will present only the conclusions of this study in the next paragraph.

Conclusions

Although the experiment was conducted only one month, the benefits of AMF inoculation were observed in the non-host species *L. angustifolius*, more pronounced in the acid water treatment. No mycorrhization was identified in the experimental conditions, but the fresh weight of stems and leaves significantly increased due to inoculation in the acid water treatments. In both neutral and acidic water conditions, the P concentrations in roots and leaves significantly increased, and SOD and POD activities were significantly decreased due to the commercial AMF inoculum. The increase in P concentration in leaves was significantly correlated with the decrease in POD activity. At the end of the experiment, the concentration of ammonium in the substrate was higher in the inoculated treatments than in the uninoculated ones. As we did not use a monoxenic spore culture of the AM fungus or have assurance that any other microorganisms than the declared strain of AMF are not present in the commercial product, it is not certain that the observed effects are due to AMF. In future work, a possibility is to study the microbiome of the AMF inoculum used in order to identify associated plant growth-

promoting microorganisms. One might also check the patterns reported here on other, more contaminated soils at the same (pot) and larger scale (lysimeter). Another possibility could be to use a second crop with a host plant without extra inoculation with AMF and look for eventual symbiosis from the initial inoculum provided to the lupine crop.

Hairy roots mutants of *Nicotiana tabaccum* resisted better in contaminated soil than the normal plants and had a very strong interaction with mycorrhizal fungi

This research was published *by Neagoe et al. 2017, in Revista de Chimie in 2017, 68, 4* with the title „Coupling *Nicotiana tabaccum* transgenic plants with *Rhizophagus irregularis* for phytoremediation of heavy metal polluted areas”

The use of transgenic plants with their hairy roots (HRs) was performed to find an optimal solution for the phytoextraction of inorganic pollutants from industrial or mining areas. This research was run using soil from an industrial area and was made possible through cooperation with the Genetics Department of the Faculty of Biology, University of Bucharest. It was part of my first **CEEX Modul II reintegration project**, and the novelty was the coupling of AMF with transgenic plants, an experiment tht was performed for the first time in the world, at University of Bucharest in 2005-2007.

The research was performed at the pot-scale and was carried out in a plant growth chamber. The **aim** was to determine the effect of colonization with the arbuscular mycorrhizal (AM) fungi (*Rhizophagus irregularis*) of HRs of tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum* L. cv. Virginia gold) under conditions of heavy metals (Cu, Pb and Zn) pollution.

Experimental conditions, design and measured variables

The pot-scale experiment was carried out using soil polluted with heavy metal sampled from Pantelimon area located in the eastern part of Bucharest, Romania (geographical coordinates: latitude: 44.4538, longitude: 26.22244 ° 27 '14 "North, 26 ° 13' 19" East, in WGS84 system). The source of pollution consisted of two factories “Acumulatorul and Neferal” with activities in the production of batteries and non-ferrous industry that operated since 1932. After 1995, the industrial activity in this area was limited to the environmental friendly recovery of non-ferrous metals from waste, such as Pb from damaged batteries, thus minimizing pollution.

It was reported by many authors that 1,748 ha were polluted with Pb (max. 784 mg / kg), 1,314 ha with Cu (max. 180 mg / kg) and 874 ha with Zn (max. 380 mg / kg). Concentrations of metals increased by 70% Cu, 45% Pb and 30% Zn from 1980 to 1995. According to our studies, about 50 ha near the two factories were found to be highly contaminated and required measures for ecological rehabilitation. The polluted soil classified in Chernisols, Luvisols - dominant class, and Hydrosols, was moderately acidic, with a clay texture, having small to average humus contents (1.8 up to 3.7%) and total nitrogen (0.130 up to 0.163%) and small amounts of soluble phosphorus (11 up to 15 mg/kg) and Corg (2 up to 3.6%). In our investigations, this soil was physico-chemical characterized by high concentrations of Pb, Cu and Zn, as can be seen in table 17.

Table 17 General physico-chemical characteristics of investigated soils (contaminated - C and non-contaminated, reference - R soils) before the experiment (Neagoe si colab., 2017).

Variables /units	pH	EC μS/cm	N-NH ₄ ⁺	N-NO ₃ ⁻	N-NO ₂ ⁻	P-PO ₄ ³⁻
R	7.34	69.8	41.98	22.48	0.202	84.32
C	5.85	161.1	30.29	19.15	0.083	15.65

Variables /units	C _{org} %	Cd	Co	Cu	Pb	Zn
R	7.49	1.249	23.05	32.08	11.80	111.7
C	3.59	2.127	15.66	341.2	1726	537.1

We worked with experimental treatments in which *Nicotiana tabacum* L. seedlings were grown in contaminated substrate without and with infection caused by *Agrobacterium rhizogenes* expressed as HRs disease.

After a preliminary germination test in which 13 plant species were used (data not shown) and a literature study, we chose to work with *Nicotiana tabacum* L. cv. Virginia gold and *Helianthus annuus* L. cv. Arena PR, both selected for the most vigorous development and their very good degree of germination, but also for the potential degree of mycorrhization and due to the performance of this plant species to form hairy roots. Before planting one seedling per pot in R and C soils, they were sterilized by autoclaving (2.2 bar, 121°C × 30 min × 2 times) and weighed into 400 ml polyethylene pots with four replications for each treatment. We have established the following treatments: 1) uncontaminated reference soil in which non-genetically modified tobacco seedlings were planted (coded R), 2) uncontaminated reference soil in which transgenic tobacco seedlings were planted (coded RT), 3) contaminated soil mixed with clay used as a control in which non-genetically modified tobacco seedlings were planted (coded C), 4) contaminated soil mixed with clay, inoculated with AMF in which transgenic tobacco seedlings were planted (coded CTM), and 5) contaminated soil mixed with clay used as a control in which transgenic tobacco seedlings were planted (coded CT) (see figure 10).

Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi were a commercial product 510 AMF (160 spores per g soil) *Rhizophagus irregularis*, sequestered in expanded clay (particle size 2 to 4 mm) and it was inoculated into each pot in the CTM treatment (10% according to von Alten et al. 2002). This experiment was run over a period of two months in a growth chamber with controlled conditions: 70% relative humidity and light/dark cycle regime of 16 h light/22°C and 8 h night/16°C with Sylvania cool-white incandescent lamps, 11 W m⁻². Watering was performed once a day, to maintain the soil moisture.

In this experiment we tried to identify an efficient strategy for the genetic transformation of *N. tabacum* and *H. annuus*, using the DNA fragment-T located in the Ri plasmid of the soil bacterium *Agrobacterium rhizogenes*. This bacterium has "oncogenes" role responsible for inducing the neoplasia known as "hairy roots" (HRs) common by numerous dicotyledonous. The bacterial strains used for transformation were *A. rhizogenes* 8916 and *A. rhizogenes* 9402 (hypervirulent strain). Both are wild Ri (root-inducing) plasmid strains and were obtained from the research center INRA, from Dr. D. Tepfer, Versailles, France.

Figure 10 Development of *Nicotiana tabacum* L. seedlings in the five experimental treatments (after Neagoe and Iordache 2021)

The first step in the genetic transformation consisted in the preparation of the bacterial suspension and co-cultivation of different types of explants (leaf explants, petiole and internodes segments) from "in vitro" culture plants. The explants were injured by a sterile injection needle (0.55 x 25 mm) and subsequently infected by imbibing injured tissue with the bacterial suspension. Finally, the explants were transferred to LS culture medium and maintained in culture room for 48 hours. Both mentioned strains have been used and the dilution of bacterial inoculum was varied. The elimination of the bacteria was performed on media with antibiotics (LS supplemented with 500 mg x l⁻¹ carbenicillin - Sigma). After two weeks, the HRs were observed at the point of infection.

These HRs could be isolated and transferred later on medium without hormones in order to achieve a roots biomass used to test the in vitro accumulation or stabilization capacity of heavy metals. The root segments were transferred every two weeks to the same medium but with low antibiotic concentrations up to 100 mg x l⁻¹. The time for induction of HRs at the injury site was 4-5 weeks in the two bacterial systems. If the dilution of bacterial culture was reduced, in the case of 9402 strain was observed a favorable effect in terms of transformation efficiency. The time for appearance of HRs was much shorter. For the two species the same bacterial strains were used, but the HRs phenotype was different. HRs crop was achieved in a shorter time for the *N. tabacum* sp. (about 2 - 4 weeks) while at *H. annuus* sp. the time was greater with 3-6 weeks. Another trend characterized as negative aspect by *H. annuus* was the browning one, at the same time with the weakening of the germplasm resistance from fungus attack, which caused loss in a significant percentage of them. Due to these aspects we decided to take in work only the *N. tabacum* sp. The regenerative capacity of the entire plants from the HRs sectors was

variable. *N. tabacum* sp. has shown a rapid callus with numerous meristems after about 3 weeks from the roots transfer sectors on regeneration media. The direct and spontaneous shoots trends without passing through the stage of callus were considered positive. The efficiency of genetic transformation *A. rhizogenes* mediated was studied based on molecular analysis (data not shown) and in vitro genotypic and phenotypic marker genes used in this system of the transgenesis, based on visual analysis of HRs phenotypic characteristic.

Plant sampling and processing

The harvesting procedure was done after 60 days from planting, and the wet biomasses were weighed and separated for analyses into roots, shoots (shoots plus leaves) and flowers. All roots of the plants were briefly washed with tap water and finally all parts of plant were washed with distilled water. The vitality of plants was recorded and measurements on all parts of the plant, such as number of individuals, height of each individual, biomass, photosynthetic activity, blooming and so on. The plant material was lyophilized, then dry biomass was measured, cold ground and then kept at minus 45 °C for analysis. We determined the following variables: concentration of elements (Cd, Co, Cu, Pb and Zn), total protein content, lipid peroxidation (LP) expressed as malondialdehyde (MDA), and assimilating pigments (chlorophyll and carotenoids).

Soil sampling and processing

After harvesting the plants, the following variables were measured: soil respiration, pH, electrical conductivity (EC), mineral N content (N-NH_4^+ , N-NO_3^- , N-NO_2^-), phosphorus content in available form by plants (P-PO_4^{3-}) and the pseudo-total content of metals after *aqua regia* microwave pressure-assisted digestions.

Selected findings

Immediately after harvesting the plants and measuring the soil respiration, we moved on to the physico-chemical characterization of the soil, all measured variables being presented in table 18. It should be noted from these variables that dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN) presented a sufficient content for plant development ($\geq 50 \mu\text{g x g}^{-1}$, while, the available phosphorus content was sufficient in R and RT treatments, but showed a deficiency in C treatments ($< 60 \mu\text{g x g}^{-1}$).

One-way ANOVA analysis of soil respiration score showed that the effect of treatments was significant, $F(4, 15) = 148.79$, $p < 0.005$. Post hoc comparison using the Tukey HSD test showed that there were significant differences between all soil types except R versus CTM. At the time of statistical analysis, no separation was made between the factors plant type and soil type. Statistical differences were obtained by considering both factors simultaneously. We conclude that the effects of HRs (in RT and CT treatments) were positive and, in addition, AMF inoculation (in CTM treatment) had a spectacular positive effect on soil respiration, the value of this variable reaching that of soil R. However, the same cannot be said for C_{org} where the effects of either HRs or AMF were insignificant, the percentage of C_{org} in soil R being approximately double that of soil C. Regarding the gel metal content of the soil there were statistically significant differences between treatments (Cu, $F(4,15) = 9.35$, $p < 0.005$; Pb, $F(4,15) = 79.46$, $p < 0.00$, $F(4,15) = 73.63$, $p < 0.00$, $F(4,15) = 34.00$ However, soil Cd content did not differ significantly between treatments, $F(4,15) = 1.28$, $p > 0.3$. To highlight these aspects, we can state that there were statistical differences between treatments for biomass production (sum of all plant parts).

Table 18 General physico-chemical characteristics (min. and max. values) of investigated soils after plant harvesting (EC is electrical conductivity, DIN is dissolved inorganic nitrogen, R mg CO₂ is respiration of soil), n=4 (adapted after Neagoe et al. 2017).

Variables /units	pH	EC μS/cm	N-NH ₄ ⁺	N-NO ₃ ⁻	N-NO ₂ ⁻ μg/g d.w.	DIN	P-PO ₄ ³⁻
R	6.94±0.126	84.4±5.75	56.78±5.58	31.36±4.889	0.191±0.032	88.33±9.777	57.863±3.893
RT	6.995±0.079	71.9±5.29	63.06±3.03	33.47±2.736	0.20±0.026	96.72±5.563	66.31±5.203
C	5.64±0.067	185.4±49.71	47.51±3.874	11.51±1.270	0.064±0.01	59.09±3.818	11.05±3.641
CT	5.825±0.179	146.2±40.8	52.03±2.751	12.06±1.646	0.074±0.018	64.16±4.259	11.57±4.188
CTM	6.09±0.137	124.1±32.03	61.95±5.196	14.18±3.298	0.052±0.007	76.18±8.161	12.09±3.155

Variables /units	R mg CO ₂ g ⁻¹ dw x 2 h	C _{org} %	Cd	Co	Cu μg/g d.w.	Pb	Zn
R	6.993±0.111	8.848±0.379	1.13±0.133	22.05±1.922	31.22±0.942	11.31±0.911	106.64±5.528
RT	9.183±0.52	8.908±0.274	1.069±0.295	21.94±0.413	29.72±1.798	11.15±1.092	99.21±10.98
C	2.945±0.631	4.623±0.046	1.864±0.392	15.01±1.484	331.3±137.7	1650±226.6	514.7±56.32
CT	4.053±0.347	4.765±0.163	1.574±0.443	14.16±1.21	268.3±97.49	1304±146.6	505±69.63
CTM	6.768±0.183	4.925±0.345	1.685±1.202	15.41±1.252	341.7±157.2	1430±289.1	465.9±66.79

In the current study, all plant parts from the CT treatment accumulated significantly higher concentrations of heavy metals (except Cd and Zn) compared to the plants of the C treatment as can be seen in table 19. To show statistical differences in the heavy metal content of plants, only the aboveground parts of plants (shoots and leaves) were compared (roots and flowers showed a similar pattern). Using analysis of variance and Tukey multiple comparisons of means, all possible differences in competing pairwise means, occurring at any one time simultaneously were accounted for, as can be seen in table 19. Variation of heavy metal content in the aboveground parts of the plants between the three treatments can be seen in figure 11. If the mean values do not overlap, there is more evidence that there is a real effect of the treatment on plant development. The blue line on the graphs pointed out this aspect. The score of heavy metal content in the aboveground parts of plants from the CTM treatment stands out from the others, being significantly higher for Cu and lower for the other elements. In the case of CT treatment, HRs mutants induced an increase in stress expressed in terms of lower protein and higher lipid peroxidation (LP) contents. What was remarkable is the increase of chlorophyll content in the CT treatment. These results on genetically modified plants without inoculation with AMF were obtained for particular growth conditions and development stages. However, we emphasize that the obtained results were in agreement with a more vigorous plant development. In our study, the question of using *Rhizophagus irregularis* inoculation along with *N. tabacum* HR was whether or not the AMF symbiosis can reduce the adverse effects due to the presence of heavy metals.

Table 19 Analysis of variance and Tukey multiple comparisons of means concentrations of heavy metals in plants (adapted after Neagoe et al. 2017).

Analysis of Variance													
	df	SS	MS	F	P	SS	MS	F	P	SS	MS	F	P
	Pb				Co				Cu				
Plant type	2	864	432	14	0.001	11.45	5.78	9.07	0.007	122.7	61.3	16.7	0.0009
Residuals	9	276	30.2	-	-	5.68	0.63	-	-	33.	3.68	-	-

Tukey multiple comparisons of means													
Treatments	diff	lwr	upr	P adj	diff	lwr	upr	P adj	diff	lwr	upr	P adj	
CT-C	8.3	-2.6	19.2	0.139	0.9	-0.64	2.5	0.27	-0.21	-4.	3.5	0.98	
CTM-C	-12.	-23.	-1.3	0.029	-1.44	-3.0	0.12	0.07	6.6	2.9	10.4	0.002	
CTM-CT	-20.	-31.	-9.7	0.001	-2.3	-3.9	-0.8	0.005	6.9	3.1	10.6	0.001	

Note: bold values indicate statistically significant difference

Other mentioned biochemical variables (only for the aboveground plant parts, the others having similar patterns) and treatments were compared using analysis of variance and Tukey multiple comparisons of means, in the same way as for physicochemical variables (table 20). Between treatments, there were statistically significant differences for all variables presented. It can be seen in table 20 and on the graphs presented in figure 12 that biomass production, chlorophyll a, and protein content were significantly higher in CTM treatment, while oxidative damage like lipid peroxidation (LP) content was significantly lower. These results could be attributed to the beneficial contribution of AMF in host roots under stress conditions. Our studies on this topic were the first in the world, carried out in the period 2005-2007. The results were presented at several conferences but published only in 2017. Meanwhile, similar results were published in 2011 studies in which the authors found lower MDA levels in HR transgenic cultures in association with *G. intraradices*.

Conclusions

As a result of using HR by *Nicotiana tabacum* L., soil respiration, biomass production, and chlorophyll a were higher than in non-genetically modified plants. It could not be concluded that the oxidative stress decreased in the CT treatment since the protein content was lower and the lipid peroxidation higher. This plant response could be attributed to significantly higher heavy metal content. However, AMF colonization of HR mutants under heavy metal stress resulted in the highest biomass production. All other measured biochemical variables indicated a decrease in oxidative stress in the CTM treatment. In addition, the CTM treatment significantly attenuated the concentration of some toxic elements in plants, while CT treatment showed a significant increase compared to C treatment. Although little is known about the behavior of HRs when infected with AMF under stress conditions with heavy metals, it can be concluded that AMF (*Rhizophagus irregularis*) colonization of HR mutants offers a promising tool in the field of phytoremediation. In any case, future research is needed on a wide range of plant species.

Figure 11 The score of heavy metal content in aboveground plant parts partitioned on C, CT and CTM treatments, (Neagoe et al. 2017).

Table 20 Analysis of variance and Tukey multiple comparisons of means concentration of chlorophyll a, protein, lipid peroxidation, and biomass in plants for C, CT, and CTM treatments (adapted after Neagoe et al. 2017).

Analysis of Variance Table																		
Variables	df	SS	MS	F	P	SS	MS	F	P	SS	MS	F	P	df	SS	MS	F	P
	Chl a					Protein				Lipid peroxidation				Biomass				
Plant type	2	122.7	61.3	16.7	0.0009	6920	3460	144.9	1.4e-7	0.128	0.061	155.9	1.0e-7	2	8.6	4.3	16.5	0.0009
Residuals	9	33.0	3.6	-	-	214.8	23.9	-	-	0.0003	3.9e-4	-	-	9	2.34	0.26		
Tukey multiple comparisons of means.																		
Treatments	diff	lwr	upr	<i>P adj</i>	diff	lwr	upr	<i>P adj</i>	diff	lwr	upr	<i>P adj</i>	diff	diff	lwr	upr	adj	
CT-C	0.21	-3.57	4.	0.987	-33	-42	-23	1.e-5	0.144	0.104	0.183	7.e-6	0.04	-0.96	1.0	0.99		
CTM-C	6.8	3.1	10.6	0.001	25.	15.8	35.	0.0001	-0.103	-0.142	-0.063	0.0001	1.8	0.8	2.8	0.001		
CTM-CT	6.6.	2.9.	10.4	0.002	58.	49.	68..	1.e-7	-0.247	-0.286	-0.208	1.e-7	1.77	0.76	2.78	0.002		

Figure 12 The score of biochemical variables in aboveground plant parts partitioned on C, CT, and CTM treatments (Neagoe et al. 2017).

The effect of AMF inoculation on plants grown in contaminated soil was species- and metal-specific, although there was a general enhancement of plant growth

The study presented in this section was published by Neagoe et al. 2013 in *Plant Nutrition and Soil Science Journal*, 176(2), 273-286, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jpln.201200079>, in an article entitled „Patterns of effects of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi on plants grown in contaminated soil”.

The aim of this study was to investigate the patterns of metal stress reduction by AMF in four plant species.

Experimental conditions, design and measured variables

For this purpose, I used clover (*Trifolium pratense* L.), sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.), mustard (*Sinapis alba* L.) and phacelia (*Phacelia tanacetifolia* Benth.) that were inoculated with *Glomus intraradices* and compared to uninoculated plants grown under heavy metals-stress conditions. Spoil used in this experiment was contaminated with heavy metal coded **C** and sampled from a former uranium dump Sorge Settendorf (50°44'0" N, 12°13'0" E) and an uncontaminated soil coded **U** sampled from Miesitz (Saale-Orla Kreis 50°44'0" N, 11°50'0" E), both from Thuringia, Germany. In the table 21 a comparison can be seen from the point of view of the physico-chemical variables of both soils used in this experiment.

Table 21 Comparison between the uncontaminated and contaminated soils (Neagoe et al. 2013).

	Uncontaminated	Contaminated	
Soil type	loamy sand	brown podzolic soil	
pH (CaCl ₂)	6.50	6.65	
C org (% d.w.)	0.80	2.50	
CaCO ₃ (% d. w.)	0.80	2.39	
P (total, mg/kg)	380	800	
P (extractable, mg/kg)	4.8	3.88	
K (total, mg/kg)	700	3241	
K (extractable, mg/kg)	12.0	5.8	
	Total	Total	Easily extractable
As (mg/kg)	11.21	254	0.995
Cd (mg/kg)	3.06	12.8	9.11
Co (mg/kg)	3.56	59	6.90
Cu (mg/kg)	5.43	234	5.82
Fe (mg/kg)	6371	21207	na
Mn (mg/kg)	268	1202	na
Pb (mg/kg)	16.21	121	5.87
U (mg/kg)	udl	110	3.80
Zn (mg/kg)	30.45	1096	631

^a d.w. = dry weight; ^b easily extractable = fraction 1 / 1M NH₄NO₃ + fraction 2 / 1M CH₃COONH₄; na = not analyzed; udl = under detection limit.

Within the uranium dump, the C soil was sampled from 1 ha surface located S on the industrial area Trünzig, divided into 9 lots (3 x 3 m) located in the "hot spot" part of this site. After homogenization, I used a composite sample for this experiment. The U soil was sampled from the first 20 cm (the most biologically active area) from a surface large enough to ensure its representativeness, later it was manually homogenized and a composite sample was further use. From the table 21 it can be seen that soil pH is comparable and both soils have low P concentrations. K concentrations are slightly different, being higher in the contaminated soil. At the beginning of the experiment, both soils were lightly fertilized with soluble N, so that the initial differences between soil N concentrations were not reflected in plant development. The total metal content showed that for many metals in the contaminated soil the concentration was higher than in the uncontaminated soil, thus demonstrating that contamination with metals is the major factor controlling the differences between plant development in the two soils. It was not possible to have the same matrix of both contaminated and uncontaminated soils, because the contaminated soil developed naturally only in this form with high concentrations of metals on the mining dump, and has not been obtained by spiking an uncontaminated soil.

Experimental design

For the experiment, these two soils were sterilized by autoclaving (2.2 bar, 121oC x 30 min x 2 time). Then, three experimental treatments were carried out (each treatment was replicated four times, for each of the four plant species used, leading to a total of 48 polyethylene pots with a volume of 400 ml): uncontaminated (**U**), contaminated soil mixed with expanded clay (**C**), and soil contaminated and inoculated (**I**) with the commercial product AMF 510 (160

spores per g soil) *Glomus intraradices*, sequestered in expanded clay, origin: "Institute für Pflanzenschutz", University of Hanover. Soils were carefully fertilized to avoid inhibition of mycorrhizal symbiosis, using 0.1 g (amount per pot) as NH_4NO_3 and watered with 60 ml distilled water per pot according to water holding capacity test. Watering was carried out twice a day to maintain the soil moisture content. After a germination test, all plant species were sown: 10 phacelia seeds (*Phacelia tanacetifolia* Benth.), 10 mustard seeds (*Sinapis alba* L.), 15 clover seeds (*Trifolium pratense* L.) and 5 sunflower seeds (*Helianthus annuus* L.). Then, all the pots were placed in one growth chamber with controlled conditions: 70% relative humidity and light/dark cycle regime of 16 hours light/22 °C and 8 hours night/16 °C with Sylvania cool white incandescent lamps, 11 W m⁻². All seeds sown germinated thus, the number of seeds was equal to the number of plant individuals grown in each pot for each plant species used. Since the key to successful establishment of vegetation is the selection of plant species, these plants were selected taking into account their suitable properties for soil exploitation. These plant species were selected because they are able to quickly establish plant cover, control erosion and persist over time. Moreover, clover and phacelia have an extensive, dense and fibrous root system (which permits to extract many nutrients not always present in surface soil, and promotes the formation of a crumbly soil structure) and foliage and higher resistance to mine spoil conditions. On the other hand, sunflower and mustard emerge quickly and produce a large amount of biomass. Excepting for the non-host mustard (taken for comparing the patterns), the other three plant species were selected for their mycorrhizal potential. The duration of the experiment was 45 days (time of physiological decline in the presented experimental conditions, especially for mustard and phacelia). At the end of the experiment, all plants were harvested, wet weighed and separated for analysis according to each plant species, in roots, shoots, leaves (dead, basal and young) and in the case of mustard and in flowers. All roots of the plants were briefly washed (repeated five times) with tap and finally with distilled water. Vitality observations and measurements were performed such as number of individuals, height of each individual, biomass, photosynthetic activity, blooming etc. All plant material was lyophilized for determination of dry weight (d.w.), ground in a stainless-steel mill equipped with cooling system and frozen at minus 20 °C until processing.

Measured variables from plants

The variables measured from the plants were the following: content of elements (As, Cd, Co, Cu, Fe, Mn, P, Pb, U and Zn), total proteins, superoxide dismutase (SOD) and peroxidase (POD) activity, lipid peroxidation (LP) in terms of malondialdehyde (MDA) content and assimilatory pigments (chlorophylls and carotenoids). For each of the four replicates, two sub-samples have been analyzed, for every measured variable. Also, we microscopically visualized 10 stained root fragments of 2 cm long from each pot after colonization by *G. intraradices*, and than root colonization was assessed.

Selected findings

Chemical and biochemical variables together with the results of statistical tests are reported into the tables 22 - 24. For biomass and height there were significant differences between reference soil and contaminated soil for all species, but the inoculation had a statistically significant effect only in the case of phacelia, sunflower and mustard. The biomass of plant parts of clover had larger values as a result of inoculation in many cases, but the differences were not significant. The decrease of metals concentration in plant parts as a result of inoculation was variable. For instance, the concentration of As in roots decreased significantly

after inoculation in the host plants, but not in mustard. With one exception, Fe in leaves, no significant decrease of concentration as a result of inoculation occurred in mustard. In the host species most of the significant effects of inoculation on metals concentration were in roots. The largest number of significant differences in metals concentration in plant parts as a result of inoculation has been in clover and sunflower. From the biochemical variables SOD had the clearest patterns, increasing (sometimes significantly) in contaminated soil compared to reference (uncontaminated) soil in host plants, and decreasing in most cases as a result of inoculation. This pattern did not occur for mustard. Variation for pigments concentration as a result of contamination and inoculation occurred only in the case of mustard. Table 25 presents the phosphorus concentrations in plant parts and ratios between the dry weights of plant parts. Clover and sunflower grown on C soil had significantly smaller P concentrations in roots than when grown on U soil, while mustard and sunflower significantly larger P concentrations in shoots. Concentrations of phosphorus were not significantly larger as a result of inoculation in any case. The aboveground/belowground dry biomass ratio increased from U to C variants in the case of phacelia and clover, but decreased in the case of sunflower and mustard. The same ratio increased as a result of inoculation in all cases, excepting for mustard.

Root colonization

Microscopic examination of the roots confirmed the symbiosis between *G. intraradices* and selected plant species, except for mustard. Arbuscules were observed in phacelia roots, and vesicles were observed in clover and sunflower roots. The extent of AMF colonization was not assessed.

Table 26 presents the percent variation of the metal concentration in different parts of plant from reference to contaminated treatment and from contaminated to contaminated and inoculated treatment. Only differences between contaminated, and contaminated and inoculated treatments were analyzed. Growing the plants on contaminated soil led in most cases to a strong increase in concentration of metals compared to the treatments with reference soil. As a general observation, the effect of soil inoculation was highly variable. Based on an analysis by metals, four different situations were observed in relation to inoculation: metals with no variations (Pb), metals with no variation or only decrease in concentration (As, Cd, Co), metals with no variation or only increase in concentration (Zn), and metals with no variation, with decrease or increase in concentration (Cu, Fe, Mn). An analysis by plant species showed differences between the patterns of metal variation as a result of inoculation. Phacelia was characterized by a decrease in As, Co, Cu, Fe, U, and by an increase in Zn concentrations. Clover showed a decrease of As, Cd, Co, Fe, Mn, and an increase of Cd, Co (in other parts of plant), and U. Sunflower had a decrease in As, Cu, Fe, Mn, and U, and an increase in Fe, Mn (in other parts of plant), and Zn. Finally, in mustard only the concentrations of Cu, Fe, and U decreased, whereas those of Zn increased. In leaves of all species, only increases were observed, except for Zn in phacelia; in shoots, there were two cases of metals with increasing concentrations (Zn and Fe), while in roots, three metals were in this situation (Cu, Mn, and U). Table 27 showed the data (as percent variation) characterizing plant performance in terms of biomass and biochemical variables. Plants grown on contaminated soil had lower total biomass, except for sunflower. As a result of inoculation, only the total biomass of mustard significantly increased. The concentration of total proteins in clover decreased as a result of contamination, and increased as a result of inoculation, but in mustard and sunflower, the situation is reversed (increase in contaminated variant and decrease after inoculation).

Table 22 Biomass in plants grown in uncontaminated soil (U) and due to soil contamination (C), and inoculation (I). Legend: F = flowers, S = shoots, DL = dead leaves, BL = basal leaves, L = young leaves, TL = total leaves, TA = total aboveground, U = underground, HI = height of individuals, bold numbers indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$) (Neagoe et al. 2013).

Parameter	Parts of plant	Mann-Whitney-U test																						
		Phacelia			Clover			Sunflower			Mustard			Phacelia		Clover		Sunflower		Mustard				
		U	C	I	U	C	I	U	C	I	U	C	I	U/C	C/I	U/C	C/I	U/C	C/I	U/C	C/I			
Biomass / g d.w. ^b	F	\bar{x}	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	0.120	0.035	0.057	na ^a	na	na	na	na	na	0.029	0.471
		s	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	0.037	0.033	0.049								
	S	\bar{x}	na	na	na	0.903	0.588	0.633	0.677	0.63	0.508	1.620	0.71	0.797	na	na	0.034	0.724	0.480	0.309	0.021	0.48		
		s	na	na	na	0.124	0.173	0.21	0.337	0.106	0.19	0.045	0.217	0.138										
	DL	\bar{x}	0.044	na	na	na	na	na	0.363	0.34	0.495	0.148	0.145	0.173	na	na	na	na	0.724	0.021	0.882	0.026		
		s	0.031	na	na	na	na	na	0.102	0.08	0.07	0.033	0.01	0.012										
	BL	\bar{x}	0.307	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	Na	0.390	0.558	0.587	na	na	na	na	na	na	0.021	0.212		
		s	0.059	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	0.064	0.041	0.021										
	L	\bar{x}	1.047	1.143	1.225	1.567	1.098	1.277	0.890	1.27	0.968	0.465	0.635	0.710	0.480	0.663	0.157	0.724	0.032	0.146	0.020	0.032		
		s	0.103	0.251	0.18	0.301	0.351	0.486	0.135	0.076	0.288	0.044	0.057	0.010										
	TL	\bar{x}	1.398	1.143	1.225	1.567	1.098	1.277	1.253	1.61	1.463	1.003	1.338	1.470	0.157	0.663	0.157	0.724	0.034	0.386	0.021	0.034		
		s		0.104	0.251	0.18	0.301	0.351	0.486	0.110	0.095	0.273	0.095	0.077	0.040									
	TA	\bar{x}	1.398	1.143	1.225	2.470	1.685	1.91	1.930	2.24	1.97	2.743	2.082	2.323	0.157	0.663	0.077	0.724	0.157	0.386	0.021	0.289		
		s	0.104	0.251	0.18	0.419	0.521	0.695	0.433	0.183	0.397	0.085	0.256	0.223										
	U	\bar{x}	0.450	0.238	0.21	1.113	0.748	0.77	0.323	0.52	0.433	0.693	0.688	0.847	0.032	0.663	0.034	1	0.157	0.564	1.000	0.032		
		s		0.052	0.101	0.105	0.051	0.257	0.269	0.193	0.181	0.146	0.114	0.079	0.006									
	T	\bar{x}	1.848	1.38	1.435	3.583	2.433	2.68	2.253	2.76	2.403	3.435	2.77	3.17	0.157	0.663	0.034	0.724	0.077	0.248	0.021	0.077		
		s	0.156	0.343	0.282	0.466	0.773	0.96	0.525	0.274	0.432	0.150	0.332	0.229										
Height /cm	HI	\bar{x}	na	na	na	na	na	na	11.5	9.1	9	28.5	12.1	12.6	na	na	na	na	0.032	1	0.021	0.724		
		s	na	na	na	na	na	na	0.7	0.7	0.5	2.1	3.1	2.8										

^a na = not analyzed (due to lack of plant part, insufficient sample, or not relevant for the species); ^b d.w. = dry weight

Table 23 Metal concentration in plants. Legend: = uncontaminated soil, C = contaminated soil, I = inoculated soil, L = young leaves, S = shoots, R = roots. Bold numbers indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$); d.w. = dry weight (Neagoe et al. 2013).

Parameter	Parts of plant													Mann-Whitney-U test								
		Phacelia			Clover			Sunflower			Mustard			Phacelia		Clover		Sunflower		Mustard		
		U	C	I	U	C	I	U	C	I	U	C	I	U/ C	C/ I	U/ C	C/ I	U/ C	C/ I	U/ C	C/ I	
As / μg (g d.w.) ⁻¹	L	\bar{x}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	4.05	3.48	0.00	0.00	0.00	na	na	na	na	0.157	0.773	na	na
		s	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.17	1.40	0.00	0.00	0.00							
	S	\bar{x}	na	na	na	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	7.48	5.55	0.00	0.00	0.00	na	na	na	na	0.077	0.149	na	na
		s	na	na	na	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.83	2.00	0.00	0.00	0.00								
	R	\bar{x}	0.00	96.36	75.75	0.00	174.0	136.3	0.00	123.4	95.20	12.13	84.79	86.50	0.028	0.021	0.028	0.034	na	0.021	0.021	0.480
		s	0.00	13.77	7.68	0.00	19.89	12.94	0.00	11.24	14.65	3.86	7.66	7.70								
Cd / μg (g d.w.) ⁻¹	L	\bar{x}	0.00	1.88	2.85	0.00	3.42	2.00	0.00	1.93	2.05	1.03	7.84	6.93	0.028	0.110	0.289	0.064	0.034	0.885	0.021	0.372
		s	0.00	1.04	0.52	0.00	0.27	0.28	0.00	0.59	0.48	1.33	0.88	1.17								
	S	\bar{x}	na	na	na	0.00	2.90	2.26	0.00	1.33	1.85	0.43	3.94	4.45	na	na	na	0.064	0.034	0.309	0.021	0.212
		s	na	na	na	0.00	0.47	0.22	0.00	0.41	0.76	0.42	0.54	0.38								
	R	\bar{x}	2.90	27.80	21.95	1.60	54.31	47.89	0.00	43.53	43.78	1.46	15.41	15.75	0.034	0.564	0.034	0.480	0.034	0.564	0.020	0.285
		s	0.53	9.21	na	0.17	14.35	6.50	0.00	3.65	6.11	0.68	1.53	0.30								
Co / μg (g d.w.) ⁻¹	L	\bar{x}	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.10	7.29	3.80	0.00	1.73	0.93	1.40	4.80	5.25	na	na	0.034	0.034	0.034	0.146	0.021	0.724
		s	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.61	0.74	0.60	0.00	0.73	0.64	1.31	1.79	1.36								
	S	\bar{x}	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.20	2.30	1.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	na	na	1.000	0.480	na	na	na	na
		s	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.35	1.14	0.71	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00								
	R	\bar{x}	2.82	31.62	24.38	10.88	46.34	36.88	0.00	64.13	61.43	5.25	26.59	28.30	0.032	0.020	0.034	0.480	0.034	1.000	0.021	0.480
		s	0.16	2.79	1.21	2.09	19.53	7.69	0.00	3.36	10.69	0.82	3.69	1.61								
Cu / μg (g d.w.) ⁻¹	L	\bar{x}	3.27	25.19	27.36	19.56	22.74	18.34	27.87	39.15	37.28	20.40	36.28	29.63	0.032	0.663	0.034	0.289	0.034	0.564	0.021	0.289
		s	0.23	0.62	3.16	1.70	0.84	4.44	0.51	1.53	3.62	5.86	2.70	7.90								
	S	\bar{x}	na	na	na	12.17	17.65	14.41	16.40	23.30	24.95	14.12	19.13	17.35	na	na	0.034	0.034	0.034	0.386	0.028	0.074
		s	na	na	na	1.46	1.03	0.71	1.40	2.48	3.38	2.63	0.86	1.51								
	R	\bar{x}	40.86	205.2	172.1	27.25	122.0	231.9	36.03	222.2	178.3	28.01	180.2	150.9	0.034	0.083	0.034	0.034	0.034	0.021	0.021	1.000
		s	10.59	17.84	24.37	1.36	11.70	87.08	0.80	61.93	3.41	3.65	65.99	16.19								
Fe / μg (g d.w.) ⁻¹	L	\bar{x}	170.9	293.3	260.8	194.4	252.9	160.6	109.6	86.33	77.13	127.7	131.0	83.25	0.034	0.149	0.157	0.077	0.157	0.564	0.773	0.034
		s	26.78	17.25	32.01	30.12	45.94	45.36	20.27	14.21	22.11	36.22	19.56	9.96								
	S	\bar{x}	na	na	na	352.7	170.7	153.7	88.50	51.70	88.35	172.7	154.0	180.3	na	na	0.077	0.724	0.034	0.043	0.146	0.480
		s	na	na	na	128.6	94.89	27.37	25.84	7.81	36.72	10.96	27.04	43.22								
	R	\bar{x}	556.6	3235	1979	2355	2131	2367	2484	1957	1347	2843	2756	3509	0.034	0.021	0.480	0.724	0.480	0.021	0.773	0.480
		s	41.46	400.8	635.2	591.2	950.2	946.0	764.6	261.2	115.1	1139	921.7	899.4								
Mn / μg (g d.w.) ⁻¹	L	\bar{x}	56.67	76.93	84.60	96.51	94.66	55.70	96.33	204.6	144.7	44.22	45.69	57.50	0.077	0.149	1.000	0.034	0.032	0.021	1.000	0.289
		s	19.69	9.86	3.60	10.16	12.53	5.25	0.23	28.00	6.92	24.16	9.57	17.06								
	S	\bar{x}	na	na	na	12.31	11.99	9.71	20.10	65.80	65.43	10.69	18.11	17.40	na	na	0.480	0.034	0.034	0.564	0.021	0.724
		s	na	na	na	2.37	0.33	0.59	4.94	4.03	10.54	0.44	2.69	1.51								
	R	\bar{x}	48.70	67.95	58.85	93.10	156.1	148.3	28.77	63.93	83.33	18.20	93.47	94.63	0.212	0.248	0.077	0.480	0.034	0.021	0.021	0.480
		s	12.24	19.70	15.79	26.61	77.05	64.88	3.16	3.99	12.70	3.02	20.67	12.26								

Table 23 Continuation

Parameter	Parts of plant	Mann-Whitney-U test																				
		Phacelia			Clover			Sunflower			Mustard			Phacelia		Clover		Sunflower		Mustard		
		U	C	I	U	C	I	U	C	I	U	C	I	U/ C	C/ I	U/ C	C/ I	U/ C	C/ I	U/ C	C/ I	
Pb / μg (g d.w.) ⁻¹	L	\bar{x}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.30	3.23	3.05	3.05	2.40	2.30	na	na	na	na	0.212	0.885	0.189	0.714
		s	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.75	0.92	1.19	0.68	0.32	0.26								
	S	\bar{x}	na	na	na	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.63	4.68	2.80	0.00	0.00	0.00	na	na	na	na	0.034	0.386	na	na
		s	na	na	na	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.31	2.89	0.86	0.00	0.00	0.00								
	R	\bar{x}	0.00	9.87	7.65	0.00	7.20	8.66	3.27	9.70	9.70	1.91	11.59	13.18	na	0.248	na	1.000	0.032	0.773	0.021	1.000
		s	0.00	1.85	2.21	0.00	4.39	1.33	0.58	1.53	3.42	0.85	2.69	0.04								
U / μg (g d.w.) ⁻¹	L	\bar{x}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na
		s	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00								
	S	\bar{x}	na	na	na	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na
		s	na	na	na	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00								
	R	\bar{x}	0	71.50	64.00	0.00	28.84	44.73	0.00	30.15	25.43	0.00	39.11	30.60	na	0.083	na	0.077	na	0.021	na	0.077
		s	0	7.39	4.86	0.00	11.98	9.80	0.00	2.30	1.81	0.00	3.03	5.72								
Zn / μg (g d.w.) ⁻¹	L	\bar{x}	53.83	120.9	180.4	74.25	258.8	226.8	50.43	297.0	324.8	62.91	672.7	658.6	0.289	0.083	0.034	0.289	0.034	0.248	0.021	0.480
		s	17.18	62.22	16.96	14.96	39.10	18.75	2.71	52.68	22.10	20.85	29.10	23.39								
	S	\bar{x}	na	na	na	22.73	64.29	69.21	39.53	300.3	431.5	62.16	307.7	343.0	na	na	0.034	0.480	0.034	0.021	0.021	0.077
		s	na	na	na	0.67	1.49	6.70	3.59	25.46	50.94	11.12	23.03	25.20								
	R	\bar{x}	183.6	732.5	758.7	1323	653.7	687.0	69.20	1002	952.5	80.85	518.3	489.8	0.034	0.564	0.034	1.000	0.034	0.663	0.021	0.724
		s	19.92	201.7	72.08	34.87	127.1	127.9	2.40	74.72	141.0	13.81	81.10	36.37								

Table 24 Biochemical parameters of plants. Legend: BL = basal leaves, L = young leaves, S = shoots, R = roots, T = total, p = computed on protein base, b = computed on biomass base, Prot. = protein concentration, Chl = chlorophyll (total, a and b), Car. = total carotenoids, Tp = total protein in plants; bold values indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$). SOD = superoxide dismutase; POD = peroxidase; LP = lipid peroxidation; MDA = Malonaldehyde; d.w. = dry weight (Neagoe et al. 2013).

Parameter	Parts of plant	Mann-Whitney-U test																						
		Phacelia			Clover			Sunflower			Mustard			Phacelia		Clover		Sunflower		Mustard				
		U	C	I	U	C	I	U	C	I	U	C	I	U/ C	C/ I	U/ C	C/ I	U/ C	C/ I	U/ C	C/ I			
Chl. / mg (g d.w.) ⁻¹	BL	\bar{x}	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	3.018	7.463	6.604	na	na	na	na	na	na	0.021	0.289
		s	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	0.728	1.028	1.844								
	L	\bar{x}	na	na	na	7.772	8.435	9.138	na	na	na	5.845	7.337	6.73	na	na	1.000	0.157	na	na	na	na	0.021	0.077
		s	na	na	na	1.833	0.499	0.607	na	na	na	0.393	0.455	0.561										
	S	\bar{x}	na	na	na	0.552	0.599	0.646	na	na	na	1.063	1.048	0.974	na	na	1.000	0.157	na	na	na	na	0.773	0.48
		s	na	na	na	0.212	0.046	0.021	na	na	na	0.097	0.138	0.047										
Car. / mg (g d.w.) ⁻¹	BL	\bar{x}	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	0.249	0.278	0.255	na	na	na	na	na	na	0.083	0.289
		s	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	0.024	0.007	0.022								
	NL	\bar{x}	na	na	na	0.210	0.236	0.241	na	na	na	0.261	0.272	0.211	na	na	0.157	1.000	na	na	na	na	0.149	0.034
		s	na	na	na	0.023	0.023	0.002	na	na	na	0.014	0.003	0.031										
	S	\bar{x}	na	na	na	0.014	0.016	0.016	na	na	na	0.042	0.036	0.033	na	na	1.000	0.289	na	na	na	na	0.149	0.157
		s	na	na	na	0.004	0.001	0.001	na	na	na	0.004	0.006	0.001										
Prot. / mg (g d.w.) ⁻¹	L	\bar{x}	na	na	na	8.021	7.733	8.750	4.462	6.966	5.443	3.394	4.267	3.635	1.000	0.564	0.032	0.034	0.032	0.021	0.021	0.021	0.034	
		s	na	na	na	0.592	0.107	0.180	1.332	1.156	0.963	0.310	0.473	0.213										
	S	\bar{x}	7.813	8.424	9.245	14.53	10.63	14.88	7.865	10.50	8.203	8.416	12.54	9.124	na	na	0.032	0.031	0.077	0.083	0.020	0.077		
		s	0.477	2.147	0.88	0.271	3.016	0.492	0.271	0.772	0.646	1.157	1.959	0.98										
	R	\bar{x}	4.097	3.638	2.318	6.771	4.323	7.153	4.964	5.078	4.349	3.233	5.776	6.207	0.289	0.020	0.034	0.034	0.593	0.149	0.020	0.48		
		s	0.719	0.685	0.131	0.551	0.886	0.592	1.475	0.698	0.573	0.319	0.973	0.737										
Tp / mg (g d.w.) ⁻¹	L	\bar{x}	na	na	na	7.197	4.305	5.541	3.272	4.337	2.836	5.494	3.051	2.91	0.289	0.386	0.034	0.157	0.034	0.043	0.021	0.077		
		s	na	na	na	0.521	1.258	1.86	2.083	0.670	1.426	0.454	1.008	0.634										
	S	\bar{x}	10.89	9.616	11.37	22.81	11.08	19.04	9.858	16.93	12.06	8.383	16.80	13.43	na	na	0.034	0.289	0.724	0.149	0.021	0.724		
		s	0.492	3.029	2.339	4.749	3.290	7.567	0.931	1.982	2.797	0.909	2.923	1.74										
	R	\bar{x}	1.860	0.878	0.482	7.554	3.154	5.455	1.558	2.613	1.921	2.235	4.012	5.253	0.034	0.149	0.034	0.034	0.157	0.386	0.021	0.157		
		s	0.493	0.406	0.223	0.923	1.078	1.750	0.795	0.903	0.811	0.391	1.074	0.590										
T plant	\bar{x}	12.75	10.49	11.85	37.56	18.54	30.04	14.69	23.88	16.82	16.11	23.86	21.59	0.289	0.386	0.034	0.157	0.034	0.043	0.021	0.289			
	s	0.744	3.175	2.556	6.175	4.655	11.1	3.066	2.88	4.205	1.073	2.728	2.226											
SOD / U (mg pro- tein) ⁻¹	L	\bar{x}	57	256	207	132	388	29	92	100	54	200	265	264	0.034	0.248	0.034	0.034	0.513	0.034	0.248	0.724		
		s	24	46	59	47	175	16	16	8	17	138	53	56										
	S	\bar{x}	na	na	na	35	46	36	170	155	121	120	110	97	na	na	0.157	0.157	0.513	0.034	0.248	1.00		
		s	na	na	na	9	10	9	31	9	23	9	38	14										
	R	\bar{x}	28	48	31	141	200	137	54	108	108	176	94	92	0.289	0.245	0.034	0.034	0.034	0.289	0.021	1.00		
		s	3	24	21	12	7	10	24	12	2	41	26	31										

Table 24 Continuation

Parameter	Parts of plant	Mann-Whitney-U test																				
		Phacelia			Clover			Sunflower			Mustard			Phacelia		Clover		Sunflower		Mustard		
		U	C	I	U	C	I	U	C	I	U	C	I	U	C	C/I	U/C	U/C	C/I	U/C	C/I	
SOD / U (mg protein) ⁻¹	L	\bar{x}	57	256	207	132	388	29	92	100	54	200	265	264	0.034	0.248	0.034	0.034	0.513	0.034	0.248	0.724
		s	24	46	59	47	175	16	16	8	17	138	53	56								
	S	\bar{x}	na	na	na	35	46	36	170	155	121	120	110	97	na	na	0.157	0.157	0.513	0.034	0.248	1.00
		s	na	na	na	9	10	9	31	9	23	9	38	14								
	R	\bar{x}	115	168	74	952	864	976	255	543	487	565	523	560	0.289	0.083	1.000	0.048	0.034	0.289	0.386	1.000
		s	26	62	52	8	184	10	83	61	67	125	71	136								
POD / μ Units (mg protein) ⁻¹	L	\bar{x}	1.136	0.921	0.892	4.852	9.255	2.085	1.445	0.934	1.291	na	na	na	0.157	0.773	0.050	0.050	0.050	0.34	na	na
		s	0.076	0.207	0.115	2.723	1.620	1.378	0.172	0.142	0.168	na	na	na								
	S	\bar{x}	na	na	na	8.866	7.094	6.591	2.773	1.164	2.174	2.203	2.094	2.975	0.000	0.000	0.275	0.513	0.050	0.034	0.564	0.157
		s	na	na	na	2.292	1.487	1.473	1.593	0.115	0.818	0.332	0.506	0.692								
	R	\bar{x}	1.591	1.736	2.756	305.7	201.8	152.0	3.164	2.112	3.932	85.8	77.5	70.4	0.289	0.020	0.157	0.289	0.157	0.289	0.724	0.724
		s	0.321	0.398	0.192	89.7	59.7	16.0	2.634	0.508	0.730	21.5	43.5	36.9								
POD / μ Units (g d.w.) ⁻¹	L	\bar{x}	8.866	7.473	8.287	70.2	112.1	31.1	11.4	9.476	10.5	na	na	na	0.077	0.773	0.275	0.050	0.127	0.157	na	na
		s	0.633	0.785	1.680	38.7	21.4	20.9	1.294	0.908	0.874	na	na	na								
	S	\bar{x}	na	na	na	70.2	51.9	57.6	11.0	8.011	12.1	7.471	8.826	10.8	na	na	0.127	0.513	0.127	0.513	0.127	0.289
		s	na	na	na	13.9	10.6	12.8	3.086	2.086	5.852	1.317	1.548	2.251								
	R	\bar{x}	6.366	6.123	6.370	2043	910.5	1082	14.2	10.5	16.9	281.3	431.2	421.5	0.034	0.146	0.034	0.289	0.034	0.289	1.000	0.724
		s	0.056	0.336	0.097	492.3	401.0	67.2	9.576	1.279	2.025	95.9	221.3	174.5								
LP / μ mol TBArm (g d.w.) ⁻¹	L	\bar{x}	0.533	0.262	0.222	0.235	0.265	0.228	0.376	0.316	0.278	0.256	0.243	0.252	0.034	0.386	0.157	0.157	0.157	0.157	0.157	0.480
		s	0.087	0.055	0.028	0.020	0.021	0.023	0.069	0.025	0.032	0.032	0.017	0.022								
	S	\bar{x}	na	na	na	0.232	0.234	0.238	0.232	0.242	0.230	0.335	0.254	0.315	na	na	0.480	0.724	0.724	0.524	0.083	0.289
		s	na	na	na	0.049	0.012	0.027	0.042	0.033	0.038	0.061	0.034	0.066								
	R	\bar{x}	0.407	0.517	0.520	0.558	0.629	0.649	0.338	0.297	0.272	0.202	0.326	0.272	0.564	1.000	0.289	1.000	0.034	0.083	0.021	0.724
		s	0.036	0.176	0.000	0.048	0.102	0.042	0.005	0.019	0.012	0.013	0.105	0.026								

Table 25 Phosphorus concentrations in plants (mg kg⁻¹). Legend: A: B = ratio between aboveground and belowground biomasses, L: S = ratio between the biomasses of leaves and shoots, S : R = ratio between the biomasses of shoots and roots. Bold values of P indicate significant differences compared to the variant located at left in the table ($p < 0.05$). Ratios have been computed based on average value in a variant, and have no associated degree of significance (Neagoe et al. 2013).

Parameter	Phacelia			Clover			Sunflower			Mustard		
	U	C	I	U	C	I	U	C	I	U	C	I
P in leaves \bar{x}	3016	3988	4421	2282	2414	2424	3110	3295	3220	3443	3501	3668
s	962.5	662.1	61.85	19.75	186.9	103.5	52.92	191.6	400.3	742.7	1065	391.2
P in shoots \bar{x}	na	na	na	1566	1829	1945	923.3	1155	1237	2918	3544	3623
s	na	na	na	143.7	181.9	94.54	93.15	70.57	133.3	137.3	265.1	76.12
P in roots \bar{x}	3957	3619	3306	2625	2147	2416	1998	1663	1800b	2835	3390	3184
s	212.0	221.5	150.9	56.04	241.6	194.6	88.06	149.1	116.2	449.7	400.0	128.2
A : B	3.11	4.81	5.83	2.22	2.25	2.48	5.97	4.31	4.55	3.96	3.03	2.74
L : S	na ^a	na	na	1.73	1.87	2.02	1.85	2.56	2.88	0.62	1.88	1.85
S : R	na	na	na	0.81	0.79	0.82	2.09	1.21	1.17	2.34	1.03	0.94

na = not analyzed / not relevant for the specie

Phacelia presented a decrease of proteins as a result of inoculation in roots. SOD increased in all plants as a result of contamination, and the inoculation led to a decrease of SOD activity in most cases. This pattern was present for POD only in clover, while in sunflower, the inoculation led to increased activity in all parts of the plant. The LP was not significantly affected by inoculation except for a decrease in the roots of the sunflower.

Table 26 Percent variation in metal concentration in plants from reference to contaminated treatment (RC), and from contaminated to contaminated and inoculated treatment (CI). The sign “+” indicates an increase when the percent could not be computed because in the reference treatment the concentration was below the detection limit. Values in bold indicate a statistically significant variation (Mann-Whitney test, $p < 0.05$).

Metals in plant parts	Phacelia		Clover		Sunflower		Mustard	
	RC	CI	RC	CI	RC	CI	RC	CI
As								
L					+	-14		
S					+	-26		
R	+	-21	+	-22	+	-23	599	2
Cd								
L	+	52	+	-42	+	6	665	-12
S			+	-22	+	40	813	13
R	858	-21	3290	-12	+	1	954	2
Co								
L			247	-48	+	-46	243	9
S			5	-27				
R	1020	-23	326	-20	+	-4	406	6
Cu								
L	671	9	16	-19	40	-5	78	-18
S			45	-18	42	7	35	-9
R	402	-16	348	90	517	-20	543	-16
Fe								
L	72	-11	30	-37	-21	-11	3	-36
S			-52	-10	-42	71	-11	17
R	481	-39	-10	11	-21	-31	-3	27
Mn								
L	36	10	-2	-41	112	-29	3	26
S			-3	-19	126	-1	69	-4
R	40	-13	68	-5	122	30	413	1
Pb								
L					40	-5	-21	-4
S					638	-40		
R		-23		20	197	0	506	14
U								
R	+	-10	+	55	+	-16	+	-22
Zn								
L	125	49	249	-12	489	9	969	-2
S			183	8	659	44	395	11
R	299	4	392	5	1348	-5	541	-5

Table 27 Percent variation in plant height, biomass, P concentrations, and several biochemical variables from reference to contaminated treatment (RC), and from contaminated to contaminated and inoculated treatment (CI). Explanations are as in the legend of table 26.

Parameters	Phacelia		Clover		Sunflower		Mustard	
	RC	CI	RC	CI	RC	CI	RC	CI
Height / cm					-21	-1	-57	4
Biomass (d.w.)								
Flowers							-71	63
Shoots (S)			-35	8	-7	-19	-56	12
Dead leaves	-100				-6	46	-2	20
Basal leaves	-100						43	5
Young leaves (L)	9	7	-30	16	43	-24	37	12
Aboveground	-18	7	-32	13	16	-12	-24	12
Roots (R)	-47	-12	-33	3	61	-17	-1	23
Total	-25	4	-32	10	22	-13	-19	14
P concentration								
L	32	11	6	0	6	-2	2	5
S			17	6	25	7	21	2
R	-9	-9	-18	13	-17	8	20	-6
Concentration of proteins								
L	8	10	-27	40	33	-22	49	-27
S			-9	19	56	-22	26	-15
R	-11	-36	-36	65	2	-14	79	7
Activity of SOD (mg protein) ⁻¹								
L	350	-19	194	-92	8	-46	32	0
S			31	-22	-9	-22	-8	-12
R	72	-36	41	-31	99	0	-47	-1
Activity of SOD (g d.w. biomass) ⁻¹								
L	387	-14	96	-88	40	-56	105	-27
S			21	-7	44	-38	13	-24
R	45	-56	-9	13	113	-10	-8	7
Activity of POD (mg protein) ⁻¹								
L	-19	-3	91	-77	-35	38		
S			-20	-7	-58	87	-5	42
R	9	59	-34	-25	-33	86	-10	-9
Activity of POD (g d.w. biomass) ⁻¹								
L	-16	11	60	-72	-17	11		
S			-26	11	-27	51	18	22
R	-4	4	-55	19	-26	61	53	-2
LP (MDA content) / $\mu\text{mol (g d.w.)}^{-1}$								
L	-51	-15	13	-14	-16	-12	-5	4
S			1	2	4	-5	-24	24
R	27	1	13	3	-12	-8	61	-16

Summary discussions

Phosphorus-nutrition status

The optimal growth requirement for plants is in the range of 2000-5000 mg P (kg d.w.)⁻¹ (Marschner, 1988). In our experimental plants, P was in the range of 2000-3000 mg (kg d.w.)⁻¹, possibly below the optimal concentrations, especially in the case of clover and sunflower. Phosphorus efficiency (estimated by P concentrations in roots and shoots in all treatments) was in the order sunflower < clover < mustard < phacelia.

The increase of aboveground to belowground biomass ratio from U to C and to I treatments in the case of the mycorrhizal plant species indicates an improvement of P nutrition status from one treatment to another for these species. For mustard, the ratio pattern was reversed, although there was a not statistically significant increase of P concentration in mustard shoots and leaves as a result of inoculation.

Metals distribution

It is documented that the variation between the samples of As, Cd, Co, Cu, Fe, Mn, U, and Zn was due to taxonomic differences, and in many cases was larger than the variation due to environmental conditions at the sampling site. In our study, the species clearly behaved differently, even those known as hosts for mycorrhizal fungi. Most studies of effects of mycorrhization on plants grown in contaminated soils have dealt only with one or a few elements. We worked with soil that had a polymetallic contamination, so the results are very different. Also, if we want to compare our results with those in the literature, we must also take into account the *Glomus* species that was inoculated, which greatly influences the distribution of metals in plants. Metal distribution in our experiment varied with plant species and plant part.

Oxidative stress

Although plants have protective enzymatic and nonenzymatic mechanisms to scavenge ROS and alleviate their deleterious effects, the growing of plants on metal-contaminated soil frequently leads to an increase of oxidative stress in their tissues. It is documented that superoxide dismutase (SOD) usually acts as the first line of defense against ROS, and subsequently, catalase (CAT), glutathione reductase (GR), peroxidase (POD), lipid peroxidation (LP), etc. (Azcón et al., 2010). In our results, we found a positive relationship between improved P nutrition and protein synthesis in plant roots, which we supposed was responsible for the negative relationship between P and SOD (expressed on a total protein base). There is also the possibility that a higher concentration of P in plants protected them from toxicity of metals. However, a larger data set in terms of number of plant species and soils with different contamination degrees is needed in order to substantiate this hypothesis, which has to be put in the context of a stoichiometric approach of C, N, and P in AMF-plant system (Johnson, 2010) that includes adding metals.

In the case of mustard, a nonmycorrhizal species, there were positive effects of the inoculation with *G. intraradices* on plant development (in terms of biomass increase and oxidative stress decrease), although the P nutrition was not improved, as indicated by the above- / belowground biomass ratios and the P concentrations in plant parts. These positive results were probably associated with growth stimulation of fungi (i.e. development of extraradical hyphae, vesicles, and even intraradical hyphae) through rhizosphere effects. According to Pawłowska et al.

(1996) and *Giovannetti* (2004), the best criterion for classifying a species as nonhost plant is the lack of arbuscule formation after the soil inoculation with AMF. *Sinapis alba* cannot be considered a host-plant sp. in our case because arbuscules were not been observed. The particular situation of *Sinapis alba* found in our experiment requires the clarification of this plant species from the perspective of endophyte phenotypic plasticity compared to pathogenic fungi.

Conclusions

Mycorrhizal inoculation led to better plant development except sunflower. Surprisingly, a biomass increase in roots occurred as a result of inoculation of the nonmycorrhizal mustard. Protein concentrations decreased in sunflower and mustard, but increased in clover, reversing the decreasing effect of the contamination on this plant. Activity of SOD behaved as expected in most cases, indicating an increase in the oxidative stress as a result of contamination and a decrease after inoculation. In no cases did inoculation result in an increase of the oxidative stress. While data concerning heavy metals was not as expected in some cases, a clear response could be given concerning the benefits provided by the AMF inoculation which led to metal-stress alleviation in the most plant parts, especially for SOD activity and in some cases the decrease in protein concentrations as well. The decrease or increase in concentration of metals is not only related to the variation in oxidative stress from one treatment to another, but is also related to the relationship between variation in metals and phosphorus. Thus, we finally propose to focus in the future on how AMF modulates the effect of metals on oxidative stress in plants in the context of variability of macronutrients availability for plants. Due to the complexity of relationships, no general simple patterns were observed. Consequently, the design of remediation methods based on at the current level of knowledge requires site-specific solutions based on exploratory experiments at each site.

A pot experiment testing the effects of plant community structure and heavy metals contamination on the leaching of elements and functional traits of plants

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I conducted a pot-scale experiment in the growth chamber testing the effects of plant community structure and heavy metal contamination on element leachate and plant functional traits. The major aim was to test the effects of heavy metals and temperature on the role of grassland plants in producing several biogeochemical services. I tested the following three hypotheses: H1. Export of N and P by leaching is lower in pots with two species than in pots with a single plant species. H2. The morphometric and mechanical traits of the plants will be different in the case of two plant species variant, compared to the single-species variant. H3. The heavy metals contamination will have a significant effect on the phenomena tested by H1 and H2.

In this experiment I used soils from three locations: Paul Valley (VP) (latitude: 46.1589,

longitude: 23.2211 46o 09' 32" North and 23 o 13' 16" East), Meteş (MT) (latitude: 46.0969, longitude: 23.0969 46o 05'49" North, 23o 25' 17" East) and Copşa Mică (CM) (latitude: 46.1347, longitude: 24.3019 46° 8' 5" North, 24° 18' 7" East) as can be seen in figure 13.

Figure 13 Locations of the polluted soils used in experiment; left - Paul Valley (VP), middle - Meteş (MT), right - Copşa Mică (CM) (from Neagoe et al. 2022).

These soils were characterized from physicochemical point of view, as can be seen in table 28. It can be observed that for CM sites both the minimum and maximum values, in addition to a very high pH and LOI (values circled in green), are also much more polluted (see the values circled in red).

Table 28 Physico-chemical characterization of the soils (Neagoe et al. 2022) .

Variable	VP min.	VP max.	CM min.	CM max.	MT min.	MT max.
pH	5.79	5.00	7.81	7.89	5.86	5.51
EC [$\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$]	15.40	23.40	95.40	105.8	18.20	26.40
LOI [%]	5.93	7.09	10.04	10.54	7.22	8.46
N-NH ₄ ⁺	2.267	1.886	0.406	2.264	1.031	1.712
N-NO ₃ ⁻	24.24	16.66	88.72	108.8	0.183	18.82
N-NO ₂ ⁻	0.041	0.037	0.504	0.183	0.033	0.020
P-PO ₄ ³⁻	2.708	6.163	15.22	18.82	1.924	8.748
Variable	VP min.	VP max.	CM min.	CM max.	MT min.	MT max.
Pb	55.91	674.5	181.4	1376	70.43	168.6
As	16.95	74.92	15.2	76.5	16.02	35.0
Zn	109.5	270.3	357.7	2746	112.3	188.3
Cu	113.8	413.6	54.26	175.7	64.7	117.2
Ni	56.37	54.48	90.22	93.23	52.47	75.37

After the physicochemical characterization of the soils, I established the experimental design which consisted of 14 treatments of 5 replicates, each treatment in which a single plant species (*Agrostis capillaris* L.) was sown had a pair with a mixture of *A. capillaris* L. and *Melilotus albus* Medick.). Thus, two control treatments were established (the first two in table 29) and two treatments for min. and two for max. for each of the three locations already described. To test H1, three pot floods were simulated during plant development.

The following variables were measured from the sampled leachate: pH, elements measured by ICP-MS, TKN - by Kjeldahl system, inorganic nitrogen (N-NH₄⁺, N-NO₃⁻, N-NO₂⁻) and bioavailable phosphorus (P-PO₄³⁻) by UV-VIS. To test H2 after three months of plant development, the following variables were measured from plants: root morphometrical variables by WinRhizo software: average root diameters, root length density (RLD), number of tips, number of bifurcations, number of crossings; root mechanical variables by Instron instrument: tensile strength and Young modulus (elasticity). Exploratory: stomatal conductance by Leaf porometer, Decagon SC-1. To test H3 were measured from leachate, soil and plants: elements by ICP-MS.

Table 29 Experimental design (adapted after Neagoe et al. 2022).

Nr.crt.	Experimental variant / Cod	Soil	Plant species
1 (5)	Top soil (TS A1)	unpolluted	<i>A. capillaris</i> (A1)
2 (5)	Top soil (TS A2,M)	unpolluted	<i>A. capillaris</i> (A2) + <i>M. albus</i> (M)
3 (5)	Paul Valley (VP min. A1)	min. polluted	<i>A. capillaris</i> (A1)
4 (5)	Paul Valley (VP min. A2, M)	max. polluted	<i>A. capillaris</i> (A2) + <i>M. albus</i> (M)
5 (5)	Paul Valley (VP max. A1)	min. polluted	<i>A. capillaris</i> (A1)
6 (5)	Paul Valley (VP max. A2, M)	max. polluted	<i>A. capillaris</i> (A2) + <i>M. albus</i> (M)
7 (5)	Copșa Mică (CM min. A1)	min. polluted	<i>A. capillaris</i> (A1)
8 (5)	Copșa Mică (CM min. A2, M)	max. polluted	<i>A. capillaris</i> (A2) + <i>M. albus</i> (M)
9 (5)	Copșa Mică (CM max. A1)	min. polluted	<i>A. capillaris</i> (A1)
10 (5)	Copșa Mică (CM max. A2, M)	max. polluted	<i>A. capillaris</i> (A2) + <i>M. albus</i> (M)
11 (5)	Meteseș (MT min., A1)	min. polluted	<i>A. capillaris</i> (A1)
12 (5)	Meteseș (MT min., A2, M)	max. polluted	<i>A. capillaris</i> (A2) + <i>M. albus</i> (M)
13 (5)	Meteseș (MT max., A1)	min. polluted	<i>A. capillaris</i> (A1)
14 (5)	Meteseș (MT max., A2, M)	max. polluted	<i>A. capillaris</i> (A2) + <i>M. albus</i> (M)

Selected findings

The export of N and P by leachate (H1)

The number of species directly controls the export of Kjeldahl N (mg) and indirectly the nitrate fluxes (by interaction with the location of soil sampling and the pollution degree). The other fluxes are controlled only by sampling time, soil location, and pollution degree (see figure 14).

Figure 14 The export of N as TKN by leachate; left for 1 species, b) right for 2 species (Neagoe et al. 2022).

Root morphometrical traits (H2) by *Agrostis capillaris*

- The number of species directly controls the root intensity (number of crossing) and indirectly all other variables (by interaction with the pollution degree) except the root volume and average diameter.
- The length of the thick roots (> 0.6 mm) depends directly only on the soil sampling location (see figure 15).

Root mechanical traits (H2) by *Agrostis capillaris* L.

- Root resistance to traction is negatively correlated with root diameter.
- The residuals of root resistance to traction extracted after the correlation with root diameter are significantly controlled by the soil pollution (variable “range”) and the number of species in the pot.
- The elasticity did not vary significantly with the experimental factors (see figure 16).

Effect / pANOVA	Av. Diam. [mm]	LengthPerVol [cm ⁻³] (RLD)	RootVolum ePot [m ⁻³]	TipsPot	Forks Pot	Crossings Pot	0<L<= 0.100	0.600<L <=0.700
Intercept	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Code Soil	0.000	0.001	0.029	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.003	0.000
Code range	0.000	0.028	0.115	0.031	0.035	0.019	0.029	0.054
Code Sp.	0.087	0.080	0.546	0.073	0.055	0.040	0.077	0.121
Code Soil*Code range	0.025	0.005	0.645	0.003	0.001	0.002	0.013	0.001
Code Soil*Code Sp.	0.530	0.242	0.838	0.304	0.245	0.213	0.260	0.324
Code range*Code Sp.	0.810	0.024	0.926	0.023	0.018	0.021	0.036	0.008
Code Soil*Code range*Code Sp.	0.380	0.109	0.878	0.085	0.107	0.117	0.124	0.080

Figure 15 Root morphometrical traits; left crossings, right average diameter (Neagoe et al. 2022).

Figure 16 Increase of root resistance to traction (RT) from 1 species to 2 species (Neagoe et al. 2022).

The effect of metals (H3)

- Direct effect of the variable “range”: code 1 site with small pollution, code 2 sampling site with large pollution. Proved by ANOVA for fluxes of N and P, mechanical and morphometrical traits.
- Indirect effect of “range” by interaction with variables soil sampling location and number of species. Proved by ANOVA for fluxes and morphometrical traits.
- Proof of the effect of “range” on the concentration of metals in *Agrostis* aboveground vegetation (ANOVA). There is an effect of the soil sampling location and number of species on the accumulation of metals, further confirming H3 (see figure 17).
- The accumulation of Zn, Cu, and Pb in aboveground parts is negatively correlated with

- LgRLD, proving the influence of metals on the export of elements by the root traits.
- The metals in roots are not yet analyzed (might provide better correlations with RLD) (see figure 18).
- Aboveground biomass is predicted by Kjeldahl N and Pb concentrations, as for RLD as can be seen in table 30

Figure 17 The effect of metals in shoots(coded S) (Cu_S, Pb_S and Zn_S) (Neagoe et al. 2022).

Figure 18 Kjeldahl N concentration in roots and Pb in shoots predict the RLD value (Neagoe et al. 2022).

Table 30 Prediction of the aboveground biomass by TKN and Pb concentrations (Neagoe et al. 2022)

Regression Summary for Dependent Variable: Biom._Sus (Exp_1_PCE_Agrostis_Anova) R= .74845224 R ² = .56018075 Adjusted R ² = .54222894 F(2,49)=31.205 p<.00000 Std.Error of estimate: .21472 Exclude condition: v1=1 (control)						
	b*	Std.Err	b	Std.Err	t(49)	p-value
N=52						
Intercept			-0.234	0.116	-2.018	0.049
TKN_S	0.702	0.095	0.419	0.057	7.409	0.000
Pb_S	-0.257	0.095	-0.002	0.001	-2.715	0.009

Discussions

- We found correlations between morphometrical properties and the export of metals as can be observed in figure 19.

Figure 19 Correlations between morphometrical properties and the export of metals

- *PCA of traits and fluxes*
 - There are many positive and negative correlations between traits and fluxes.
 - The pots are separated by variants in the PCA factors space (see figure 20).

Figure 20 PCA of traits and fluxes (Neagoie et al. 2022).

- *Stomatal conductance is correlated with the export of Kjeldahl N* as can be seen in figure 21 left; 21 right is depicted variation of average diameter of *Melilotus albus* (Neagoie et al 2022).
- *Stomatal conductance is significantly influenced by time and number of species* as can be seen in figure 22.

Figure 21 Stomatal conductance correlated with the export of TKN (left). Variation of average diameter of *Melilotus albus* (right).

Conclusions on hypotheses

H1. The number of species directly decreased the export of TKN [mg]; the number of species indirectly affects the nitrate fluxes (by interaction with location of soil sampling and pollution

degree); the other fluxes of N and P forms are controlled only by sampling time, soil location, and pollution degree.

Figure 22 Variation of stomatal conductance by time and number of species (Neagoe et al. 2022).

H2. The number of species directly controls the root intensity (number of crossing) and indirectly all other variables (by interaction with the pollution degree) except the root volume and average diameter; the length of the thick roots (> 0.6 mm) depends directly only on the soil sampling location; the residuals of root resistance to traction extracted after the correlation with root diameter are significantly controlled by the soil pollution (variable “range”) and the number of species in the pot; the elasticity did not vary significantly with the experimental factors. *H3.* The effect of heavy metals is proved first of all by the variable “range” (degree of soil pollution, from a minimum - code 1 - to a maximum - code 2 pollution in the contaminated area). The effect of range on fluxes and traits occurs either as a single variable or in interaction with other variables); the “range” variable significantly affected heavy Cu, Zn, and Pb concentrations in plants.

Conclusions about mechanisms

- N, Cu, Zn and Pb concentrations controlled root length density in plants.
- There are many correlations between N and P fluxes and root traits. The strongest ones are between LgRLD and the flux of Klejdahl N (positive) and between LgRLD and the flux of nitrate (negative).

B4.2.2 Lysimeter experiments

The extra inoculation of the repacked contaminated soil with *Streptomyces* species reversed the effect of the mycorrhization by increasing metal concentrations in the leachate form lysimeters, and increasing the plant-exported metals by stimulating plant growth

These researches was published by Neagoe et al. 2009 in *Chemie der Erde Geochemistry journal*, 69, S 2, 2009, pp. 57-73, (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemer.2008.01.002>) in an article titled "The effect of bioremediation methods involving different degrees of soil disturbance on the export of metals by leaching and by plant uptake"

Next, I will present a published experiment conducted at lysimeter scale to investigate the effects of two bioremediation methods on metal export from a former uranium mine located near Ronneburg, Thuringia, Germany. The first method consisted of applying compost and top soil to the contaminated soil. These amendments were carried out on plots established in the field one year before soil sampling for the lysimeter-scale experiment (this research is in details described in the section B4.2.3). I will refer to these two modified soils as previously disturbed or intact soils. The second method involved mixing soil from the contaminated plot (soil without any amendments) with expanded clay, mycorrhizal fungi and *Streptomyces* sp., soils that will be referred to as recently disturbed or repacked.

The purpose of this study was to investigate the export of metals by leachate and plants, from soil contaminated with heavy metals in different degrees of disturbance, amended with compost, top soil, expanded clay, or inoculated with fungi and bacteria.

The **working hypotheses** were the following:

1. Microorganism inoculation of recently disturbed contaminated soil will alter the export of metals.
2. Export of metals from recently disturbed treatments will be greater than export from previously disturbed treatments (1 year before the lysimeter experiment) and will follow patterns interpretable by succession theory (these patterns are not shown here).

Experimental conditions, design and measured variables

Soil sampled from two contaminated amended (with municipal compost and top soil) field plots and from one unamended contaminated plot, all located on a former uranium leach pile were physico-chemically characterized at the time of running the experiment with lysimeters, as can be seen in table 31.

The experimental design consisted of ex-situ outdoor experiments using zero-tension lysimeters with intact soil to simulate natural field conditions. Soil was sampled in the undisturbed (intact) structure from contaminated plots used as control and coded **C**, municipal compost amended contaminated plots coded **CK**, and top soil amended contaminated plots coded **CTS**, directly into metal lysimeters (five replicates each).

Table 31 General characterization of the soils used in the experiments (10 cm means rhizospheric soil, 50 cm means the whole height of lysimeters) (Neagoe et al. 2009).

Parameter/soil code	C		CK		CTS		CB	
	10 cm	50 cm	10 cm	50 cm	10 cm	50 cm	Min.	Max.
Moisture (%)	9.7	8.0	23	10	13	8.9	9.7	9.9
pH (H ₂ O) (%)	4.8	5.1	8.1	4.1	6.6	3.8	3.4	5.1
pH (CaCl ₂) (%)	4.2	4.5	7.5	4.0	6.1	3.8	3.0	4.4
Eh (mV)	470	390	230	500	360	510	440	460
EC (µS/cm)	670	269	412	940	146	1010	360	380
N-NH ₄ ⁺ (µg/g d.w.)	4.7	8.4	3.9	4.0	4.9	9.9	3.6	4.7
N-NO ₃ ⁻ (µg/g d.w.)	0.4	1.0	1.6	1.4	0.1	0.9	0.2	0.3
N-NO ₂ ⁻ (µg/g d.w.)	0.1	0.2	0.6	0.2	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.1
P-PO ₄ ³⁻ (µg/g d.w.)	8.9	23	122	17	30	21	8.9	13
S-SO ₄ ²⁻ (µg/g d.w.)	642	1699	461	2245	148	2431	642	1387

Another 15 lysimeters were repacked after inoculation of soil C in the following treatments: C plus expanded clay (trade name Blähton) coded **CB**, C plus expanded clay which mycorrhizal fungi (*Glomus intraradices*, now renamed *Rhizophagus irregularis*, spores VAM 510, 115 spores / g soil) coded **CBM** and CBM plus a mixture of *Streptomyces tendae* and *Streptomyces acidiscabies*, coded **CBMS**, each in 5 replicates, repacked in polyethylene lysimeters. All 30 lysimeters have been 50 cm high, and 20 cm in diameter. The soil used for the repacked treatments (CB, CBM, and CBMS) had the same physicochemical characteristics at the time the experiment was set up and, consequently, a single set of values is presented in table 31. Soil samples were sampled from the first 10 cm (the most biologically active zone) and from the total depth (50 cm) of the lysimeters.

Three types of disturbances can be compared: C with CK, vs. C with CTS, vs. C with CB. From the perspective of time, within the time scale of the experiment, the intact soil lysimeters group includes only one truly undisturbed soil (C), and two soils (CK and CTS) disturbed 1 year before sampling. In the longer term, even the control soil is actually a disturbed soil resulting from mining activity. It is not acceptable to compare the intact soil group with a mixed soil group, but it makes sense to compare C soil with soils having different types - times of disturbance, and modulated by other treatments such as inoculation (see figure 23).

The soils in the lysimeters were sowed with a mixture of seeds from two acidophilic plant species. These were a grass (*Festuca rubra* L.) and a clover (*Melilotus albus* Medick.). During the three months study period, plants were watered as needed with rainwater to maintain soil moisture. During the experiment, two heavy rain events were recorded, so it was possible to sample twice the leachate from the 30 lysimeters. At the end of the experiment, the plants were harvested, washed with tap water and then several times with ultrapure water, weighed (fresh biomass) and divided for analysis into the above- and belowground plant parts. All plant material was frozen and lyophilized for dry biomass determination, then ground in a stainless-steel mill equipped with a cooling system, and stored at -20 °C until processing.

Variables measured from soil

The following variables were measured: soil moisture, pH, redox potential (Eh), electrical conductivity (EC), ammonium (N-NH₄⁺), nitrate (N-NO₃⁻), nitrite (N-NO₂⁻), phosphate (P-PO₄³⁻), sulphate (S-SO₄²⁻), and elements content.

Figure 23 Experimental design of the disturbed (repacked) and undisturbed (intact soil) lysimeters that were sowed with a mixture of two plant species in the same growing season. On the right can be seen the high salt content of the intact soils (Neagoe et al. 2011).

Variable measured from leachate

The following variables were measured: volume, pH, Eh, hydraulic conductivity, dissolved organic carbon (DOC), and elements content.

Variable measured from plants

The following variables were measured: fresh and dry biomass, non-enzymatic and enzymatic variables (these are not presented in the published article), and elements content.

Selected findings

The export of metals by leachate from the repacked lysimeters

Table 32 presents data describing the export of metals through leachate from the repacked lysimeters. The volume of leachate was significantly higher (Mann-Whitney test) after the second rain event than after the first rain event, for any treatment. The pH of the leachate was not significantly different between the two rain events in any treatment. Eh was significantly lower in leachate during of the second rain in control and mycorrhizal fungi (CBM) treatment, and DOC concentration was significantly lower in all treatments. The concentrations of Pb and Cr were higher in the leachate during the second rain event after the mycorrhizal fungi treatment, than the concentrations the control (C) leachate. Cu concentrations were not significantly different between the two rain events. The concentrations of the other metals were significantly lower in leachate during the second event, as follows: U in all treatments, Ni in control and mycorrhizal fungi treatments, and Mn, Ca, Mg only in treatment with mycorrhizal fungi (without significant decreases to any of the other treatments).

Table 32 Presentation of the volume of exported leachate from the repacked lysimeters after the first and second rain, the values of physico-chemical parameters and DOC, and selected metal concentrations in the percolated water (Neagoe et al. 2009).

Variable/treatment		Rain 1			Rain 2			Mann-Whitney					
		CB	CBM	CBMS	CB	CBM	CBMS	1	1	2	3	4	5
		1	2	3	4	5	6	2	4	5	6	5	6
Volume [ml]	Av.	260	316	308	1155	968	930	+	+	+	+	-	NS
	SD	12	15	10	62	49	187						
pH	Av.	6.3	6.5	6.4	6.6	6.4	6.7	NS	NS	NS	NS	-	+
	SD	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.1						
Eh [mV]	Av.	510	506	522	406	416	548	NS	-	-	NS	NS	+
	SD	14	19	51	11	5	27						
DOC [mg l ⁻¹]	Av.	19	9.2	12	6.0	4.0	4.3	NS	-	-	-	-	NS
	SD	17	1.2	4.2	1.0	0.8	0.8						
Pb [µg/l]	Av.	0.7	0.6	2.3	0.7	2.2	1.4	NS	NS	+	NS	NS	NS
	SD	0.1	0.0	2.4	0.0	3.3	1.0						
U [µg l ⁻¹]	Av.	3.1	6.2	3.5	1.0	0.7	0.7	NS	-	-	-	NS	NS
	SD	1.8	2.7	1.5	0.7	0.0	0.0						
Cr [µg l ⁻¹]	Av.	0.8	0.8	1.9	4.7	5.8	4.1	NS	+	+	NS	NS	NS
	SD	0.0	0.0	2.5	1.2	1.8	1.4						
Cu [µg l ⁻¹]	Av.	44	63	85	32	59	105	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
	SD	17	52	52	21	75	120						
Ni [mg l ⁻¹]	Av.	9.5	13	8.8	4.6	2.4	6.0	NS	-	-	NS	NS	+
	SD	4.7	1.7	4.8	1.9	0.8	2.0						
Mn [mg l ⁻¹]	Av.	157	218	147	106	37	96	NS	NS	-	NS	-	+
	SD	88	28	93	40	16	31						
Ca [mg l ⁻¹]	Av.	417	549	454	392	280	442	+	NS	-	NS	-	+
	SD	83	35	110	63	71	74						
Mg [mg l ⁻¹]	Av.	733	1053	750	519	235	469	NS	NS	-	NS	-	+
	SD	390	107	394	191	87	100						

Tests of significance have been performed between the average values (Av.) of the parameters coded with numbers as indicated in columns below the codes of the experimental variants (+* means significantly higher, -* significantly lower, NS no significant difference).

As mentioned in the previous paragraph, after fungi inoculation there was a significant increase in leachate volume during the first rain event, but a decrease in volume during the second event. Also, pH and COD concentration significantly decreased in the leachate during the second event as a result of fungi inoculation. By comparison, the further inoculation with *Streptomyces* had no significant effect on leachate volume. However, it was associated with a significant increase in leachate pH and Eh during the second rain event compared to the CBM treatment. The effects of inoculation on concentrations of metals in the leachate were almost absent during the first rain event. Only Ca had a significantly higher concentration in the mycorrhizal fungi treatment. However, the effects of inoculation were observed at the time of the second rain.

The concentration of Ni, Mn, Ca and Mg in the leachate decreased significantly as a result of mycorrhization, but then significantly increased as a result of *Streptomyces* inoculation. However, the concentration metals with low-mobility metals such as Pb, U, Cr and Cu in

leachate was not significantly different between the experimental treatments. Thus, the patterns of variation among experimental treatments differed between the first rain (low rainfall, small plants) and the second rain events (high rainfall, large plants). The total export of metals by water from the repacked treatments was mainly controlled by the second rain event, which happened to be more intense. Differences between treatments in relation to the total metal export are controlled by differences specific to the stage of full plant development, when the second rain event occurred. Inoculation of the repacked contaminated soil with mycorrhizal fungi decreased the leaching of metals. Additional inoculation of the repacked contaminated soil with *Streptomyces* partly reversed the effect of the mycorrhizal fungi by increasing leachate metal concentrations.

The export of metals by plants from the repacked lysimeters

The export of metals by plants grown in the repacked lysimeters is presented in figure 24. The biomass of *Festuca* sp. was significantly larger ($p < 0.05$ Mann–Whitney test) than the biomass of *Melilotus* sp., in all treatments. Because of this situation, the metal export pattern was not strongly influenced by *Melilotus* sp. in these experimental treatments. The mycorrhizal fungi significantly increased the below- and aboveground biomass of *Melilotus* sp., and had no significant effects on the biomass of *Festuca* sp. The further inoculation with *Streptomyces* resulted in even stronger increase of *Melilotus* sp. biomass, but also of the aboveground biomass of *Festuca* sp. The mycorrhizal fungi decreased the concentration of metals in the belowground biomass of *Melilotus* sp. Its effect was metal dependent in the aboveground biomass of *Melilotus* and *Festuca* sp. A significant increase of U, Ni and Mn in the aboveground biomass of *Festuca* sp. could be observed. The further inoculation with *Streptomyces* led to a decrease of the accumulation of Ni and Cu in the belowground parts of *Festuca* sp. and *Melilotus* sp., and to a decrease of the accumulation of Mn in *Festuca* sp. In most cases, the pattern of the plant metal stock followed the pattern of the biomass variation. This occurred because metals concentration either had the same trend of variation as biomass, or did not vary between experimental treatments. However, in some cases the changes in the metal concentration were very strong and in opposite direction to the change in biomass (i.e., when biomass increased metal concentration decreased, or vice versa). In this situation, the metal stock followed the concentration trend, not the biomass trend. The effect of the inoculation with mycorrhizal fungi on the total metal export by plants was metal dependent. The effect of extra inoculation of contaminated soil repacked with *Streptomyces* on total export by plants was also metal dependent.

The export of metals by leachate from the intact lysimeters

Table 33 presents data describing the leachate export of metals from intact lysimeters. Leachate volume, pH, Eh or DOC concentration were not significantly different between the two rain events for any of the experimental treatments. However, the concentration of Pb was significantly lower in the leachate during the second rain event in compost treatment (CK). U and Cu concentrations were significantly lower in the leachate from the CTS top soil treatment after the second rain. The concentrations of the other metals were not significantly different between the two rain events. The volume of leachate in the control during the first rain was too low to allow the variables determination in all replicates. Consequently, no significant differences could be reported between treatments in this respect during the first rain event. The amendment with compost led to an increase in leachate volume during both rain events.

Figure 24 Average stocks of metals exported by plants, from the repacked lysimeters. Average dry weight biomass was inserted on the graphs. The same scale was used in all graphs in order to allow easy comparison. Stars indicate significant changes in biomass compared to the nearby treatment on the left (Neagoe et al. 2009).

The amendment with top soil led to an even higher significantly increase of volume during the second rain. DOC concentrations significantly increased in the leachate during the second event as a result of the amendment with compost or top soil. The pH, Eh and DOC concentrations did not significantly differ between the compost and topsoil treatments. The effects of amendments on leachate metal concentrations could not be tested for the first rain event, but an inspection of Table 33 suggests large increases in concentrations of Pb, U and Cr in the leachate, and an increase in Cu concentration, as a result of amendments. This observation was also valid for the data describing the second rain event, and in this case, there was statistical confirmation. The amended top soil treatment did not differ from the compost treatment during the first rain event. During the second event, the concentration of Pb in the leachate from the CTS treatment was significantly higher than that in the leachate from the CK treatment and that of Ca was significantly lower. Thus, in contrast to the situation for repacked lysimeters, for the intact lysimeters there were rather similar patterns of variation between the experimental treatments during the first and second rain events. The total metal export by water from the intact treatments was controlled by the experimental treatment, and not by the time of the rain event. Soil amendments, either with compost or with top soil, strongly increased the amount of leachate by lysimeters, as well as the concentration of some metals in the leachate. The higher

hydraulic conductivity of the lysimeters was confirmed by independent measurements in the field. Figure 25 shows the distribution of the metals concentrations in the soil profile near the sampling sites for the intact treatments, as well as the hydraulic conductivity of each soil horizon. Increased metal concentrations could be observed in the control treatment down to 50 cm, and decreasing concentrations in the amended treatments, i.e., the clearest in the 1 CK experiment treatment.

Table 33 Presentation of the volume of exported leachate from the intact lysimeters after the first and second rain, the values of physicochemical variables and DOC, and selected leachate metal concentrations (Neagoe et al. 2009).

Variable/treatment		Rain 1			Rain 2			Mann-Whitney					
		C	CK	CTS	C	CK	CTS	1	1	2	3	4	5
		1	2	3	4	5	6	2	4	5	6	5	6
Volume	Av.	24	327	204	46	312	379	NA	NA	NS	NS	+	+
[ml]	SD	54	170	11	92	297	390						
pH	Av.	4.9	4.3	4.5	4.3	4.4	4.6	NA	NA	NS	NS	NS	NS
	SD		0.3	0.3	1.0	0.2	0.3						
Eh	Av.	520	572	602	487	564	506	NA	NA	NS	NS	NS	NS
[mV]	SD		42	37	12	42	5.5						
DOC	Av.	8.5	17	10	5.5	19	18	NA	NA	NS	NS	+	NS
[mg l ⁻¹]	SD		0.6	12		3.1	23						
Pb	Av.	1.1	9.1	4.7	1.3	5.6	7.4	NA	NA	-*	NS	+	+
[µg/l]	SD		2.2	1.7	1.0	1.7	5.4						
U	Av.	24	770	674	13	801	79	NA	NA	NS	-*	+	NS
[µg l ⁻¹]	SD		452	475	12	289	115						
Cr	Av.	0.8	16	53	10	30	15	NA	NA	NS	NS	+	NS
[µg l ⁻¹]	SD		12	88	1.6	17	5.2						
Cu	Av.	868	1098	1562	70	1007	327	NA	NA	NS	-*	+	NS
[µg l ⁻¹]	SD		557	855	58	260	423						
Ni	Av.	4.9	11	9.8	5.3	9.6	10	NA	NA	NS	NS	NS	NS
[mg l ⁻¹]	SD		2.1	4.6	3.7	2.3	5.4						
Mn	Av.	93	188	112	82	156	111	NA	NA	NS	NS	NS	NS
[mg l ⁻¹]	SD		29	66	66	40	56						
Ca	Av.	630	583	535	617	587	500	NA	NA	NS	NS	NS	-*
[mg l ⁻¹]	SD		35	50	34	18	48						
Mg	Av.	634	831	682	905	682	948	NA	NA	NS	NS	NS	NS
[mg l ⁻¹]	SD		134	181	290	191	483						

Tests of significance have been performed between the average values (Av.) of the variables coded with numbers as indicated in columns below the codes of the experimental variants (+* significantly higher, -* significantly lower, NS no significant difference, NA test not applicable due to single sample in C for rain one).

The apparently unexpected higher average of the standardized concentration in the upper 10 cm horizon of the CK treatment compared to the control treatment was due to high concentrations of Ca and Mg in the 10 cm horizon of the compost-amended soil (while the concentration of most toxic elements was lower than in control treatment). The particular pattern of metal distribution in the control treatment was associated with a comparatively much lower soil hydraulic conductivity than in the amended treatments.

Figure 25 Distribution of hydraulic conductivity (HC) (round markers, right y-axes) and concentrations of the analysed elements in the soil of the intact lysimeters (left: control, middle: amended with compost, right: amended with top soil) (Neagoe et al. 2009).

The export of metals by plants from the intact lysimeters

The export of metals by plants from the intact lysimeters is presented in figure 26. The biomass of *Festuca* sp. was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$ Mann–Whitney test) than the biomass of *Melilotus* sp. in the control and top soil amended treatment, and lower in the compost amended treatment. The differences between the biomasses of *Festuca* and *Melilotus* sp. were not as high as in the repacked treatments. As a result of this situation, *Melilotus* sp. played an important role in the plant metal export, in intact lysimeter treatments.

Figure 26 Average stocks of metals exported by leachate from the repacked lysimeters: average dry weight biomass (g d.w.). The same scale was used in all graphs in order to allow comparison. Stars indicate significant variations compared to the nearby left treatment (Neagoe et al. 2009).

The compost amendment significantly increased the biomass of *Melilotus* sp., and possibly also the aboveground biomass of *Festuca* sp. The top soil amendment also had a positive effect on the biomass, but to less extent than the top soil amendment. The compost or top soil amendments decreased the concentration of U and Mg in the biomass of *Festuca* sp. The addition of compost increased Cr concentration in both plant species. The effects of amendments on metal accumulation in *Melilotus* were less, because they were masked by the huge effects on biomass production. In all *Melilotus* sp. cases, the pattern of metal export by plants followed the pattern of biomass variation. In the case of *Festuca* sp., the changes in the metal concentration mentioned in the previous paragraph were strong enough to reverse the export trends caused by biomass variation. However, the overall effect of amendments on the total metal export by plants was less metal-dependent than for the repacked treatments.

Comparison of the export of metals from repacked and intact lysimeters

In the previous sections, the differences between repacked and intact lysimeters occurring in the patterns of metal percolation during rain events, and in the pattern of metal export by plant species were analyzed. The focus was on the dynamic of metal concentrations in the upper soil horizon and on the relative importance of metal export by plants compared with the export by leachate. Table 34 shows the concentrations of metals in the upper soil horizon before and after the experiment.

34 Concentrations of metals in the upper soil horizon before and after experiment (Neagoe et al. 2009).

Variable/treatment	Repacked lysimeteres				Intact lysimeters						Mann-Whitney			
	Before		After		Before			After			1	1	1	
	CB	CB	CBM	CBMS	C	CK	CTS	C	CK	CTS	2	3	4	
Pb	Av.	11	12	13	12	13	22	26	13	28	21	+	+	+
[$\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$]	SD	0	0.3	0.3	0.3				0.3	8.8	2.2			
U	Av.	5.4	5.2	6.2	5.4	6.6	3.7	2.0	6.3	4.2	3.4	NS	NS	NS
[$\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$]	SD	0	0.5	1.8	0.1				0.2	0.3	0.2			
Cr	Av.	22	31	31	28	25	23	21	38	29	27	+	NS	+
[$\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$]	SD	0	1.9	4.6	0.4				4.5	2.0	0.8			
Cu	Av.	26	39	38	37	24	33	17	32	42	24	+	+	+
[$\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$]	SD	0	0.9	1.1	0.4				0.5	1.4	1.4			
Ni	Av.	56	52	50	50	39	45	25	46	44	36	-	NS	-
[$\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$]	SD	0.00	0.7	2.7	1.2				2.1	3.5	2.2			
Mn	Av.	674	645	585	655	333	609	608	363	592	518	NS	NS	NS
[$\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$]	SD	0	31	83	20				12	44	59			
Ca	Av.	2155	1191	1366	1334	1109	14108	2398	1170	12745	1891	-	-	-
[$\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$]	SD	0	131	126	53				176	3462	219			
Mg	Av.	3279	2859	2874	2817	3140	4465	3282	2994	4212	2998	-	-	-
[$\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$]	SD	0	80	60	47				80	426	91			

The concentrations of metals in the repacked soil were identical in all replicates before the experiments, so SD of the concentrations is 0.

In the repacked treatments, Pb and Cu concentrations increased with time (Mann-Whitney test) in all experimental treatments. In the same treatments, the Cr concentration increased significantly in the control and CBMS treatment but not significantly in the CBM treatment. Contrary to this pattern, Ca, Mg, and Ni concentrations decreased in all experimental treatments (significantly in all cases except Ni in the CBM treatment). The differences

characterizing treatments using intact lysimeters, although following roughly the same pattern as for the repacked treatments, were significant in fewer cases. However, Cu concentrations significantly increased with time in all the intact treatments, Cr concentration significantly increased in the CB and CBMS treatments, and Mg significantly decreased in any treatment over time. Figure 27 compares the average of total metal export from the repacked and intact lysimeters. The point here was not to look at the absolute values (which depend on the experimental design), but to compare the experimental treatments and pathways of exports. The export of Pb, Cr, Ni, Mn, Ca, and Mg was higher in the repacked lysimeters compared with the intact lysimeters (computed as average of CK and CTS), while the total U and Cu export was lower. The relative role of plants in the total export of Pb, U and Cu (estimated by the plant export / water export ratio) was higher in the repacked lysimeters. The relative role of the leachate export of Ni, Ca and Mg in the repacked vs. intact lysimeters was higher. The role of plants vs. leachate in the export of Cr and Mn was more or less the same in the two sets of experimental treatments. The experimental treatments were characterized by different degrees of soil disturbance. The control was the least disturbed and the mixed expanded clay treatments was the most disturbed. In this context, one could predict that the C treatment would have the lowest relative export of metals compared to the metal stock in the soil.

Figure 27 The average export of metals (absolute amount) from repacked and intact experimental treatments (up - by leachate, down - by plants, inserted - total). The total export is presented for control (C), intact treatment (I, computed as average of CK and CTS), and repacked treatments (R). The scale of the inserted graphs is similar with that of larger graphs (unit:mg per lysimeter) (Neagoe et al. 2009).

At the other extreme, the CB, CBM and CBMS treatments would have the highest metal export compared with the soil metal stock. This prediction was confirmed by our computations excepting for U and Cu, as presented in table 35 (the total metals exported as a proportion of the concentrations of metals present in the upper soil horizon).

Table 35 Total metals exported as a percent (%) of the stock of metals in the 0-10 cm soil horizon at the start of the experiment (Neagoe et al. 2009).

Elements	Experimental treatments											
	C		CK		CTS		CB		CBM		CBMS	
	Av.	SD	Av.	SD	Av.	SD	Av.	SD	Av.	SD	Av.	SD
Pb	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.06	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.02
U	0.02	0.01	2.59	2.27	0.74	0.36	0.05	0.01	0.09	0.04	0.05	0.02
Cr	0.08	0.06	0.54	0.38	0.35	0.12	1.21	0.49	0.79	0.66	0.31	0.18
Cu	0.06	0.07	0.71	0.54	0.44	0.10	0.33	0.05	0.38	0.19	0.36	0.09
Ni	0.23	0.38	4.31	2.93	2.90	1.48	6.47	1.82	5.36	0.82	6.45	1.25
Mn	0.24	0.40	6.35	4.31	2.92	1.71	10.87	3.18	7.10	1.13	8.71	1.73
Ca	0.72	1.20	2.70	1.61	4.95	2.80	12.29	1.87	9.78	1.49	12.03	1.38
Mg	0.35	0.61	3.84	2.58	2.77	1.43	10.94	2.23	7.80	1.13	9.13	1.65

Since the soils were identical at the beginning of the experiment, except for the different inoculations, the differences between the repacked treatments were insignificant during the first rain event (small plants, low rainfall). During the second rain event, however, the differences were significant (large plants, large precipitation). Treatment with mycorrhizal fungi resulted in a significant decrease in leachate volume over time the second rain, probably due to the stronger development of plant roots. Metal concentrations in the leachate from the second rain were, in many cases, lower than those in the leachate from the first rain. This could be due to some depletion of the mobile fraction after the first rain, but most likely due to the dilution effect resulting from the large amount of leachate during the second rain event. This amount was greater than that percolated from intact lysimeters, where the pattern of decline in metal concentrations between rain events was not as evident. Uranium bioaccumulation increased greatly as a result of inoculation with mycorrhizal fungi. This fact may be due to a specific behavior of the plant species undergoing mycorrhization. It is known that the uptake and subsequent translocation of U is dependent on the plant species, *Festuca* sp. being a genus with a high bioaccumulation factor for uranium. This behavior was associated with a higher biomass of *Festuca*, which led to a more important role of plants than leachate, in the export of U from the repacked lysimeters.

Double inoculation with *G. intraradices* and *Streptomyces* sp. strongly stimulated plant development. However, it is widely accepted in the literature that studies of mycorrhizal interactions with rhizosphere bacteria show variable results depending on plant species, abiotic environment and soil community structure. In the CBMS treatment, there was a significant decrease in leachate DOC concentration during the second rain event compared to the first rain event, but the changes in Mn concentration and Eh were not significant. The higher values of their variables in CBMS compared to CBM during the second rain it was actually due to a significant decrease of Eh and concentrations of Ni, Mn, Ca and Mn in leachate from the CBM during the second rain event compared to the first. This decrease in variable values was probably due to a change in the functioning of the microbial community from the CBM

treatment. This means that during plant development, the function of microbial communities from two treatments, CBM and CBMS, had different dynamics, with different biogeochemical consequences.

Based on the above results and discussions, it could be concluded that *the first working hypotheses were confirmed*, i.e. the inoculation of contaminated soil repackaged and inoculated with microorganisms changed the export of metals. The use of this mixture in bioremediation methods of sites contaminated with metals can be recommended because it can lead to an increase in plant biomass. Attention should be paid, however, to the eventual mobilization of metals (followed by leaching) as a result of changes in DOC quality in the soil.

It is known that the fluxes by plants are usually locally recycled in the field, and thus only the transfer by leachate counts as an export from the system. On the other hand, other mechanisms of metal export are possible in the field, especially by runoff. After all, the plant development is very low on the control soil and thus the erosion potential is high, the purpose of the sets of bioremediation methods tested in this study being mostly the phytostabilization of the area. With these precautions, it can be concluded that *the second working hypotheses was confirmed*: the export of metals from the repacked treatments was in many cases higher than the export from the intact treatments and the results are interpretable in terms of succession theory.

Conclusions

The average total export of metals from the repacked treatments was higher than the export from the intact treatments for most metals, and the relative role of the export by leaching compared to the export by plants uptake increased as a result of strong soil disturbance. It could also be observed that the plant uptake in the export of metals from the repacked treatments frequently played a more important role than the leaching. After the inoculation of the repacked contaminated soil with mycorrhizal fungi a decrease in the leaching of metals was observed, accompanied to a certain extent, by an increase in the export of metals by plants as a results of stimulating plants growth. The extra inoculation of the repacked contaminated soil with *Streptomyces* sp. reversed the effect of the mycorrhization by increasing metal concentrations in the leachate, and also increased the metals exported by plants to some extent, by stimulating plants growth. The results supported the idea that the success of bioremediation approaches depends on the appropriate knowledge of the initial system state and of successional processes in contaminated areas. Bioremediation techniques can induce a disturbance of the system in the first phases of the process. Long-term studies on population of contaminated sites are needed in order to fully assess the effects of the manipulation on the successional processes and the real success of bioremediation.

The extra inoculation of the repacked contaminated soil with *Streptomyces* species reversed the effect of the mycorrhization by increasing metal concentrations in the leachate form lysimeters, and increasing the plant-exported metals by stimulating plant growth

These researches was published by *Nicoară et al. 2010 in Proceedings of MEEMB Conference, Timisoara, Romania.*

Further, I will present the second published lysimeter experiment with soil contaminated with heavy metals without inoculum, with AMF (*Glomus intraradices*) inoculum, and with AMF and *Streptomyces* species (two *Streptomyces* species (*Streptomyces tendae* and *Streptomyces*

acidiscabies) and two plant species (plant crops consisted of 4 alternating successions of *Secale cereale* L. and *Helianthus annuus* L.).

The purpose of this study was to investigate the influence of mycorrhizal fungi and streptomycetes on heavy metal mobility and plant uptake in a soil enriched with Pb (about 2000 mg/kg), Cu (about 250 mg/kg) and Zn (about 500 mg/kg) through atmospheric deposition from a battery factory near Bucharest, Romania.

Experimental conditions, design and measured variables

This experiment is much more complex compared to the one at point a, because in addition to the very different intact sampling mode (see figure 28 left), each lysimeter was equipped as can be seen in the figure 28 (right). The lysimeters were equipped with temperature, redox and humidity sensors and data was constantly monitored with a datalogger. Field tension was simulated at the bottom of the monoliths with a vacuum pump, also used to sample leachate.

Figure 28 Sampling method and equipment of light tension lysimeters (adapted after Nicoară et al. 2010)

A schematic representation of a lysimeter system is provided in figure 29. The installation was housed in an underground chamber for the purpose of thermal insulation. Plant crops consisted of 4 alternating *Secale cereale* L. (sowed in autumn, harvested in summer) and *Helianthus annuus* L. (sowed in mid-summer and harvested in autumn). Experimental treatments consisted of 2 noninoculated, negative control replicates, 4 replicates inoculated with AMF (*Glomus intraradices*) in expanded clay (10%, mixed in the first 20 cm of soil), and 4 replicates amended both with *G. intraradices* and the streptomycetes: *Streptomyces acidiscabies* and *Streptomyces tendae* in liquid CSA growth medium, 10 ml per lysimeter.

Variables measured from soil: sampling in the field in the immediate vicinity of each of lysimeters from 0 to 60 cm depth in 10 cm increments and after each plant harvest at 0 - 15 and 15 - 30 cm depths. The variables of interest were: pH, humidity (H), mineral N as ammonium (N-NH₄⁺), nitrate (N-NO₃⁻), and nitrite (N-NO₂⁻), bioavailable phosphate (P-PO₄³⁻), and pseudo-total content of elements by ICP-MS after digestion with *aqua regia*.

Variables measured from plant samples

The following variables were measured: element content after wet digestion, protein content, enzyme activity such as superoxide dismutase (SOD) and peroxidase (POD), lipid peroxidase (LP) and, photosynthetic pigments (chlorophyll a and b and carotenoids).

Variable measured from leachate

Leachate was sampled after major rain events, leachate volumes and element concentrations in were recorded.

Figure 29 Lysimeter system experimental design and photos with rye and sunflower cultures (adapted after Nicoară et al. 2010).

Microorganism analysis

Root fragments were cleared with KOH and colored with lactophenol blue for mycorrhiza differentiation. Roots were divided into approximately 1cm long fragments and around 20 fragments from each experimental variant were observed.

Selected findings

We focused mainly on Pb, Zn and Cu, as they were the major contaminants in the studied area. We were unable to correlate differences between mean plant tissue metal concentrations and stress for unamended reference against fungi amended and fungi and streptomycetes amended variants due to insufficient biomass for one of the R variants, however comparing the latter two yielded significant results. Most important, there were lower metal concentrations in the roots of fungi and streptomycetes amended replicates, but other parameters also varied in a significant manner (figure 30).

Figure 30 Linear logarithmic relationship between the total biomass of each lysimeters and their plant metal concentrations. R = unamended reference, F = amended with mycorrhizal fungi, S = amended with fungi and streptomycetes (after Nicoară et al. 2010).

In the case of Pb, Cu and Zn soil concentrations at the time of monolith sampling were decreasing with depth (Figure 31).

Figure 31 Soil metal concentration. R = unamended reference, F = amended with mycorrhizal fungi, S = amended with fungi and streptomycetes (after Nicoară et al. 2010).

The monitoring of humidity and redox potential was done with the help of the data logger. A two-month monitoring of moisture variation showed differences in drainage between some of the lysimeters. Drainage patterns that were homogeneous with each other is repeated, with a decrease in the moisture dynamics with depth, explained by slowing the flow of water as it seeped deeper into the monoliths after irrigation or a weather event.

Differences were recorded as follows: the F2 lysimeter, one of those with plant growth problems (due to excessive soil heterogeneity) showed higher moisture dynamics at 30 cm than at 10 cm, showing a possible preferential flow in that area. The S2 lysimeter also showed consistently higher moisture at 50 cm, indicating possible drainage problems (figure 32).

Figure 31 Humidity monitoring data. **a** normal dynamic in negative reference lysimeter R1. **b** possible preferential flow in AMF lysimeter F2. **c** drainage problems in fungi and streptomycetes amended lysimeter S2. **d** normal dynamic in lysimeter S4 (after Nicoară et al. 2010).

Monitoring the evolution of the redox potential gave the most interesting results on low biomass production of R2, F2 and F4 replicates. These lysimeters showed a much stronger decrease in redox potential in the first 10 cm of soil under rain events than the other lysimeters (Figure 32).

Figure 32 Redox monitoring data. Lysimeters R1, F1 and S3 show a normal redox evolution. Lysimeters R2, F2 and F4 show stronger drops in redox at rain events (after Nicoară et al. 2010).

Conclusions

Using streptomycetes as additional inoculum significantly influences soil conditions, plant health and metal uptake. As this is a multistage experiment, the complete data will be available only after the publication of the entire experiment with four successive cultures.

B4.2.3 Field plot experiment

The effect of soil amendments on plant performance in an area affected by acid mine drainage

This research was published, as I mentioned in section B3, by Neagoe *et al.* 2005 in the journal *Geochemistry*, 65, Supplement 1, 115-129 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemer.2005.06.009>), the title of the article is identical to the title of this subchapter. Next, I will briefly describe a field-scale experiment that was conducted somewhat independently from the two other pot and lysimeter-scale experiments.

The experimental site was a disturbed soil where uranium leaching occurred (East Thuringia, Germany). Uranium mining in the former East Germany was extensive from 1946 to 1990, with a total production of over 200 kt. This output made East Germany third behind Canada and Australia, still 14 years after ending uranium production. The exploited area was 460 ha and the waste dumps had a volume of $125 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$. Since 1990, a substantial effort has been made to remediate the affected area, with these remedial actions continuing for several decades, to date. Prior to initiation of any remedial action, the leachate recorded a pyrite concentration of 0.7 wt%, 70 g t^{-1} uranium and $< 3.40 \text{ Bq g}^{-1}$ radium. Among these remedial actions it is also the researchers presented in this section, conducted within the framework of the experiment carried out at the scale of the experimental plots.

The *aim* of this experiment was to prove the effects of amendments (top soil, municipal compost and urea) used for the first time in Wismut area, more specifically in Gessenwiese site, on plant performance and on the uptake of heavy metals by plants from contaminated soil.

Experimental conditions and design and measured variables

To investigate the effects of the selected amendments, an experimental design consisting of three Latin square lattices was used. Areas of 20 x 20 m were delineated for the experimental lattice plot. On one of the plots, a 5 cm layer of commercially available municipal compost was added evenly over the entire surface. On the second experimental plot, a 5 cm thick layer of top soil was added. A third duplicate control plots was delineated and left without any amendment (see figure 33). A 12 x 12 m Latin square was placed in the center of each plot, so each of the nine subplots measured 4 x 4 m. Two plant species, *Lupinus angustifolius* L. and *Secale cereale* L. were sowed and growed, in a controlled environment. To counteract the lack of nutrients, the soil was fertilized with urea as a solution ($20 \text{ kg N x ha}^{-1}$). This fertilization was added once to one-third of the Latin squares (1 month after sowing, but before partially harvesting plants for analysis) and twice (1 and 3 months after sowing and before the second harvesting of plants) in another third; the last third was kept unfertilized as a control. Plants were sampled (5 individuals from each subplot) after one month, in July, and at the end of the experiment, in October. Soil samples were sampled from all subplots at the beginning of the experiment, before sowing, as well as at the end of the experiment in October.

Soil analyses were performed on the upper 10 cm of soil assumed to be the most biologically active area (i.e. max. root concentration) and also, on the area most subjected to erosion and atmospheric deposition processes. Yellow-brown loamy sand soil (10-20% clay) was analysed for moisture, pH, organic matter, mineral N concentrations, sulphate, phosphate and heavy metals. The elements analysis was done after digestion (*aqua regia*), and the analysed elements were: Al, As, Ba, Ca, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Mo, Ni, P, Pb, Ti, V, U and Zn.

Figure 33 Plot-scale experiment in Gessenwiese, Thuringia (Latin square lattice) adapted after Neagoe et al. 2011)

After sampling, *plants* were weighed (w.w.) and divided for analysis into aboveground and underground parts. Plant roots were washed briefly (repeated five times) with tap water and finally with distilled water. All plant material was lyophilized (d.w.), ground, and stored at -20 °C until further processing. Enzyme activity, such as superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity and peroxidase (POD) activity were assessed. Assimilatory pigments (chlorophyll and carotenoids) and the concentration of elements were determined. The combined effect of amendment with compost or topsoil with the addition of urea is not further discussed, as no additional effects from the urea were observed. The presentation of the results will focus on the three treatments (adding compost, top soil, or urea) to improve plant performance in the Gessenwiese area.

Selected findings

There were no data for urea 1x and urea 2x in July; it was applied after harvesting the plants. Figure 34 shows the increase in biomass from control plots, to the plots where urea was applied twice. It was also found that with increased nitrogen content, lupins were almost eliminated by competition with rye. A plausible explanation was the different life expectancy of lupins, which may change with increased fertilization. Acidic soils are also known to be an important constraint on crop production. In figure 35 it can be seen how the biomass increased significantly between the experimental variants and the fact that the lupins were definitively eliminated after the second urea application in October in the compost treatment.

The soil was characterized to investigate the causes of this increase in biomass. The concentration of most metals in the soil did not change significantly ($p < 0.05$) between treatments, so it was impossible to attribute the increase in biomass to such a cause.

Figure 34 The effect of urea 1, and urea 2 times addition on the total biomass and relative abundance of plants in control plots (Neagoe et al. 2006, Jena oral presentation)

Figure 35 The effect of urea 1 and urea 2 times addition on total biomass and relative abundance of plants in control, top soil and compost treatments (Neagoe et al. 2006, Jena oral presentation)

Table 36 shows the concentration of elements in soil identified for 0, 3 and 4 soil treatments (it is assumed that the addition of urea (treatments 1 and 2) did not change the metal concentration, so, treatment 1 and 2 were treated as treatment 0). If we look at the soil variables (table 37), an important difference can be observed between the experimental variants. In July, there was a strong increase in inorganic N and phosphate and a decrease in sulfate after adding top soil or compost.

Table 36 The effect of treatments on the element concentration in soil (mg kg⁻¹) (Neagoe et al. 2005)

Elements	Experimental variants			Elements	Experimental variants		
	0 Control	3 Top soil	4 Compost		0 Control	3 Top soil	4 Compost
Al	7370	9540	9720	Mg	2100	4180	2810
As	17.00	23.00	24.00	Mn	365.0	429.0	414.0
Ba	60.00	135.0	78.00	Mo	2.00	2.00	1.00
Ca	660.0	15900	806.0	Ni	40.00	37.00	55.00
Cd	2.00	2.00	3.00	P	321.0	1490	414.0
Co	13.00	11.00	19.00	Pb	n.d.	30	n.d.
Cr	22.00	28.00	29.00	Sr	10.00	73.00	13.00
Cu	9.00	29.00	23.00	Ti	318.0	286.0	399.0
Fe	22300	21600	28800	V	30.00	31.00	39.00
K	696.0	4620	871.0	Zn	44.00	117.0	61.00

n.d. indicate that the metal was not detected

This trend was still present in October for phosphate and sulphate, but not for N. This can be explained by the greater mobility and bioavailability of N. Nitrogen reduction in compost was stronger than in top soil, probably due to the higher mobility of N in this organic mixture. In addition to transfer to plants, some immobilization in microbial biomass may have occurred as well as a leaching to lower soil horizons. However, high biomass growth was the most likely cause to this N depletion. Soil humidity and LOI⁴ (from 2.91% in the case of control to 5.27% in top soil and 11.40% in compost) significantly increased with the addition of compost and top soil. This increase was present as early as October, suggesting that the change in water uptake of the organic material that was responsible for the higher water holding capacity was maintained during the growing season. This clearly showed the importance of these amendments for improving soil quality. A lower plant metal content was expected to be found in plants grown under these experimental conditions. Indeed, if we look at metal concentrations in plants (table 38 for rye and 39 for lupine), a pattern of decreasing concentrations of the following elements was observed: Al, As, Cd, Co, Cu, Cr, Fe, Mg, Mn, Ni, Pb (only for rye), V and Zn from control (0) to compost (4).

This decrease could be explained by the higher pH of the soil, but also by the better condition of the soil nutrients, as it is present not only in the case of top soil and compost, but also in the case of urea addition. On the other hand, some metal concentrations varied in both plant species and almost all experimental variants were in/or above the excessive, or toxicity range. In tables 38 and 39 show the uptake of an excess amount of aluminum in the lupine harvested in October, as well as in the rye, in the control treatments at both harvesting times.

⁴ LOI - Loss On Ignition

Table 37 Soil variables in the experimental treatments (humidity in %, other variables in mg kg⁻¹ d.w.) (Neagoe et al. 2005).

		July			Mann-Whitney $p < 0.05$	October					Mann-Whitney $p < 0.05$
		0 Control	3 Top soil	4 Compost		0 Control	1 Urea 1	2 Urea 2	3 Top soil	4 Compost	
pH	Mean	4.63	6.01	7.39	0-3, 0-4, 3-4	4.70	4.69	4.66	6.04	7.49	0-3, 0-4, 1-3, 1-4, 2-3, 2-4, 3-4
	SD	0.03	0.11	0.15		0.06	0.08	0.00	0.11	0.15	
Humidity	Mean	6.78	7.43	14.90	0-4, 3-4	9.81	9.64	7.67	13.78	18.00	0-3, 0-4, 1-3, 1-4, 2-3, 2-4, 3-4
	SD	0.67	2.36	4.22		0.64	0.80	2.69	0.82	4.07	
N-NH ₄	Mean	2.76	5.65	16.10	0-3, 0-4, 3-4	2.43	1.95	2.17	2.37	0.86	(1-4), 3-4
	SD	1.55	1.29	5.20		1.63	1.23	2.74	1.84	0.42	
N-NO ₃	Mean	1.46	21.30	92.70	0-3, 0-4, 3-4	2.26	2.32	2.93	0.94	2.99	0-3, 1-3, (2-3), 3-4
	SD	0.76	9.59	45.50		0.71	0.48	1.67	0.45	2.11	
N-NO ₂	Mean	0.02	0.06	0.24	0-3, 0-4, 3-4	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.07	0.10	(0-3), 0-4, 1-3, 1-4, 2-3, 2-4, (3-4)
	SD	0.01	0.05	0.12		0.03	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.03	
P-PO ₄	Mean	6.91	25.00	76.50	0-3, 0-4, 3-4	12.90	19.20	8.24	27.00	106.0	0-2, 0-3, 0-4, 1-2 1-4, 2-3, 2-4, 3-4
	SD	2.01	6.57	22.50		0.40	9.72	0.81	5.04	37.30	
S-SO ₄	Mean	1944	375.0	845.0	0-3, 0-4	3010	1790	1860	443.0	648.0	0-3, 0-4, 2-3, 2-4
	SD	1002	171.0	705.0		780.0	1460	815.0	174.0	547.0	

Mann Whitney test indicates statistically significant differences between data, parentheses indicate a p level between 0.1 and 0.05.

In these tables, gray areas show decreasing concentration from control (0), one (1) or two times (2) urea application, top soil (3) to compost (4), while bold and underlined values the increase of concentration from control to the amendments; n.d. indicate that the metal was not detected, and $p < 0.05$ indicates significant difference according to Mann-Whitney. The manganese content of terrestrial plants depends on the species, the stage of growth, and the part of the plant involved. Also, it can be high at a low pH of the soil (details can be found in the full article).

In this research, Mn concentration in lupine as well as in rye are far over the excessive or toxicity level which is approximated in mature leaf tissue for various species between 400-1000 mg kg⁻¹ d.w. Also, the excessive or toxicity level of Ni was slightly exceeded in the case of rye only in control variants but, very high in the case of lupine, especially in October 2004, in all experimental variants. Other metals such Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, V and Zn have been found in excessive or toxicity level in the case of lupine. It was found at the end of the experiment that the growth of the lupine was severely affected by the toxicity stress, causing the disappearance of the lupine in some experimental variants. Another remarkable effect that emphasizes the role of soil nutrients status is the increase in P and K concentration in plants from the minimum in the control to the maximum in the compost. The effects were not similar in lupine in the case of P, which was stable in October 2004 in treatment [0] and [3].

The low concentration of so many metals in plants, as well as the mitigation of drought, reflected by increase soil humidity, should have resulted to a reduced oxidative stress and more energy for investment in photosynthetic pigments and in proteins. SOD and POD activities in both plant species decreased from control to compost amendments, and chlorophyll increased significantly (Tables 40 a and b). It is documented that Zn, Fe, Cu, Mn or Ni are directly involved in protein synthesis. Despite the toxic level of Mn found in the experimental compost and top soil treatments, they showed significantly higher protein production than the control. The data in tables 40 a and b show that the plants did not suffer from metal toxicity. The decrease in SOD and POD activity and the increase in protein level were an indication that the plants did not suffer from metal stress in July.

Normally, nutrient toxicity influences SOD and POD activities, but changes in enzyme activities depend on type and duration the stress. However, although the doubling of biomass in the compost field was not balanced by a decrease in metal concentration, the total amount of metals extracted in the aboveground parts of the plants was not only controlled by biomass production, but in principle also by the size part of the plant. This implies that the quality of vegetation cover could be addressed by improving soil quality through amendments. It would be possible without risking a massive transfer of metals from soil to plants because the total amount of metals extracted from soil was not correlated with biomass production.

Table 38 Metal concentrations in rye (Neagoe et al. 2005).

	Aboveground										Belowground										
	July					October					July					October					
	0	3	4	<i>p</i> <0.05	0	1	2	3	4	<i>p</i> <0.05	0	3	4	<i>p</i> <0.05	0	1	2	3	4	<i>p</i> <0.05	
Al	Mean	1250	703.0	396.0	0-4	1690	1600	729.0	395.0	264.0	0-2, 0-3, 0-4, 3-4	2420	3350	1880.0	3-4	8830	7390	7990	4360	1010	2-3, 2-4, 3-4
	SD	309.0	364.0	223.0		285.0	1180	137.0	111	97.30		1150	738	625.00		1010	821.0	1560	1840	445.0	
As	Mean	2.59	0.79	n.d.	0-4	3.45	3.71	2.40	0.23	n.d.	0-3, 0-4, 3-4	4.01	5.72	4.25		17.70	16.20	16.70	10.10	1.53	2-3, 2-4, 3-4
	SD	0.35	1.37	n.d.		0.89	1.61	0.37	0.69	n.d.		2.99	2.10	0.93		0.71	0.14	3.80	9.44	1.54	
Ba	Mean	14.90	21.30	8.90	3-4	16.30	17.40	8.55	24.50	9.88	0-2, (0-4), 3-4	24.40	41.50	36.14		87.00	68.50	81.00	64.30	22.20	2-4, 3-4
	SD	5.64	16.74	2.00		1.92	11.90	1.58	9.71	4.61		10.40	6.35	17.80		18.00	9.62	26.00	18.20	7.07	
Cu	Mean	358.0	204.0	305.0		282.0	251.0	209.0	250.0	208.0	0-2, 0-3, 3-4	132.0	301.0	416.0	0-3, 0-4	172.0	132.0	137.0	245.0	299.0	2-3, 2-4, 3-4
	SD	132.0	93.00	35.30		85.00	60.00	53.30	46.20	35.00		22.90	86.20	58.00		58.10	4.04	8.53	31.90	63.30	
Cd	Mean	0.20	0.22	n.d.		0.76	0.66	0.44	0.05	n.d.	0-3, 0-4, 3-4	1.10	0.91	n.d.	0-4, 3-4	2.58	2.33	2.51	1.77	0.21	(2-3), 2-4, 3-4
	SD	0.35	0.38	n.d.		0.15	0.37	0.41	0.18	n.d.		0.28	0.14	n.d.		0.18	0.53	0.10	0.64	0.32	
Co	Mean	5.10	3.81	0.50	0-4	6.16	5.94	4.74	0.37	0.69	0-3, 0-4, 3-4	19.40	4.21	3.70	3-0, 0-4	35.70	33.20	33.20	4.72	2.40	2-3, 2-4, 3-4
	SD	2.06	6.03	0.79		1.51	4.02	1.76	0.67	0.46		2.57	1.05	0.60		5.48	13.60	1.96	1.83	1.10	
Cr	Mean	4.04	3.71	3.18		4.03	3.42	1.76	1.17	1.13	0-2, 0-3	6.19	16.74	10.10	0-3	60.20	61.70	53.05	17.40	2.77	2-3, 2-4, 3-4
	SD	1.50	1.18	1.88		1.36	3.31	0.41	0.31	0.47		3.52	6.84	8.49		13.00	9.26	3.03	15.80	1.21	
Cu	Mean	14.80	8.40	10.50	0-3, 0-4	9.31	9.53	9.89	7.69	8.62	0-3, 0-4, 3-4	12.00	18.00	14.60	0-3, 3-4	38.10	34.80	33.00	20.60	11.70	2-3, 2-4, 3-4
	SD	1.91	1.92	1.00		1.25	1.68	1.45	1.16	1.75		3.00	0.62	1.64		2.38	3.83	5.63	5.81	2.63	
Fe	Mean	728.0	965.0	402.0	0-4, 3-4	948.0	1180	777.0	272.0	299.0	0-3, 0-4, 3-4	2110	2810	1170		11690	12100	11800	5310	768.0	2-3, 2-4, 3-4
	SD	45.00	68.00	118.0		140.0	990.0	309.0	134.0	117.0		1090	1970	800.0		3610	6910	5150	5750	627.0	
K	Mean	23000	23000	39400	0-4	15700	15800	17700	20400	28200	0-3, 0-4, 3-4	9220	22000	23900	0-3, 0-4	6760	5100	6360	7130	10800	2-4, 3-4
	SD	1800	7530	4420		5690	3580	1400	9010	6130		2700	1270	3730		1240.0	1120.0	1840.0	800.00	1150.0	
Mg	Mean	3990	2170	1990	0-4	2410	2340	2630	1870	1610	0-3, 0-4	1740	1920	2170		2520	2500	2710	1450	1410	2-3, 2-4
	SD	635	1280	593.0		460.0	776.0	1950	455.0	395.0		407.0	323.0	338.0		67.10	492.0	333.0	361.0	205.0	
Mn	Mean	9870	2970	1240	0-3, 0-4	7650	6910	6930	1430	1110	0-3, 0-4, 3-4	6020	1610	1110	0-3, 0-4, 3-4	7370	5300	6330	1820	852.0	2-3, 2-4, 3-4
	SD	549.0	377	297.0		2490	337.0	1510	788.0	304.0		808.0	356.0	95.10		2140	1110	1250	851.0	218.0	
Mo	Mean	0.91	1.30	5.70	0-3, 0-4	0.65	0.52	0.19	1.53	6.74	(0-2), 0-3, 0-4, 3-4	0.90	1.75	2.37		2.93	3.50	2.99	1.57	3.47	2-3, 2-4
	SD	0.10	0.29	1.02		0.04	0.52	0.33	1.02	2.56		0.25	0.87	1.08		1.46	1.92	1.18	1.67	1.33	
Ni	Mean	33.80	22.80	12.10	4	35.20	30.50	20.80	5.67	5.65	0-2, 0-3, 0-4	82.20	64.60	46.00		280.0	300.0	260.0	66.10	17.10	2-3, 2-4, 3-4
	SD	6.49	17.40	5.94		9.70	21.60	10.30	2.41	1.72		21.40	7.53	27.30		173.0	26.50	36.10	44.10	5.77	
P	Mean	2250	3610	5970	0-4, 3-4	2450	2320	2320	4060	5080	0-3, 0-4, 3-4	1540	3150	2780	0-3, 0-4	1000	835.0	893.0	1400	1700	2-3, 2-4, 3-4
	SD	302.0	1280	1380		185.0	136.0	336.0	626.0	929.0		536.0	520.0	334.0		158.0	59.40	186.00	168.0	332.0	
Pb	Mean	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		5.19	7.80	7.86	2.33	1.19	
	SD	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		8.99	6.76	6.93	6.98	3.58	
Sr	Mean	8.85	3.44	13.20	0-4	9.29	9.02	7.13	15.80	9.01	0-3, 0-4, 3-4	8.84	21.70	25.50	0-3, 0-4	19.00	15.80	16.80	21.20	15.90	3-4
	SD	1.18	7.28	0.38		1.62	3.28	1.22	3.16	1.62		1.47	4.34	3.42		5.34	2.40	3.73	3.59	2.85	
Ti	Mean	16.40	21.50	7.00	0-4, 3-4	15.10	20.70	15.50	10.00	8.03	0-4	21.14	40.80	16.40		71.90	76.10	87.30	52.90	15.10	2-4
	SD	3.82	11.52	1.19		4.11	10.80	6.22	5.34	2.12		7.83	38.40	13.80		29.80	37.50	40.80	42.20	11.20	
U	Mean	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	
	SD	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	
V	Mean	2.55	1.87	1.23		4.17	4.22	2.13	0.99	0.66	0-2, 0-3, 0-4, 3-4	6.32	7.76	3.79		20.20	19.00	22.00	10.30	2.56	
	SD	0.47	1.34	0.82		0.66	3.04	0.32	0.22	0.45		3.03	2.38	0.23		5.44	10.13	9.55	7.14	1.62	
Zn	Mean	45.10	38.20	67.20		45.50	41.90	43.30	38.00	40.10		76.20	107.0	91.70	0-3	114.0	69.70	69.30	67.50	58.10	(2-3), 2-4
	SD	14.60	7.76	17.50		7.17	9.53	4.07	15.60	5.84		19.00	13.70	12.90		38.50	11.30	19.00	23.60	15.60	

Table 39 Metal concentrations in lupine (Neagoe et al. 2005)

	Aboveground										Belowground										
	July					October					July					October					
	0	3	4	<i>p</i> <0.05		0	1	2	3	4	<i>p</i> <0.05	0	3	4	<i>p</i> <0.05	0	1	2	3	4	<i>p</i> <0.05
Al	Mean	848.0	314.0	374.0	0-3, 0-4	4710	5610	3620	1980	n.m.	0-3	1373	1099	817.0	0-4	n.m.	n.m.	3300	1870	n.m.	2-3
	SD	260.0	185.0	86.30		1690	1020	643.0	533.0	n.m.		399	183.0	241.0		n.m.	n.m.	1690	371.0	n.m.	
As	Mean	3.41	n.d.	3.00	0, 3, 3, 4	12.00	11.10	7.20	3.73	n.m.	0, 3	4.52	5.16	n.d.	0, 4	n.m.	n.m.	5.04	3.99	n.m.	
	SD	0.87	n.d.	0.47		7.12	1.72	0.82	1.20	n.m.		0.39	1.36	n.d.		n.m.	n.m.	1.91	1.41	n.m.	
Ba	Mean	11.70	12.30	16.00		39.60	49.00	29.00	27.40	n.m.	0-3	13.40	24.30	18.00	0-3	n.m.	n.m.	21.70	26.00	n.m.	
	SD	3.40	5.83	12.40		14.00	9.93	5.50	3.53	n.m.		4.01	7.50	5.95		n.m.	n.m.	9.43	5.49	n.m.	
Ca	Mean	13600	10170	13880		17100	21800	9680	13400	n.m.	0, 2	1500.0	7380	4850	0, 3, 0, 4	n.m.	n.m.	4400	5710	n.m.	
	SD	3890	5350	4470		4950	3230	1270	4410	n.m.		967.0	1350	546.0		n.m.	n.m.	1620	1840	n.m.	
Cd	Mean	2.59	1.05	0.87	0-3, 0-4	9.37	11.10	11.70	4.36	n.m.	0-3	4.22	1.62	1.19	0-3, 0-4	n.m.	n.m.	6.98	4.43	n.m.	
	SD	0.96	0.53	0.24		1.36	2.57	1.62	1.55	n.m.		1.52	0.66	0.00		n.m.	n.m.	2.12	2.37	n.m.	
Co	Mean	19.90	6.41	6.47	0, 3, 0, 4	41.80	57.20	61.10	20.40	n.m.	0, 3, 0, 2	36.40	6.36	6.04	0, 3, 0, 4	n.m.	n.m.	5.43	1.90	n.m.	2, 3
	SD	4.19	1.98	4.33		16.00	26.10	18.40	7.31	n.m.		8.90	1.63	2.16		n.m.	n.m.	3.27	0.87	n.m.	
Cr	Mean	0.83	0.58	1.87	3-4	11.60	13.29	7.13	10.60	n.m.	0-2	21.30	18.00	8.32	0-4	n.m.	n.m.	18.70	59.90	n.m.	2-3
	SD	0.25	0.45	2.30		5.38	5.80	2.78	3.30	n.m.		19.00	5.47	4.89		n.m.	n.m.	5.33	24.00	n.m.	
Cu	Mean	13.40	12.00	9.46	0-4	31.80	37.10	33.80	20.40	n.m.	0-3	13.80	13.60	13.40		n.m.	n.m.	29.80	13.90	n.m.	2-3
	SD	0.43	3.00	1.83		2.55	7.86	0.98	3.62	n.m.		6.88	1.46	2.96		n.m.	n.m.	15.80	3.29	n.m.	
Fe	Mean	769.0	331.0	343.0	0, 3, 0, 4	4420	6090	2650	1740	n.m.	0, 3	1350	1000	798.0	0, 4	n.m.	n.m.	279.0	178.0	n.m.	2, 3
	SD	280.0	26.30	110.0		1280	3040	507.0	600.0	n.m.		238.0	36.80	273.0		n.m.	n.m.	164.0	46.80	n.m.	
K	Mean	15700	20200	32400	0-4, 3-4	6410	5600	4000	16000	n.m.	0-3	8690	35000	51300	0-3, 0-4	n.m.	n.m.	1780	19200	n.m.	2-3
	SD	3180	3350	7770		2080	2370	814.0	3980	n.m.		1480	4310.0	12500		n.m.	n.m.	85.60	6280	n.m.	
Mg	Mean	12000	6990	6400	0, 3, 0, 4	10550	8990	9320	8960	n.m.		7190	9200	5730	0, 3, 0, 4	n.m.	n.m.	3970	4170	n.m.	
	SD	3270	741.0	1350		2250	1790	1230	1930	n.m.		2920	1805	1280	3-4	n.m.	n.m.	1790	690.0	n.m.	
Mn	Mean	4930	1190	1370	0-3, 0-4	4820	5500	5260	2510	n.m.	0-3	764.0	326.0	283.0	0-4	n.m.	n.m.	1680	681.0	n.m.	2-3
	SD	2060	761.0	586.0		511.0	440.0	1870	567.0	n.m.		295.0	112.0	113.0		n.m.	n.m.	1160	280.0	n.m.	
Mo	Mean	3.10	5.15	1.71		3.07	2.66	1.36	2.66	n.m.	0, 2	1.09	2.46	3.93	0, 4	n.m.	n.m.	1.06	3.20	n.m.	
	SD	1.97	6.62	0.36		1.51	0.43	0.40	0.39	n.m.		0.27	0.28	1.47		n.m.	n.m.	0.64	1.48	n.m.	
Ni	Mean	90.43	25.20	36.60	0-3, 0-4	223.0	288.0	274.0	102.0	n.m.	0-3	126.0	39.70	23.10	0-3, 0-4	n.m.	n.m.	319.0	109.0	n.m.	2-3
	SD	18.40	14.00	29.40		30.00	77.50	69.40	27.20	n.m.		44.10	7.92	7.17		n.m.	n.m.	139.0	26.80	n.m.	
P	Mean	2160	2210	2710		3110	3240	2080	2960	n.m.	0, 2	1050	2590	1640	0, 3, 3, 4	n.m.	n.m.	814.0	1350	n.m.	2, 3
	SD	146.0	572.0	423.0		264.0	803.0	190.0	430.0	n.m.		124.0	341.0	172.0		n.m.	n.m.	152.0	429.0	n.m.	
Pb	Mean	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.m.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.m.	n.m.	n.d.	n.d.	n.m.	
	SD	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.m.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.m.	n.m.	n.d.	n.d.	n.m.	
Sr	Mean	30.30	48.80	5.82	0-4	37.60	49.90	27.40	65.50	n.m.	0-3	10.40	58.10	39.60	0-3, 0-4	n.m.	n.m.	17.30	41.90	n.m.	2-3
	SD	5.99	24.10	2.36		9.08	11.13	3.37	17.70	n.m.		4.72	12.00	5.67	3, 4	n.m.	n.m.	5.60	11.30	n.m.	
Ti	Mean	19.10	8.26	9.90	0, 3, 0, 4	54.40	80.20	24.90	31.40	n.m.	0, 2	30.10	32.80	27.50		n.m.	n.m.	44.40	44.20	n.m.	
	SD	7.14	3.10	3.11		16.10	45.70	4.64	17.50	n.m.		7.54	5.55	6.60		n.m.	n.m.	27.50	13.20	n.m.	
U	Mean	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.m.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.m.	n.m.	n.d.	n.d.	n.m.	
	SD	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.m.		n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.m.	n.m.	n.d.	n.d.	n.m.	
V	Mean	1.54	0.84	0.63	0, 3, 0, 4	15.40	15.00	12.00	4.63	n.m.	0, 3	2.78	1.96	2.20		n.m.	n.m.	7.14	4.21	n.m.	
	SD	0.46	0.00	0.00		9.09	4.30	1.81	1.33	n.m.		0.79	0.43	0.34		n.m.	n.m.	3.04	0.77	n.m.	
Zn	Mean	76.30	71.10	68.10		136.0	156.0	149.0	121.0	n.m.		45.10	67.20	41.20		n.m.	n.m.	76.00	58.90	n.m.	
	SD	4.30	22.80	14.60		15.40	21.60	21.60	15.20	n.m.		12.20	6.05	6.23		n.m.	n.m.	29.10	13.70	n.m.	

Table 40 Oxidative stress variables in lupine (a) and rye (b). The units are in [$\mu\text{g} \times \text{g}^{-1}$] biomass d.w. aboveground, [$\text{mg} \times \text{g}^{-1}$] d.w. total leaf chlorophyll, [Units $\times \text{g}^{-1}$ protein] SOD, [$\mu\text{units} \times \text{g}^{-1}$ protein] POD (Neagoe et al.2005).

a)		Lupine, July, Aboveground			Mann–Whitney $p < 0.05$
		0	3	4	
Protein	Mean	3540	4540	6190	0–3, 0–4, 3–4
	SD	754.0	533.0	1190	
SOD	Mean	899.0	713.0	539.0	0–3, 0–4, 3–4
	SD	134.0	79.90	91.00	
POD	Mean	1.91	1.79	1.00	0–4, 3–4
	SD	0.49	0.89	0.20	
Chl total	Mean	1.78	3.16	3.81	0–3, 0–4
	SD	1.03	0.65	2.32	

b)		Rye, July, Aboveground			Mann–Whitney $p < 0.05$
		0	3	4	
Protein	Mean	1340	5240	6060	0–3, 0–4
	SD	60.0	213.0	701.0	
SOD	Mean	599.0	153.0	133.0	0–3, 0–4
	SD	27.0	6.0	15.0	
POD	Mean	100	6.0	69.0	0–3, 0–4, 3–4
	SD	8.90	0.90	0.31	
Chl total	Mean	1.30	7.60	8.00	0–3, 0–4, 3–4
	SD	0.07	0.66	1.44	

Gray areas show a decrease from control, to top soil and to compost and bold/underline values increase.

Conclusions

The most effective amendment (in terms of increasing biomass production) for the period studied was compost, followed by the addition of top soil and urea. The mechanisms underlying this effect were the changes in soil variables that resulted in lower metal bioavailability and increased nutrient availability. Following these conclusions, further studies were needed to investigate how nitrogen depletion can best be compensated in the long term. Such studies subsequently involved, in addition to nitrogen application, inoculation with microorganisms, thus coupling plant performance (e.g., phytoremediation) with bacterial and fungal remediation (Neagoe et al. 2004). In describing the fluxes of elements between different compartments, it is necessary to consider both biological and geochemical factors, similar to the conceptual model found in Ebenå (2003). The metals present in the soil surface at the site did not appear to be increasingly mobilized to any greater degree by the introduction of vegetation, nor fertilizers or other amendments necessary to increase plant performance. Plant effects are considered to be minor, and the integrated effects of the applied amendments may actually have reduced the available pool for phytotoxic elements. It was thus concluded that where there are severe risks of erosion or loss of material from the area, means of improving the vegetation cover would be recommended. The choice of amendment or fertilizer is more a matter of cost. Therefore, if there is a severe risk of erosion in the area, it can be prevented by introducing plants that stabilize the soil surface without risking an increase in metal flows in the area.

B4.2.4 Coupled pot-lysimeter experiment

A system *A. capillaris* - compost - PGPB selected from the rhizosphere of the tailing dam native plants can be an option for the phytostabilisation of tailing dams

This research was published by *Nicoara et al. 2014 in Environmental Science Pollution Research, 21:6905–6920*, <https://doi.org/10.11356-013-2489-92>, as an article titled “Coupled pot and lysimeter experiments assessing plant performance in microbially assisted phytoremediation”.

The research presented in this section took place at the pot scale, an experiment in which we evaluated the effect of PGPB⁵ on the development of five plant species grown in a polluted substrate sampled from a mine tailing dam. The experiment was repeated at lysimeter scale with the species showing the best development at pot scale, and the significant total biomass increase as a result of inoculation was confirmed. Since the substrate of a tailing dam is very poor in organic matter, it usually has a very low pH and high concentrations of toxic heavy metals, installing in a natural way of a vegetative is very difficult, sometimes impossible. For this reason, to prevent the entry of metals into the food chain, or to avoid the emergence and development of invasive species, it is desirable to apply a phytostabilization technique of the polluted sites, with a dense culture that is also crucial for limiting wind erosion. In this context, **the objective of our research** was to investigate the hypotheses that the PGPB inoculum increases the biomass of plants grown on tailing material amended with compost and decreases the concentration of toxic metals in the biomass and leachate. A simplified concept model for testing this hypothesis is presented in figure 36.

Figure 36 General concept model for investigating the effect of bacterial inoculum isolated from tailing material on plant development. Arrows indicate causal effects.

Experimental conditions, design and measured variables

The mining substrate used for these experiments was sampled from Valea Mică tailings dam located near Zlatna, Romanian, and known for their polymetallic Cu, Pb and Zn pollution. Geographical coordinates of the study area and mine tailings substrate are 46°09'32"N23°13'16"E. More details about the site can be found in the previous section and in the related article, as well as in a review of the situation of the tailing dams in Romania, including information about the Valea Mică tailing dam. In order to carry out these experiments, preliminary activities were necessary, such as: selection of a site-specific microbial consortium, mine tailing substrate characterization and a germination test, as well as

⁵ PGPB - plant growth promoting bacteria

the establishment of experimental design. These activities are briefly described in the following paragraphs.

Selection of site-specific microbial consortium

Bacteria were isolated from the rhizosphere soil of native *Agrostis capillaris* growing on the mine tailing and a composite soil sample from the same area. Soil suspensions were realised and plated on Standard I and selective Starch-Casein Agar and incubated at 28 °C for two weeks, in order to isolate as slow as fast-growing bacteria. Colonies of different morphologies were considered to be microscopically analysed, purified and further characterised for physiological traits of plants growth promotion, metal(s) resistance and taxonomical affiliation. The universal primers fD1 Forward (5'-AGAGTTTGATCCTGGC TCAG-3') and rP2 Reverse (5'-ACGGCTACCTTGTTAC GACTT-3') were used for the amplification of the 16S rDNA gene and sequencing, as performed by GATC (Konstanz, Germany). To prepare the inoculum for pot and lysimeter experiments, each strain was individually cultured in liquid Standard I medium and shaken at 150 rpm at 28 °C before enumeration of the colonies number (CFU/ml) via direct plate counts method. In case of filamentous bacteria, spore was harvested from 5-day-old Starch Casein agar plates and quantified with a Thoma counting chamber. Each isolate was then diluted in 0.9 % NaCl to realise a solution containing 10⁹ CFU/pot.

Mine tailing substrate and germination tests

The substrate for experiments was collected from 20 sampling points to represent the heterogeneity of the tailing dam surface. The sampled substrate was dried at room temperature and mixed several times with a concrete mixer. This substrate was a sandy silt mixture with fine grain size, a WHC⁶ of about 32 % and pH (H₂O) of around 4 (see tables B1.4.8.1 a and b). We used commercially available natural compost consisting in a mixture of 50 % white peat and 50 % black peat (*Sphagnum* sp.), a form of limestone composed of the mineral calcite-chalk 2 kg m⁻³, and 1 kg/m³ NPK (14-17-21) fertiliser (GB Universal potting soil, type of product: growing media, producer: Bioland Tözegfeldolgozó Kft.).

A germination test was performed with unamended inoculated and not inoculated tailing substrate using commercially available seeds of *Euphorbia pythiusa*, *Helianthus annuus*, *Verbascum thapsus*, *Deschampsia flexuosa*, *Agrostis capillaris* and *Festuca rubra*. No seeds germinated in any experimental treatment. We repeated the germination test with tailing substrate amended with compost (30 % compost (w:w)). All species excepting *E. pythiusa* had 100 % germination rate in this case. In table 41a, a comparison of variable between pure mine tailing substrate and mixed with compost can be seen. Toxic element concentrations in the compost were much lower than those in the tailing and caused a dilution of toxic elements (table 41b).

Experimental design at pot and lysimeter scales

A *pot experiment* was performed using 1 litter polyethylene pots with 12 cm diameter and a surface of 113 cm². We have established two experimental treatments: amended with bacterial inoculum (coded with B), and negative control (unamended, coded with NB), each with 5 pots per treatment. Inoculation was performed by mixing substrate with 20 ml of bacterial

⁶ WCH - water holding capacity

suspension at time of plant seeding into the respective substrate. We sowed with 0.045 g *A. capillaris* var *metallica* commercially available seeds/pot, which correspond to 20 kg ha⁻¹ as the producer Rieger-Hofmann, Germany recommended. Seeds of the other species were provided by Plant World Seeds (St. Marychurch Road, Newton Abbot, Devon, TQ12 4SE, U.K., <http://www.plant-world-seeds.com/>) and have been sowed as described by Wernitznig et al. (2013) reporting a similar pot experiment on different contaminated substrates. Pots were kept in a greenhouse for 3 months, at temperatures ranging from 25 to 35 °C during the day and 15 to 25 °C during the night. We arranged them in a randomised pattern and randomly rearranged every 2 days in order to minimise the influence of climatic variation. All pots were watered daily using distilled water, to maximum WHC.

The *lysimeters* were part of an experimental system comprised of 35 lysimeters in an aboveground wooden box. More details about the construction of the whole system can be find in figure 37. Each individual lysimeter consisted of a 30 cm wide PVC tube that was 50 cm deep. The two experimental treatments which have been part of a larger experiment with 9 experimental treatments were the same as for the pot experiment, with 5 lysimeters per treatment. The first 20 cm from the top were filled with the mixture of tailing substrate and 30 % (w:w) compost, while the last 30 cm were filled with pure tailing substrate. Inoculum was added in the top 20 cm in the same mass proportion as in the pot experiment. Lysimeters were exposed to the more appropriate field conditions and were watered daily using distilled water when there has been no hydrological event (rain or snow). Each lysimeter was sowed with *A. capillaris* seed funnels after one heavy rain, sampled using a polyethylene syringe.

Figure 37 Experimental design of the lysimeter system (adapted after Nicoară et al. 2014).

In both pot and lysimeter experiments the same variables have been measured. *Amended mine tailing substrate* was sampled at the end of the two experiments (with distroing in the case of pots, and without destroying in the case of lysimeters, where it was sampled from the first 15 cm of each lysimeter) and was analysed with regard to pH, EC, LOI, mineral-N concentrations (N-NH₄⁺, N-NO₃⁻ and N-NO₂⁻) and available phosphorus (PPO₄³⁻), soil respiration, heavy metals content in form of pseudo total (aqua regia) or in sequential extractions, respectively, bioavailable fractions (F1 and F2).

Plants were harvested after 3 months in pots and 20 months in lysimeters and separated into underground and aboveground biomass, and after washing with tap water and rinsing several times with distilled water, ultrapure water were lyophilised and weighed to determine dry weight (dw). Lyophilised plant material was ground in a cooling stainless steel mill and then stored at minus 45°C until further processing. These parameters were chlorophyll and

carotenoids, total proteins, lipid peroxidation, and heavy metals. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) imaging and energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis were carried out using an environmental SEM (ESEM, QUANTA 200, FEI), and a field emission gun SEM (Schottky thermal field emitter) under high vacuum conditions (data not shown in this section). *Leachate* was filtered using 0.45 µm Whatman cellulose nitrate membrane filter and preserved with 1 % v:v ultrapure nitric acid, from which the variables were subsequently measured: pH, EC, concentrations of N-NH₄⁺, N-NO₃⁻ and N-NO₂⁻, PPO₄³⁻, and heavy metals content.

Table 41a Physicochemical parameters of pure mine tailing substrate and mixed with 30 % compost; **b** Toxic element concentrations in the tailing substrate and compost (n=5) (Nicoară et al. 2014).

a	Variable	pH	EC	LOI	N-NH ₄ ⁻	N-NO ₃ ⁻	N-NO ₂ ⁻	P-PO ₄ ³⁻
	Unit	H ₂ O	[mS/c m]	[%]	[µg g ⁻¹ d.w.]			
Tailing substrate	Average	4.61	0.603	0.40	11.59	2.714	0.156	3.747
	SD	1.41	0.124	5.3	0.12	8.913	3.645	1.283
Substrate+ 30%compost	Average	6.305	1.793	7.186	8.694	59.66	0.017	4.298
	SD	0.042	0.173	1.296	1.100	11.56	0.003	0.738
b	Variable	As	Cr	Cu	Mn	Ni	Pb	Zn
	Unit	[µg g ⁻¹ d.w.]						
Tailing substrate	Average	436.3	913.8	2747	948.5	64.65	1200	10064
	SD	72.78	132.6	963.1	355.7	17.47	36.77	1396
Compost	Composi te	20.92	27.99	29.87	367.3	18.21	40.1	111.5
Substrate + 30% compost	Average	362.5	536.8	1904	715.0	22.41	782.5	6924
	SD	5.744	31.64	53.33	22.53	3.285	30.42	475.4

Selected findings

PGPB adapted to metal stress

PGPB adapted to metal stress Out of 25 isolated strains, 21 were selected for being tested on metal(s) resistance and plant growth promotion features, leading to a bigger fraction of Gram-positive, with just 29 % of the isolates being Gram-negative. Most strains did show plant growth promotion capacities, and the ten best performing strains with overlapping PGP properties were selected for the site-specific consortium (table 42): *Rhodococcus erythropolis* Uz1005, *Brevibacterium frigoritolerans* Uz1008, *Bacillus atrophaeus* Uz1106, *Streptomyces olivochromogenes* Uz1010, *Streptomyces aureus* Uz1109, *Burkholderia phytofirmans* Uz1014, *Burkholderia fungorum* Uz1101, *Arthrobacter phenantrenivorans* Uz1801, *Arthrobacter cupressi* Uz1102, *Tetrathiobactersp.* Uz1110. The strains were able to grow on minimal medium containing soil extract, well resembling survival in the environment on the multi-metal impacted soil. All isolates chosen for the consortium showed siderophore and phytohormones production, as well as nitrogen fixation (by six of the strains) and phosphate solubilisation (by seven of the strains).

Soil respiration

Soil respiration statistically increased as a result of inoculation in all experimental treatments (figure 38)

Metals in mobile soil fractions and in leachate

A general pattern of elements concentration decrease occurred, with many significant

differences. For instance, following inoculation, As in the leachate of pot experiment with *A. capillaris* decreased by three quarters, Ni by almost two thirds, while Cu and Mn were down by half. Pb could not be detected in leachate of the inoculated pots. Zn also showed a decrease in average concentration, but this was not statistically significant. As, Cu, Ni and Zn concentrations decreased in the leachate from *F. rubra* pots. In the lysimeter experiment, metals in leachate also showed a decrease in concentration as a result of inoculation but manifested great heterogeneity, leading to fewer statistically significant differences (Mn and Zn).

Table 42 Physiological tests for identification of PGPB to create a site-specific consortium (Nicoară et al. 2014).

Strain	Taxonomy	Accession number	PVK	AzM	CAS	IAA	MMSE
UZ1110	<i>Tetrathibacter</i> sp. Uz1110	JX133205	+	+	+	+	+
UZ1109	<i>Streptomyces aureus</i> Uz1109	JX133213	+	-	+	+	+
UZ 1807	<i>Agromyces bauzanensis</i> Uz1807	KC618494	-	-	+	-	-
UZ 1806	<i>Bacillus pumilus</i> Uz1806	KC618493	+	+	+	-	-
UZ 1805	<i>Arthrobacter</i> sp. Uz1008	KC618491	-	+	+	-	-
UZ 1804	<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. Uz1804	KC618492	-	-	+	-	+
UZ 1802	<i>Arthrobacter</i> sp. Uz1802	KC618490	-	-	-	-	+
UZ 1801	<i>Arthrobacter phenantrenivorans</i> Uz1801	JX133209	-	-	+	+	+
UZ 1106	<i>Bacillus atrophaeus</i> Uz1106	JX133210	-	+	+	+	+
UZ 1104	<i>Microbacterium resistens</i> Uz1104	KC618489	+	-	+	-	-
UZ 1103	<i>Bacillus simplex</i> Uz1103	KC618488	-	+	+	-	+
UZ 1102	<i>Arthrobacter cupressi</i> Uz1102	JX133208	+	+	+	+	+
UZ 1101	<i>Burkholderia fungorum</i> Uz1101	JX133206	+	-	+	+	+
UZ 1014	<i>Burkholderia phytofirmans</i> Uz1014	JX133207	+	-	+	+	+
UZ 1013	<i>Bacillus</i> sp. Uz1013	KC618487	-	-	+	+	-
UZ 1010	<i>Streptomyces olivochromogenes</i> Uz1010	JX133212	+	+	+	+	+
UZ 1008	<i>Brevibacterium frigoritolerans</i> Uz1008	JX133211	-	+	+	+	+
UZ 1007	<i>Psychrobacillus psychrodurans</i> Uz1007	KC618486	-	+	+	-	-
UZ 1006	<i>Paenibacillus</i> sp. Uz1006	KC618485	+	-	+	-	-
UZ 1005	<i>Rhodococcus erythropolis</i> Uz1005	JX133204	+	+	+	+	+
UZ 1002	<i>Ochrobactrum intermedium</i> Uz1002	KC618484	+	+	-	+	+

- no growth or halo formation, + growth or halo formation, bold strains chosen for the consortium, PVK phosphate solubilisation, AzM nitrogen fixation, CAS siderophore production, IAA indole acetic acid production, MMSE minimal medium with soil extract.

Figure 38 The ratio between soil respiration in inoculated (B) and not inoculated (NB) treatments at pot (treatment 1-5 on the x axis) and lysimeter (treatment 6 on the x axis) scale.

The number above each treatment the average of the respiration rate in each inoculated treatment ($\text{mg CO}_2 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ d.w. in 2 h}$). 1 *Helianthus annuus*, 2 *Verbascum thapsus*, 3 *Deschampsia flexuosa*, 4 *Agrostis capillaris* at pot scale, 5 *Festuca rubra*, 6 *A. capillaris* at lysimeter scale. * Indicates significant increase as a result of inoculation (Mann-Whitney U test) (Nicoară et al. 2014).

Figure 39 presents results concerning leachate and easily available substrate fractions from pots and lysimeters.

Figure 39 Patterns of element distribution in leachate and in mobile soil fractions (F1+F2). **Above:** the ratio between element concentration in leachate from inoculated (B) and not inoculated (NB) treatments at pot (treatments 1-5 in the legend) and lysimeter (treatment 6 in the legend) scale. **Below:** the ratio between the mobile fractions at the end of the experiment and at the start of the experiment. Cr concentrations in the mobile fractions at lysimeter scale were detectable at the start of the experiment, and below the detection limit at the end of the experiment (ratio assumed to be zero on the graph). 1 *Helianthus annuus*, 2 *Verbascum thapsus*, 3 *Deschampsia flexuosa*, 4 *A. capillaris* at pot scale, 5 *Festuca rubra*, 6 *A. capillaris* at lysimeter scale, * indicates significant change as a result of inoculation (above) and between the end and the start of the experiment (below; Mann-Whitney U test) (Nicoară et al. 2014).

The inoculation did not have a statistically significant effect on the concentration of toxic elements in easily available fractions from the amended mining substrate. However, there was a statistically significant decrease of concentrations at the end of the experiments both for pots (Cu, Ni, Pb, Zn, inoculated and not inoculated) and for lysimeters (As, Cu, Ni, Pb, Zn, inoculated and not inoculated). The patterns of variation of root and total biomass are presented in figure 40. The biomass of *Helianthus annuus*, *Verbascum thapsus* and *Deschampsia flexuosa* was very small, with no significant changes as a result of inoculation. The largest biomass in

pot experiments was that of *A. capillaris*, significantly larger than that *F. rubra* in the inoculated and not inoculated treatments. For both species with large biomass production the inoculation significantly increased the roots biomass. At the lysimeter scale also the total biomass of *A. capillaris* significantly increased in the inoculated treatment.

Figure 40 The ratio between average elements concentrations (above graph) and average total amounts of elements (stocks, below graph) in the roots and aboveground parts of *A. capillaris* and *F. rubra* (in inoculated (B) and not inoculated (NB) treatments at pot and lysimeter scale). R (Ab)-A-pot(lys) roots or aboveground parts of *A. capillaris* at pot scale or lysimeter scale, R(Ab)-F-pot roots or aboveground parts of *F. rubra* at pot scale. * Indicates significant change as a result of inoculation (Mann-Whitney U test) (Nicoară et al. 2014).

Elements in plants

These variables and the biochemical ones have been measured only for *A. capillaris* and *F. rubra* because, for the other species, the available biomass was too small. The main patterns are in figure 41 As, Cr and Cu concentrations were significantly lower in the roots of *A. capillaris* grown in the inoculated pots, while Mn and Zn were significantly lower in the shoots of plants grown in inoculated lysimeters. Phosphorus concentrations were significantly larger in the roots of inoculated plants at lysimeter scale (average \pm SD=683.4 μ g/g \pm 27.26 compared to 605.4 μ g/g \pm 54.51). Cu, Ni and Zn concentrations in the root of *F. rubra* significantly decreased in inoculated treatments. Inoculation led to a statistically significant increase of Mn, Pb, and Zn stocks in the roots of *A. capillaris* at pot scale, and to a significant decrease of Cu stocks in the roots of *F. rubra*. At the lysimeter scale, there were no significant differences between stocks of elements in inoculated and not inoculated treatments

Biochemical variables in plants. Chlorophyll a, b and carotenoids had significantly smaller concentrations in *A. capillaris* and *F. rubra* at pot scale as a result of inoculation (table 43). No significant changes occurred at lysimeter scale between inoculated and not inoculated treatments.

Figure 41 The ratio between average elements concentrations (above graph) and average total amounts of elements (stocks, below graph) in the roots and aboveground parts of *A. capillaris* and *F. rubra* [in inoculated (B) and not inoculated (NB) treatments at pot and lysimeter scale]. R(Ab)-Apot(lys) roots or aboveground parts of *Agrostis capillaris* at pot scale or lysimeter scale, R(Ab)-Fpot roots or aboveground parts of *F. rubra* at pot scale. * indicates significant change due to inoculation (Mann-Whitney U test) (Nicoară et al. 2014).

Table 43 The effect of inoculation on biochemical variables in plant parts at pot and lysimeter scales (Nicoară et al. 2014).

		<i>Agrostis capillaries</i>				<i>Festuca rubra</i>	
		Pot		Lysimeter		Pot	
		NB	B	NB	B	NB	B
LP (μM MDA/g dw)	Average	0.27	0.29	0.16 ^a	0.17 ^a	0.27	0.27
	SD	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.05	0.03	0.03
LP (μM MDA/g dw)	Average	0.20	0.21	0.26	0.32 ^a	0.18	0.19
	SD	0.02	0.02	0.10	0.06	0.01	0.02
Chl a (mg/g dw)	Average	9.98	8.29*	2.78 ^a	2.96 ^a	10.75	8.06*
	SD	0.51	0.76	0.67	0.74	1.36	1.93
Chl b (mg/g dw)	Average	4.09	3.41*	1.02 ^a	1.18 ^a	4.28	3.14*
	SD	0.26	0.27	0.22	0.19	0.66	0.79
Carotenoids (mg/g dw)	Average	0.46	0.39*	0.13 ^a	0.14 ^a	0.48	0.36*
	SD	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.09
Protein (mg/g dw)	Average	18.8	16.40	18.87	15.74	NA	NA
	SD	5.56	5.26	8.59	6.48		
Protein (mg/g dw)	Average	42.10	34.31	38.96	40.14	NA	NA
	SD	4.12	12.85	10.75	15.42		

Grey cells point out significantly smaller values as a result of inoculation, ^a indicates significant differences between lysimeter and pot, * indicates statistically significant differences between not inoculated and inoculated treatments, NB not inoculated, B inoculated, LP lipids peroxidation, NA not available

Comparison of A. capillaris at pot and lysimeter scales

The respiration rate in the lysimeter experiment was significantly larger than in the pot experiment with *A. capillaris* both in non-inoculated and inoculated treatments (data can be found in supplementary materials of the original article). Compared to pots the leachate from lysimeters had significantly larger concentrations of As, Mn, and Ni, and significantly smaller concentrations of Zn. All elements in lysimeters had significantly smaller concentrations in the available fractions at the end of the experiment than those in pots. Cu and Zn concentrations in roots of *A. capillaris* were significantly smaller at the lysimeter scale than at pot scale in both not inoculated and inoculated treatments. Pb concentrations were significantly smaller in roots in lysimeters only in the inoculated treatment. Cu and Zn concentrations were smaller in aboveground parts of *A. capillaris* in lysimeters only in the inoculated treatment. Cr concentrations in roots and Mn in aboveground parts significantly increased from pot to lysimeter scale. Chlorophyll a, b, carotenoids, and lipids peroxidation (LP) were significantly smaller in lysimeter *A. capillaris* plants than in the younger pot plants.

Summary of discussions about own data PGPB adapted to metal stress

Our inoculum included genera *Bacillus*, *Streptomyces*, *Pseudomonas*, *Burkholderia*, *Agrobacterium* *Tetrathioabacter*, *Rhodococcus*, *Arthrobacter* and *Brevibacterium*. We also isolated a strain of *B. fungorum* Uz1101 to be part of the consortium. Due to the abilities as PGPB that we found in our investigation, we believe that this strain should be reconsidered in terms of application for bioaugmentation, for many strains belonging to the *Burkholderia cepacia* complex.

Substrate respiration

The total metabolic activity of the microbial community strongly increased by inoculation, as proven by soil respiration rate (with up to 77 % in the case of *A. capillaris* in lysimeters). This may be due to the larger resistance of the inoculated strains to toxic elements compared to what can be expected from the bacteria already existing in the compost added to tailing material. The larger respiration rate at lysimeter scale in both inoculated and not inoculated treatments was in phase with a better development of the rhizosphere system as a result of plant age (3 months in pots, 20 months in lysimeters).

Effect on plant biomass

Effect on phosphorus and toxic elements uptake. In our results at lysimeter scale (the higher root phosphorus concentrations found in bacterial inoculated lysimeter plants, coupled with the statistically significant increases in root biomass) phosphorous solubilisation has been found to enhance plant biomass, with no significant effect on metal uptake. We detected significantly lower metal concentrations by inoculation, especially in plant roots, also the inoculation with a consortium of bacteria gave better results than with single strains. We can state that the general tendency to decrease the accumulation of toxic elements, reinforced by some statistically significant results, shows the potential of the presented plant-substrate bacterial consortium to reduce phytotoxicity. Our PGPB did not result in an increase in the concentrations of toxic elements in aboveground biomass, so our results support the use of *A. capillaris* for phytostabilization rather than phytoextraction. Our PGPB did not result in an increase in the concentrations of toxic elements in aboveground biomass, so our results support the use of *A. capillaris* for phytostabilization rather than phytoextraction, a finding that was not surprising as *A. capillaris* is one of the most popular grasses for phytoremediation

experiments. Our strains have been selected for phosphate solubilisation, growth on a nitrogen-free medium, siderophore production, indole acetic acid production, and resistance to co-occurring and bioavailable metals in the soil. Although *A. capillaris* and *F. rubra* clearly have been developed better as a result of inoculation, it was difficult to identify all effective causes of this process based on our data. There was a proven decrease in several toxic element concentrations in roots of both species at age 3 months, a decrease of some toxic elements in aboveground parts of *A. capillaris* at 20 months age, and an increase in P concentrations in *A. capillaris* roots at the age 20 months. Cu and Zn were identified only at the surface on *A. capillaris* roots grown in inoculated substrate. The same Cu and Zn (together with Ni) showed significantly smaller concentrations in roots in inoculated material at pot scale. Copper also had significantly smaller concentrations in the leachate of all plant species treatments at pot scale, while Zn in two cases only. So, there are indications that the beneficial effect of inoculation is due to the immobilisation of at least Cu and Zn at the root surface and due to the mobilisation of phosphorus.

Effect on stress variables

Besides the increase in plant biomass, coupled with a decrease in toxic element bioaccumulation, another expected result of bacterial inoculation was an improvement in stress parameters, such as an increase in protein and pigment concentrations and a decrease in oxidative stress indicators. However, we found a decrease of pigments concentration as a result of inoculation. Although plant biomass improved and the bioaccumulation of heavy metals was reduced, this was not correlate with physiological stress variables (protein, pigments, and LP). While the plant biomass concentrations of As, Cr and Mn were below the average for grasses, Cu, Ni, Pb and Zn greatly exceeded those values. Thus, in aboveground biomass, Cu was around three times higher than average, Ni up to 20 times, Pb up to five times and Zn up to ten times. We observed a clustered distribution of elements by plant age and experimental scale. Knowing and understanding the causes of the existence of such patterns is double: from basic science perspective (the dynamic of plant development under stress conditions) and from applied science perspective (the limits of using plant chemical and biochemical variables resulted from one sampling moment in monitoring the effect of pollution and restoration success).

Conclusions

The inoculation with PGPB selected from the rhizosphere of plants grown on tailing dams induced a larger respiration rate of tailing material amended with compost in all experimental treatments, irrespective of the development of plants. In the case of *A. capillaris* and *F. rubra*, it also significantly increased the root biomass in pot scale experiment. However, a statistically significant decrease of Cu and Zn concentration in the roots of *A. capillaris* and *F. rubra* occurred at pot scale (also of other elements), as well as of their concentration in leachate, suggesting that, in one way or another, the inoculation with PGPB reduced the mobility of metals from the tailing material amended with compost. Another important finding is the increase of phosphorus in roots of *A. capillaris* at the lysimeter scale following inoculation, consistent with the selection of bacteria for inoculum based on their P solubilization capacity. Therefore, the inoculation with PGPB led to a better plant development and diminished metals percolation for two of five tested plant species at pot scale, which was confirmed for *A. capillaris* also at the lysimeter scale. A system *A. capillaris*-compost-PGPB selected from the tailing dam native plants can be an option for the phytostabilisation of tailing dams.

B4.2.5 Coupled pot-lysimeter-field plot experiments

Effects of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi on *Agrostis capillaris* grown on amended mine tailing substrate at pot, lysimeter, and field plot scales

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The methodological novelty present in this study consisted of coupling in a single research program experiments carried out at three scales: pot, lysimeter and field plot, with different ages of the plants at the sampling time (six subsets of samples in all). In our research program, we introduced work consecutively at three experimental scales, on the one hand, to develop applied research regarding the methods of remediation of contaminated areas, and on the other hand to obtain new information on the physiological and ecological mechanisms in supporting the resistance of plant communities to stress conditions due to toxic elements. Phytostabilization is the primary technique to be applied when one deals with mine tailings.

Experimental conditions, design and measured variables

All three experiments performed at different spatial scales were performed using a mine substrate from a tailing dam located in the Ampoi catchment from the South Apuseni Mountains (maximum altitude of 1,300 m) near Zlatna region (geographic coordinates 46°09'32"N and 23°13'16"E), Romania (see figure 42).

Figure 42 Mining area Zlatna (Mica Valley) (by Neagoe et al. 2010).

The tailing dam appeared through dumping the refuse coming from the primary flotation of ores from polymetallic minerals (Cu, Pb, and Zn) and metalloids such as As. The tailing substrate has a fine grain size (sand-silt mixture) having a field capacity of 32 vol.% water content (pF 1.8) and presenting large areas covered by cemented layers. It has a large

heterogeneity on its surface in the distribution of metals (especially Cu, Pb, and Zn) and metalloids such as As, pH (H₂O), humidity (H), an EC values, as well as the available nutrient content (nitrogen and phosphorus) (table 44).

Table 44 General *physico*-chemical characteristics of mine tailing substrate (Neagoe et al. 2014).

Variable (n=50)	pH (H ₂ O)	EC (μ S/cm)	H (%)	N-NH ₄ ⁺ (μ g/g d.w.)	N-NO ₃ ⁻ (μ g/g d.w.)	N-NO ₂ ⁻ (μ g/g d.w.)	P-PO ₄ ³⁻ (μ g/g d.w.)	As (μ g/g d.w.)	Cu (μ g/g d.w.)	Pb (μ g/g d.w.)	Zn (μ g/g d.w.)
Min	2.43	63	4.17	2.149	0.716	0.05	1.374	59.84	141.2	150.4	368.5
Max	7.82	1,947	20.4	36.13	12.78	0.365	15.68	429.4	4,300	2,879	2,680

The properties of the mine tailing substrate affected the establishment of vegetation cover. Only some plant species such as *Rumex acetosella*, *Rubus caesius*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Betula pendula*, and *Agrostis capillaris* were extremely rare in small patches on the surface of the tailing dam (Onete et al. unpublished data). Species with potential use in remediation in our field conditions were found to be (a) species that prefer conditions on the dam: *R. acetosella* and *Polygonum aviculare* and (b) species that tolerate natural dam conditions but prefer uncontaminated areas: *R. caesius*, *C. monogyna*, *B. pendula* and *A. capillaris*. We wanted to use seeds from the field, but it was proven after a germination test in the laboratory, that these seeds harvested from the extremely polluted site, were not viable. Thus, we ran a second germination test using only commercial seeds of *A. capillaris*, grown in mining substrate. Consequently, for the phytostabilization method that we managed to develop by carrying out these three experiments, we selected the *A. capillaris* species as the plant for reasons of abundance in the investigated site, but also because it is an acidophilic species and highly adaptable to stress due to excess heavy metals, were cam the name var. *metallica*. In all three experiments, an amount of *A. capillaris* seeds of 20 kg ha⁻¹ was used, double the amount recommended by the supplier (Rieger-Hofmann GmbH, Germany), due to the hostile nature of the mining substrate. To improve the quality of mine tailing, substrate top soil (20 % (w/w) wet weight in field and dry weight basis in lab and lysimeter experiments) was applied. The source of the topsoil was a village-Ålmaşu Mare located in the Zlatna area (geographical coordinates 46°06'33"N and 23°07'11"E) which, due to topographic conditions, has not been affected by heavy metal pollution, neither from mining effluents nor from atmospheric deposition. It was a reddish-brown soil very rich in clay (table 45). To reduce the solubilization of metals in the polluted tailing dam substrate, a natural calcium carbonate was used to neutralize the acidity of the tailing substrate. The amount used was 5% (w/w), based on dry weight determined after some laboratory tests (details in the article). Natural zeolite (characterization shown in was used as potential sorbent of excess free cations (i.e., Cu, Zn, and Pb).

Table 45 *Physico*-chemical characteristics of top soil (Neagoe et al. 2014).

Variable (n=50)	pH (H ₂ O)	EC (μ S/cm)	H (%)	LOI (%)	N-NH ₄ ⁺ (μ g/g d.w.)	N-NO ₃ ⁻ (μ g/g d.w.)	N-NO ₂ ⁻ (μ g/g d.w.)	P-PO ₄ ³⁻ (μ g/g d.w.)	As (μ g/g d.w.)	Cu (μ g/g d.w.)	Pb (μ g/g d.w.)	Zn (μ g/g d.w.)
Mean	7.083	136.0	8.278	4.172	35.73	9.908	0.156	52.95	13.12	22.19	28.87	55.06
SD	0.026	9.274	0.243	0.778	6.905	3.823	0.097	1.993	0.508	1.233	6.510	7.805

The application rate (5 % (w/w)) of natural zeolite was determined on the previous basis studies in similar places in the literature. Mine tailings substrate testing by Turnau (unpublished data) has shown that it does not contain any mycorrhizal fungi. The mycorrhizal inoculum used was a commercially available mixture of *Glomus intraradices*, *Glomus etunicatum* and *Glomus claroideum* (producer INOQ GmbH, Germany), with 210 spores per square centimeter substrate, in 2 mm expanded volcanic clay particles. Regarding the amount of inoculum, a percentage of 10 (w/w) in soil is recommended. Instead of this, we used with our tailing material experimental treatments with 1 and 7 % (w/w) in order to check if there is a substantial improvement in plant development as a result of increase of any quantity of inoculum, justifying the increased costs of the remediation method.

Experimental design of pots

The mining substrate used in the experiment was sampled from 20 stations organized on two transects on the surface of the dam to cover the high heterogeneity. The samples were dried and mixed several times using a concrete mixer to ensure homogeneity and limit the variation of the experimental treatments. Three experimental treatments coded with (C) which contain besides the mine tailing substrate, 20% top soil, 5% CaCO₃ and 5% zeolite; (F1%) and (F7%) both have the same substrate and amendments plus 1 % and 7 % fungi, respectively. These experimental treatments have been part of a larger experiment with nine experimental treatments and five replicates each. The experiment was carried out in a growth chamber under controlled conditions (60% relative humidity and light/dark cycle regime of 16-h light/22 °C and 8-h night/16 °C with Sylvania cool-white incandescent lamps, 11 W m⁻²) using 400 ml polyethylene pots that were arranged in a randomized pattern, and randomly rearranged every 2 days to minimize the influence of microclimatic variation. All pots were watered daily using distilled water to a maximum WHC. The water flow was vertical, and no leaching occurred from the experimental pots. After 3 months, the plants have reached maturity, and the experiment was considered completed; destructive sampling was done.

Experimental design of lysimeters

The lysimeters described in this section were part of an experimental system comprising a total number of 35 lysimeters, which were made of PVC tubes 30 cm wide and 50 cm deep each. All lysimeters were arranged keeping the same number of replicates as in pots, in an aboveground box placed outdoors in the city climate. They were filled in the first 20 cm from the top, with the same mine tailing substrate and treatments as in the pot experiment, representing a mid-scale version. The last 30 cm of each lysimeter was filled with mine tailing substrate only, without treatments. They were sown in October and sampled non-destructive after 11 months, only aboveground parts on 1 September, and destructive after 20 months on 2 June. All systems were exposed to the more appropriate field conditions with free access to small invertebrates, but no of birds and mammals, and without wind regime, these being protected by construction walls. The water flow was vertical with the possibility of collecting the leachate and with a better assessment of the biomass production than it would have been possible in the field. All lysimeters were watered daily using distilled water in the summer, weekly in spring and autumn seasons, or they were not watered during rainy days. The water that stagnated on the surface of the substrate after melting the snow was extracted with a polyethylene syringe, and later filtered. The leachate was collected with the help of funnels installed at the base of each lysimeter, after heavy rains.

Experimental design of plots

A randomized block design (four blocks) was used to cover the longitudinal and transversal gradients present on the tailing dam, leading to a total of 36 plots of 2×2 m. The substrate was manually homogenized with a shovel between and within plots. Amendments were applied only in the first 20 cm of the substrate; the homogenization with the tailing substrate was also manually done with shovels within each plot. In this experiment, there was no boundary, and the substrate was less compacted. All plots were watered two times a week with uncontaminated spring water only in the first month after seed in and then were left under natural conditions reaching extreme temperatures of +60 °C in summer and -40 °C in winter on the surface of the tailing dam. The water flow was both vertical and lateral, and invertebrates had access into the plots as well as birds and mammals. Sowing was done in May, and *A. capillaris* was sampled on 1 September (after 3.5 months), 2 October (after 5 months), and 3 March (after 10 months).

An overall comparison of the experiments from the point of view of the methodological details is presented in table 46.

Sampling of the mine tailing substrate and measured variables

After physicochemical mine tailing substrate characterization at the beginning of the experiment, mine tailing substrate was also sampled at the end of the pot and lysimeter experiments. In the field experiment, two extra campaigns for substrate sampling were done before the first plant sampling campaign, so there were five sampling soil campaigns in total. Each time, nine (amended) substrate sub-samples were sampled from each plot and pooled in a single homogenized sample. In all experiments, the same variables were determined: pH, H, EC, and mineral nitrogen concentration in the form of N-NH₄⁺, N-NO₃⁻, and N-NO₂⁻ and available phosphate P-PO₄³⁻ and pseudo total element content using *aqua regia*. Apart from these, LOI, total carbon, and CEC were performed only at the start and at the end of the field experiment, while sequential extractions were measured using the substrate from pots, lysimeters, and field at the start and at the end of the experiment.

Sampling of plants, their preliminary preparation and measured variables

Plants in the field experiment it was sampled in five small clumps from each subplot. At the second plant sampling campaign in the field, species identification was performed, and the coverage of each species on 2×2 m was measured. This moment was chosen because it was at the end of the growing season, with maximal plant development. A correction of the measured cover for the small clumps of *A. capillaris* sampled in September was not performed. moment. Plants were washed with tap water and rinsed several times with ultrapure water. Before drying, a small part of roots was preserved in a fixing solution (45.85 % ultrapure water, 45.85 % (v/v) ethanol, 6 % (v/v) formaldehyde, and 2.3 % v/v) acetic acid). Further, histochemical staining of AM and estimation of the mycorrhization degree within the root system were performed.

In all three scale experiments, plants were separated in aboveground and underground parts, and only in the case of field experiment that a composite sample was used for each plot and sampling. The fungal structure of the root segments was visualized at×40 magnification. After that, we computed the intensity of the mycorrhizal colonization (M%) and the arbuscular abundance in the root system (A%). Then, all plant materials were lyophilized and weighted to determine their dry weight (d.w.). Dry plant material was grounded using a cooling stainless

steel and stored at minus 45 °C until use for determining of variables. These variables were: photosynthetic pigments, (chlorophyll a and b and carotenoids), protein concentration, enzyme assays (superoxide dismutase (SOD) and peroxidase (POD)), and lipid peroxidation in terms of malondialdehyde content, and elements content.

Table 46 Comparison of the experiments from the point of view of the methodological details (Neagoe et al. 2014).

	Pot	Lysimeter	Field plots
Experimental treatments	Control (code C): Substrate+20% top soil+5% CaCO ₃ +5% zeolites Treatment 1 (code F1%): Substrate+20% top soil+5% CaCO ₃ +5% zeolites+1% inoculum Treatment 2 (code F7%): Substrate+20% top soil+5% CaCO ₃ +5% zeolites+7% inoculum		
No of replicates	5	5	4
Homogenization of tailing substrate	Concrete mixer		Manually with shovels between and within plots
Homogenization of amendments with tailing substrate	Pot by pot in small plastics	Concrete mixer	Manually with shovels within each plot
Boundary material holding the substrate	Plastic pot	Plastic tube	No boundary, less compacted substrate
Date of seeding	Not relevant	October	May
Watering	Daily	Daily in the summer, weekly in spring and autumn, no during rains	The first month after seeding two times a week, then only natural rains
Water flow	Vertical	Vertical	Vertical and lateral
Wind regimen	Absent	Protected by building walls	Natural
Light regimen	Controlled	Natural	Natural
Temperature regimen	Controlled	Natural in a city	Natural at the surface of tailing pond
Access of small invertebrates	No	Yes	Yes
Access of birds and mammals	No	No	Yes
Type of sampling	Destructive (end of experiment)	Not destructive first sampling (only above ground parts), destructive second sampling	Not destructive, three times, only <i>Agrostis capillaris</i> L 3.5 months (September, 1 st sampling), 5 months (end of October, 2 nd sampling), 10 months (March, 3 rd sampling)
Month of plants sampling	3 months after the start of experiment	11 months (September, 1 st sampling), 20 months (June 2 nd sampling)	

Variables measured from leachate

Leachate was sampled after each abundant hydrological event. These were measured after filtration the leachate through a 0.45µm Whatman cellulose nitrate filter, and the measured variables were: N-NH₄⁻, N-NO₃⁻, and N-NO₂⁻ and available phosphate P-PO₄³⁻ and total element content.

Selected findings

Table 47 shows that the intensity of mycorrhizal colonization (M%) and the arbuscule abundance (A%) in the root system of the F1% inoculated treatment were significantly larger than the control and F7% at month 5 (end of growing season), and there were no significant differences between the control and F7% treatment.

Table 47 Mycorrhization degree of *A. capillaris* roots in the experiment at field scale at sampling months 5 and 10 (Neagoe et al. 2014).

		October 2009, month 5		March 2010, month 10	
		A%	M%	A%	M%
Treatment (<i>n</i> =4)					
Control	Mean	7.96	14.06	8.40	14.03
	SD	6.40	15.41	7.46	5.77
F7%	Mean	6.53	10.76	1.01	12.30
	SD	6.93	7.30	1.00	16.22
F1%	Mean	32.56	51.81	7.51	18.22
	SD	15.36	21.25	4.87	10.23
Mann–Whitney <i>U</i> test					
Control vs. F7%		NS	NS	NS	NS
Control vs. F1%		0.021	0.043	NS	NS
F7% vs. F1%		0.043	0.021	0.021	NS

NS not significant

Table 48 summarizes the variation patterns of P in plant parts at lysimeter and field scales from one treatment to another. In all cases, the P concentration in plants is larger in the inoculated treatments than in the control. The differences between P concentrations are not statistically significant at lysimeter scale, but in many cases, statistically significant at field plot scale (at all sampling months for roots, and at 3.5 and 10 months for aboveground). In the field, the largest concentrations of P in plants are in the case of F1% treatment.

Proteins, SOD, and POD

As can be seen in table 49, the protein concentrations increase statistically significant in the aboveground parts of plants (at lysimeter scale, and 3.5 and 10 months at field plot scale) and in the roots (at 5 and 10 months at field plot scale), with maximum concentrations always in the F1% treatment. There is also a decrease of SOD and POD enzymatic activities statistically significant in some cases in the field for SOD in roots and shoot, and many cases at lysimeter and field scales for POD in roots and aboveground.

Patterns of plant development

The patterns of plant development at the three scales are summarized in figures 43, 44, and 45. Statistically significant differences could not be found in the pot subset of data and in the lysimeter subset at the month 6 crop. However, in the lysimeter subset at month 20 crop, the aboveground biomass of treatment 1 % was significantly larger than that of the control and 7 % treatment. The average value of the root biomass increased not statistically significant from the control to 7 % treatment and 1 % treatment figure 44), although the 1 % treatment at lysimeter scale at month 20 crop had a much larger biomass than the control and 7 % treatment. The total biomass at lysimeter scale at month 20 was significantly larger in 1 % treatment than in the control ($p=0.028$) and in 7 % treatment ($p=0.047$). All biomasses at pot and lysimeter scales were the result of the growth of *A. capillaris*, without any other species from the seed bank of the topsoil. In the field, an important phenomenon was the growth of many different

species than *A. capillaris*. Fourteen plant species grew in the plots, with different average richness (not statistically significant) in each treatment. The total cover of *A. capillaris* and the other species had the largest average value in the F1% treatment, but not statistically significant (figure 45), compared to the control. This was not due to an increase of *A. capillaris* cover. What made the difference was the significant increase ($p=0.043$) of the cover of other species than *A. capillaris* in F1% treatment compared to the control. The relative importance of not-seed species increased strongly from the control to the 1 % treatment (figure 45).

Figure 43 Aboveground biomass patterns (standardized values) at scales 1 and 2. In month 20 at lysimeter scale the biomass of the 1% treatment was significantly larger than that of the control and the biomass of the 7% treatment (Mann-Whitney U test). The other differences in the data subsets were not significant (Neagoe et al. 2014).

Figure 44 Root biomass patterns (standardized values) at scales 1 and 2. None of the differences between the experimental treatments at pot or lysimeter scale was statistically significant (Mann-Whitney U test). The p value of the test for differences between 1 % treatment and control in month 20 at lysimeter scale was 0.15 (Neagoe et al.2014).

Table 48 Phosphorus, proteins, SOD, and POD in *A. capillaris* and shoot/root ratio at experimental scales 2 and 3 (Neagoe et al. 2014).

Shoots/roots d.w.		Ratio	Lysimeter, month 20			Field, month 3.5			Field, month 5			Field, month 10		
			Control 0.71	F7% 0.78	F1% 0.77	Control 5.85	F7% 3.60	F1% 2.36 ^a	Control 1.80	F7% 1.75	F1% 1.53	Control 3.28	F7% 2.52	F1% 2.24
Roots	P (µg/g d.w.)	Average	655.0	764.8	713.1	660.9	707.8 ^a	748.0 ^{a,b}	614.1	634.8	725.1 ^{a,b}	615.9	729.0 ^a	772.6 ^a
		SD	181.9	85.08	84.64	11.32	20.82	14.53	15.23	23.32	23.58	14.54	42.22	26.80
	Proteins (mg/g d.w.)	Average	13.21	14.70	17.42	28.25	33.77	35.63	16.31	26.19 ^a	31.83 ^a	33.43	41.67	42.81 ^a
		SD	1.34	5.60	3.08	3.852	5.116	8.39	0.814	8.875	6.916	8.891	1.524	1.562
	SOD (U/mg protein)	Average	77.45	71.25	65.07	54.91	50.24	42.51	92.86	71.24 ^a	65.27 ^a	44.80	34.17	32.60 ^a
		SD	8.890	13.46	16.30	5.747	7.702	7.629	7.202	12.24	5.935	15.94	1.438	2.470
	POD (U/mg protein)	Average	50.84	43.00	49.21	82.90	75.14	73.51 ^a	305.0	121.6 ^a	75.78 ^{a,b}	65.71	39.73	36.01
		SD	16.84	24.05	16.73	9.718	5.360	7.794	83.99	41.66	5.166	22.34	11.59	6.73
Aboveground parts	P (µg/g d.w.)	Average	1,261	1,409	1,304	1,314	1,313	1,416 ^b	1,270	1,342 ^a	1,516 ^b	1,296	1,373 ^a	1,452 ^{a,b}
		SD	215.3	366.6	242.4	86.06	9.563	31.13	32.03	44.51	71.19	21.02	27.56	51.28
	Proteins (mg/g d.w.)	Average	38.24	44.59 ^a	52.46	97.99	119.5	163.7 ^a	53.73	66.05	78.26	130.1	139.0 ^a	162.1
		SD	11.86	11.45	25.96	14.24	22.06	28.13	3.699	21.91	25.36	12.58	12.61	29.78
	SOD (U/mg protein)	Average	47.64	30.78	36.38	16.75	13.79	12.06	29.04	26.06	21.52	16.55	14.70	12.35 ^a
		SD	16.78	18.01	19.03	4.905	3.743	4.113	3.540	7.117	7.760	1.678	1.887	3.083
	POD (U/mg protein)	Average	18.99	12.82 ^a	11.76	8.484	5.871	3.848	11.14	7.129	4.143	8.20	7.51	5.23
		SD	8.798	6.502	2.978	2.036	2.567	0.940	1.808	2.171	0.762	1.45	1.25	1.84

In this case, aboveground plant was simply noted with shoot

^a Significantly different than the control

^b Significantly different than F7% according to Mann–Whitney *U* test ($p < 0.05$)

The 7 % treatment had lower plant cover than the control (figure 45), although the differences were not statistically significant. The total plant cover of F1% treatment was significantly larger ($p=0.043$) than that of F7% treatment. The shoots/roots ratio decreased statistically significantly from the control to the F1% treatment in the field at month 3.5 (table 50). In the case of all other data subsets, the decrease of the ratio was not statistically significant. Apart from these results, many correlations of the whole data set were found (not shown here).

Figure 45 Plant cover and richness patterns at scale 3. The total plant cover and the plant cover of species other than *A. capillaris* in the 1 % treatment were significantly larger than in the 7 % treatment (Mann-Whitney U test). The plant cover of species different than *A. capillaris* was significantly larger in the 1 % treatment than in the control. The differences between the cover of *A. capillaris* were not significant between experimental treatments (Neagoe et al. 2014).

Summary of discussions about own data

Roots mycorrhization: although our research hypothesis was relatively simple, referring to the effect of inoculation on the plant development, the testing approach with experiments performed at three scales and with different plant ages at the sampling moment allowed us to have an insight into the complexity of the phenomena. There was a native mycorrhizal colonization from the amendment topsoil up to values of 14 %. The experimental treatment F7% did not differ from the control from the point of view of this variable, but F1% treatment had significantly larger mycorrhizal colonization compared to the control and F7%, up to 51 %. We believe that the addition of 7 % inoculum carrier into the substrate significantly changed the substrate features concerning plant development requirements. Although it is recommended to use the inoculum in a percentage of 10% for the soil, our results showed that this was not the case for tailing substrate. A weakness of our data is that the measurement of mycorrhization degree was operationally limited to two subsets of samples (sampling moment) at the field scale. We chose the samples from the field scale experiment because this scale is the most relevant for the application of research results in real remediation projects. Because of the similar amendments and the small scale specific to the root infection process, it is reasonable to consider that a larger mycorrhization in F1% treatment occurred also in the experiments performed at pot and lysimeter scales.

Phosphorus and toxic elements concentration

Phosphorus concentrations in *A. capillaris* significantly increased in roots in F1% treatment compared to the control in all field data subsets. P in shoots also increased significantly in F1% treatment in one subset (month 10). In addition, the concentrations of P in shoots and roots in

F7% were larger than the control in several field subsets, but they have also been significantly smaller than those in F1% treatment. The difference between F7% and F1% treatments might be due to a decrease of the contact surface between roots and the control substrate (dilution of control substrate concentration due to an increase of expanded clay concentration). This decrease could be stronger in the field than in pots and lysimeters because of the larger heterogeneity of topsoil distribution in space (larger pieces of soil than in the plot and lysimeter experiments). However, we cannot provide evidence supporting these speculations because the idea for working with F1% and F7% treatments was based purely on the intention to optimize the costs of remediation in the field using the combination of amendments and the strong difference between these treatments was not anticipated. Phosphorus concentrations in plants in our experiment are smaller than the minimum of the optimal range for plants (2,000–5,000 mg P/kg d.w.), explaining the rather strong and systematic effect at all sampling moments.

There was almost significant effect on toxic element mobility and uptake in plants. Toxic elements decreased significantly only in one single case, namely As in the roots of young plants in field experiment (3.5 months). Metal concentrations had an influence on biochemical variables independent of P in field conditions only at the beginning of plant development (plant age 3.5- months). Still, one cannot generalize this to all plant development cases represented in our data set. This could be because the substrate was excessively contaminated, and the available toxic elements for plants are too large to be controlled by the changed rhizosphere conditions resulting from inoculation.

Oxidative stress

The oxidative stress enzyme activity significantly decreased in roots in all field data subsets and in shoots in the lysimeter experiment at sampling month 20 (POD) and field experiment at sampling month 10 (SOD). The concentrations of proteins significantly increased in roots and shoots together with those of P in some data subsets. The decrease of oxidative stress after inoculation of contaminated substrate with AMF is found in many studies, but it is usually due to a decrease of metal accumulation in plants. In our case, the oxidative stress (estimated by SOD and POD) decreased as a result of inoculation and was inversely proportional with the concentrations of proteins, which in turn were controlled by P nutrition improvement.

Biomass and plant cover

The biomass of *A. capillaris* was larger in the F1% treatment only in the lysimeter experiment at month 20 in roots. The average biomass values in the other pot and lysimeter data subsets were larger, but not statistically significant. In the field data subsets, the cover of *A. capillaris* in F1% treatment was not larger than the control, although the P concentration in *A. capillaris* significantly increased, and the shoot/root ratio significantly decreased in young plants (3.5 months) showing a better root development in F1% inoculated substrate under the conditions of P scarcity in our plants. The cover of species other than *A. capillaris* was significantly larger in F1% treatment compared to the control. F1% treatment in the field had a total cover significantly larger than F7% treatment. To possibly explain this, we observe that in the field compared to pot and lysimeter experiments, the substrate is less compact, not being held by a rigid boundary. This may have led to a lower bulk density of the amended substrate (not measured), lowest in the F7% treatment (where the largest quantity of expanded clay was applied). In conditions of daily or regular watering occurring in lysimeter experiments, the differences between the treatments resulting from their different WHC have not been so

evident; moreover, in the pot, the WHC was kept constant by weighing pots during watering. However, in the case of natural watering by rains occurring in the field, these differences probably has been a much stronger effect, reversing the positive effect of inoculation in the case of the F7% treatment. At the same time, in the heterogeneities of F7% treatment where the plants developed, the P nutrition of the existing *A. capillaris* individuals is improved compared to control, so the lower cover with plants is not associated to a worse physiological condition of plants than in control. The fact that only in the field there are other plant species than *A. capillaris* can be explained by the difference between the states of the soil used at pot and lysimeter scales and that used at field plot scale. In the field, the soil was fresh, with intact seed bank and plant fragments with potential for vegetative development, while in the pot and lysimeter experiments, the soil was dried at room temperature and stored for a while before the experiments. Better plant conditions especially in F1% treatment probably allowed the development of species less adapted to stress conditions, which competed for resources with *A. capillaris*.

Our data have indirect relevance for the use of plants in the monitoring of soil contamination, pointing the crucial importance of knowing the development stage of the individuals of a species in the interpretation of the measured concentrations of toxic elements and oxidative stress variables in samples from the field. Proposals for using biochemical variables and concentrations of toxic elements in plants for monitoring pollution were reported only by few researchers. Also, from an applied point of view, based from our results, we can recommend the use of AMF inoculation in a package for amendments in tailing dams, but the optimal amount of expansion to be used should still be verified testing concentrations larger than 1 % but smaller than 7 %.

Conclusions

The inoculation with AM fungi in expanded clay carrier had a beneficial effect on the development of plants in the amended mine tailing substrate heavily contaminated with toxic elements. The effect of inoculation was stronger when the quantity of expanded carrier was smaller (1 vs. 7 % inoculum in expanded clay), probably because of changes in substrate features. The improvement of plant growth was due mainly to an improvement in phosphorus nutrition leading to an increase of protein concentration and decrease of oxidative stress enzyme activity (SOD and POD). In a single data subset, an effect of inoculation on the uptake of several toxic elements could be proved (a decrease of As concentration in plant roots correlated with a decrease of oxidative stress independent from the effect of P concentration increase). The multi-scale approach allowed us to find differences between the patterns characteristic to the data subset (identified by experimental scale and/or sampling moments). There were some types of such differences: significant statistical differences between the averages of the measured variables have not been similar in all subsets (e.g., biomass of plant parts), correlations between measured variables have not always been the same in all subsets (e.g., As vs. SOD and P vs. proteins), These subset-specific patterns point out the existence of physiological differences between plants in different development states (as a result of sampling at different plant ages). Consequently, we can conclude that there are arguments supporting the acceptance of the specific research hypothesis, especially the largest number of significant differences involving P than those involving toxic elements. However, the situation is much more complex than envisaged on two lines: the processes involved at each scale (especially the existence of important ecological processes at field scale) and the dynamic

nature of the causal effects of P and toxic elements (as reflected by differences between data subsets due to plant age at sampling moment). From an applied perspective, an important result is related to the role of non-seeded species in providing a plant cover at least in the initial phases of remediation. Even if the not seeded species would have died in the later stage of development, they would provide important quantities of organic matter to the substrate allowing the better development of the resistant *A. capillaris*. Performing the experiments at multiple scales allowed us to decrease the risks associated with field experiments and to characterize the complexity of the phenomena involved in real ecologically based phytoremediation.

Two methodological rules for phytostabilization: account for the spatial geochemical variability of tailings and cover the broadest possible range of time scales by experiments

This type of research was published by *Constantinescu et al. 2019, in Science of the Total Environment 692, 1057-1069*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.07.299> in the article with the title: "Implications of spatial heterogeneity of tailing material and time scale of vegetation growth processes for the design of phytostabilisation".

Phytostabilisation projects for tailing dams depend on processes occurring at spatial scales of 10^6 m² and at decadal time scales. Most experiments supporting the design and monitoring of such projects have much smaller spatial and time scales. Usually, they are only designed for one single scale. Our studied reported in this section were performed at three coupled experiments carried out at pot, lysimeter and field plot scales using six sampling times from 3 to 20 months. These three experiments are actually the treatments not reported in the first part of this section, and are part of the same experiments already described there. I will complete here only with the briefly description of the treatments that are the subject of this section, without going into too much detail regarding the experimental design.

Experimental conditions, design and measured variables

Physical and chemical characterization of mine tailings can be seen in section the first part of this section. I will only mention here that the mine tailing substrate used in these experiments is an arid one with a sand-silt texture, and the screening on the whole tailing dam revealed a large spatial heterogeneity of the substrate variables (for example, the pH varied between 2.43 and 7.82 and Pb ranged between 150.4 and 2879 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$). For this reason, we used composite samples (as described in the first part of this section) for prepared the following additionally treatments: the mixture of substrate, top soil and limestone was considered as the control (C). We added 5% zeolite (S.C. Biosolaris SRL Braşov, Romania) (Z), and 5% raw *Trifolium* fertilizer (Tr), hereinafter called green fertilizer, which was obtained from the same source as the topsoil for the control, to create treatments (CZ) and (CZTr). The doses of limestone (CaCO₃) and top soil to the polluted mine tailing substrate were established at the beginning of the first experiment as can be seen in first part of this section.

In the present study, we decided to use only 5% (w/w) of zeolite (half of the recommended amount) due to the cumulative effects of the other amendments used in the mixture on the composite mine tailings. In this manner, we maintained a pH similar to the mine tailings, and any difference between the applied amendments should be due to mechanisms other those due to a pH increase. The amount of green fertilizer was the same (5%) due to similar considerations. To use raw *Trifolium* as a source of fertilizer, this plant species was harvested

from the same location as the topsoil, namely, in Ȃlmaşu Mare village, located in the Zlatna area (46°06'33"N and 23°07'11"E) which is a non-polluted area due to its topographical position. Harvesting took place in May, just before flowering, because the tissues of immature plants decompose more rapidly than those of mature plant parts. Two perennial species were used, *Trifolium pretense* L. and *Trifolium repens* L. The plants were sown in August, two years before harvesting. They were chopped to 2 cm to increase their decomposition rate. Table 49 describes the properties of mine tailings, topsoil, green fertilizer and zeolites. An experiment description and orthophoto images of the investigated mine tailing are presented in figure 46.

Table 49 Elemental composition of mine tailings and amendments (topsoil, green fertilizer and zeolite) used in all experiments, n=5 from homogenized materials except for the zeolite, that was characterized by the manufacturer (EC in [$\mu\text{S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$], elements in [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{d}\cdot\text{w}$]) *Kjeldahl nitrogen, (Constantinescu et al. 2019).

Variables	Mine tailing			Top soil		
	Min.	Max.	Mean±Stdev	Min.	Max.	Mean±Stdev
pH	2.43	7.82	5±2.43	706	712	7.08±0.03
EC	63	1947	603.1±653.9	41.5	46.11	44.08±2.011
As	59.84	429	237.3±106.6	12.28	14.06	13.1±0.737
Cu	141.2	4300	1737±1472	40.05	44.12	42.24±1.537
Pb	150.4	2879	1137±689.7	27.09	30.20	28.94±1.354
Zn	368.5	2680	1020±714.2	51.36	62.09	55.11±4.057
P	427	579	465.9±46.26	1423	1578	1488±84.2

Variables	Green fertilizer		
	Min.	Max.	Mean±Stdev
N *	18.8	25.02	22.1±2.6 %
Protein	6.33	8.41	7.45±0.87 %
As	0.359	0.468	0.45±0.084
Cu	8.44	14.89	11.61±2.655
Pb	2.516	4.502	3.401±0.933
Zn	69.42	88.80	74.32±8.305
P	3259	3293	3282±13.73

Variables	Zeolite - clinolit		
	Mineralogical composition		
Clinoptilolit	71-83.3 %		
Volcanical glass	4.1-9.7%		
Plagioclas	6.6-6.67%		
SiO ₂	2.25-2.6%		
Other minerals	3-4%		
CEC	1.51 meq 100 g ⁻¹ soil		
Bulk density	1.65-1.75 g cm ⁻¹		

Figure 46 Left: Orthophoto images of the tailing dams in Zlatna area, Romania. The small tailing dam was selected for experiments; the white arrow indicates the location of the field experiment. Right: the structure of the bivariate experimental approach (Constantinescu et al. 2019).

Selected findings

The full raw dataset can be found in the Data in Brief accompanying the original article. The biomass of the plants was very low in the pot experiment (0.077 - 0.14 g for the aboveground parts and 0.071 - 0.175 g for the roots). As a consequence, the other variables could not be measured in all replicates for pots, precluding the application of tests for differences between averages.

The effects of treatment and time on the substrate

a) The effects on geochemical and mineralogical variables

We considered as conventional geochemical variables the elements determined by ICP-MS. No significant differences between the geochemical variables (listed in table 49) of the experimental substrates were obtained as a result of treatment or of sampling time at the same experimental scale. There were significant differences between the overall average values for each experimental scale (pots vs. lysimeters vs. field plots), reflecting, as expected, the substrate heterogeneity on the tailing dam surface. This phenomenon is illustrated by the PCA for all sampled substrates at all sampling times and scales (figure 47). Bi, Cd, Co, Pb and V showed a correlated distribution of concentrations (factor 1 of the PCA), Zn correlated with As and Li on factor 2, while Sr and Rb were represented mostly on factor 3. The biplot of sample scores shows the clustered distribution of samples by experimental scale. We then applied the ANOVA test separately for other effects of variables for the samples resulting from each experiment. Quartz, fayalite, magnetite, and clay minerals were identified with XRD (details can be found in supplementary material of the original article). Additionally, some minor peaks were observed. There were no differences in mineralogy over time or between treatments.

As shown in figure 47, the heterogeneity of mine tailing substrate sampled from the surface of a single tailings dam, makes the data characterizing the mining substrate very well grouped, depending on the three experiments.

Figure 47 Biplots of sample scores (left) and of variable coordinates (right) using two PCA factors from the geochemical data (Constantinescu et al. 2019).

b) The effects on forms of nitrogen, phosphorus and substrate (soil) respiration

Many soil variables significantly changed by treatments in the pot experiments (averages, standard deviations and results of ANOVA test are listed in Table 50a and 50b), but these

changes were not seen in the lysimeter and field plot experiments. Soil nitrate increased as a result of the zeolites and of green fertilizer addition after three months, while soil phosphate increased only for the CZTr treatment. Total P in soil was affected both by treatment and by time in the field, with a strong effect from the addition of green fertilizer. Soil respiration did not change significantly in the pots for any treatment, but strongly increased in the CZTr lysimeter experiment.

Table 50a Means, standard deviations (in italics) and results of the ANOVA test for the effects of treatment and time on the mobile forms of nutrients and other soil variables: pots and lysimeters. NA = not available, NS = not significant. * - *** = levels of significance. EC is expressed in [$\mu\text{S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$]; all N and P forms in [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{ d.w}$]; moisture in [%] and respiration in [$\text{mg CO}_2\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{ d.w}\cdot 2\text{ h}$] (Constantinescu et al. 2019).

Variables	Pot				Lysimeter			
	Treatment			ANOVA	Treatment			ANOVA
	C	CZ	CZTr		C	CZ	CZTr	
EC	1067	1022	1292	***	479.8	635.2	636.4	NS
	<i>95.38</i>	<i>187.7</i>	<i>58.43</i>		<i>182.9</i>	<i>121.4</i>	<i>128.5</i>	
pH (H ₂ O)	7.476	7.438	7.302	***	7.168	6.882	7.082	NS
	<i>0.101</i>	<i>0.081</i>	<i>0.065</i>		<i>0.064</i>	<i>0.639</i>	<i>0.219</i>	
N-NO ₃ ⁻	0.479	5.164	38.32	***	16.97	22.76	40.37	NS
	<i>0.152</i>	<i>1.764</i>	<i>5.401</i>		<i>6.679</i>	<i>6.115</i>	<i>31.53</i>	
N-NO ₂ ⁻	0.709	0.265	0.594	***	0.094	0.097	0.120	NS
	<i>0.210</i>	<i>0.094</i>	<i>0.172</i>		<i>0.076</i>	<i>0.040</i>	<i>0.056</i>	
N-NH ₄ ⁺	25.42	9.297	11.24	***	4.176	4.307	6.242	NS
	<i>7.574</i>	<i>2.785</i>	<i>5.165</i>		<i>1.701</i>	<i>1.519</i>	<i>0.629</i>	
P-PO ₄ ³⁻	5.984	4.196	20.15	***	27.18	52.34	39.39	NS
	<i>2.141</i>	<i>1.919</i>	<i>6.204</i>		<i>8.982</i>	<i>39.15</i>	<i>25.25</i>	
Moisture	11.03	10.43	14.00	***	4.862	4.962	2.890	NS
	<i>0.565</i>	<i>0.901</i>	<i>0.876</i>		<i>2.019</i>	<i>0.970</i>	<i>0.898</i>	
Respiration	2.048	2.499	3.233	NS	4.274	4.291	18.50	***
	<i>0.628</i>	<i>0.897</i>	<i>1.210</i>		<i>1.384</i>	<i>1.164</i>	<i>8.978</i>	
P _{total}	638.7	570.1	726.1	NA	363.7	432.8	422.8	NS
	<i>35.18</i>	<i>17.04</i>	<i>251.7</i>		<i>29.28</i>	<i>106.6</i>	<i>75.52</i>	

The clustered distribution of the samples from the three experiments can be seen. Variables increase in the directions pointed to by the lines in the right-side graphs (for instance, samples from the pot experiments - sampled after 3 months, are shown in the left graph, have the largest concentrations of Cd, V, Bi and Co in the substrate); the origins of the biplots correspond to the average values of the variables; the overlap or small angle between the lines of two variables or of a variable and a factor indicates a strong positive correlation, while orthogonality indicates lack of correlation; the length of a variable line is proportional to the contribution of the variable to the extracted factors.

c) *The effects on other variables*

There are several variables, which were measured only for the field plots, at t_0 and at the 10th

month of the experiment, namely, CECeff, LOI and total TC (the data can be seen in the raw data set accompanying this article) for which LOI significantly increased from approximately 0 to 1.1%; CECeff increased approximately five times; and the TC content increased from approximately 0 to 7 g kg⁻¹. There were no significant differences in these variables between the treatments, either at the beginning or after 10 months.

The development of vegetation in the lysimeters was associated with a decrease in the number of lysimeters in which leachate (the concentrations of elements measured by ICP-MS in this water can be seen in the raw data set accompanying the article), especially for the CZTr treatment. No statistical tests for differences between the qualities of the leachate could be performed because of the low and different number of samples for each treatment. The mobile fraction of elements in the substrates differed significantly between the experimental scales, following to some extent the pseudo-total geochemical differences. There were no differences between treatments within an experimental scale, or in time from the start to the last time of sampling.

The effects of treatments on plant variables

The effects of treatments and time on the roots and aboveground parts variables in the lysimeters and field plots are presented in tables 51 and 52 (means and StDev, results of ANOVA tests). The addition of 5% green fertilizer increased the dry root biomass in pots (raw data in the Data in brief, no other variables were measured in all replicates for statistical tests due to the small biomass) or in the lysimeters, but no effect of 5% zeolites was noticed in this respect (both treatments were added to the control already having 20% top-soil and 5% limestone added). The aboveground biomass significantly increased (ANOVA test) in the pots after three months for both the zeolite and green fertilizer raw data, shown in the Data in Brief accompanying this article). In the lysimeters, the concentrations of elements in the roots decreased with the treatments for many elements. This was not observed under field conditions. In contrast, the concentration of P in the roots significantly increased with treatments in the field, but not in the lysimeters. The activities of SOD and POD in roots were significantly decreased by zeolites and green fertilizer additions in the field and lysimeters for some sampling times.

The concentrations of toxic elements in the aboveground biomass significantly changed in the lysimeters over time but not with the treatments. In comparison, under field conditions, the levels of toxic elements changed with the treatments in several cases and changed over time only for Cu (table 52). P concentrations in the aboveground biomass increased with the treatments in the field, but not in the lysimeters (table 52). POD decreased for sampling times of 4 and 5 months as a result of the zeolites and green fertilizer. In the lysimeters, the concentrations of pigments in the biomass were significantly changed by the treatments and by the sampling times, while in the field, pigment concentrations varied mostly by sampling time (table 52). The differences in accumulation factors followed those of the concentrations of the toxic elements in plants (data can be seen in the supplementary material of the original article). There were no significant changes in the transfer factors for these elements over time or as a result of treatments. In the field, a diversification of the plant community occurred in the plots by five months (figure 48). The total cover of plants consisted not only in the planted *Agrostis capillaris* but also in many other species (as listed in the raw data set that can be found in the supplementary material of the original article), these species probably originated from the top soil.

Table 50b Means, standard deviations (in italics) and results of the ANOVA test for the effects of treatment and time on the mobile forms of nutrients and other soil variables: field plots. NS = not significant. * - *** = levels of significance. EC is expressed in [$\mu\text{S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$]; all N and P forms in [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ d.w]; and moisture in [%] (Constantinescu et al. 2019).

Variables	Field experiment															ANOVA	
	0 months			1 month			4 months			5 months			10 months			Treatment	Time
	C	CZ	CZTr	C	CZ	CZTr	C	CZ	CZTr	C	CZ	CZTr	C	CZ	CZTr		
EC	469.0	482.8	402.0	327.5	342.4	358.0	962.3	935.5	778.0	418.0	437.3	489.0	202.3	147.0	131.3	NS	***
	<i>147.6</i>	<i>213.0</i>	<i>87.61</i>	<i>52.85</i>	<i>31.69</i>	<i>189.1</i>	<i>163.7</i>	<i>227.1</i>	<i>210.2</i>	<i>101.6</i>	<i>184.0</i>	<i>114.4</i>	<i>35.29</i>	<i>64.42</i>	<i>23.19</i>		
pH (H ₂ O)	4.99	5.62	4.96	7.24	7.33	7.16	6.87	7.05	7.10	7.47	7.65	7.65	7.90	7.98	8.06	NS	***
	<i>0.53</i>	<i>0.76</i>	<i>0.30</i>	<i>0.13</i>	<i>0.20</i>	<i>3.15</i>	<i>0.07</i>	<i>0.30</i>	<i>0.25</i>	<i>0.16</i>	<i>0.25</i>	<i>0.26</i>	<i>0.09</i>	<i>0.15</i>	<i>0.07</i>		
N-NO ₃ ⁻	2.113	2.304	2.434	4.803	1.995	1.955	4.065	3.372	9.072	0.508	3.455	4.526	18.59	15.60	11.74	NS	***
	<i>0.172</i>	<i>0.426</i>	<i>0.312</i>	<i>4.611</i>	<i>0.622</i>	<i>1.201</i>	<i>3.372</i>	<i>1.092</i>	<i>8.034</i>	<i>0.336</i>	<i>2.580</i>	<i>1.979</i>	<i>13.61</i>	<i>9.293</i>	<i>9.354</i>		
N-NO ₂ ⁻	0.144	0.206	0.160	0.131	0.097	0.110	0.613	0.344	0.553	0.289	0.303	0.493	0.239	0.262	0.307	NS	***
	<i>0.101</i>	<i>0.044</i>	<i>0.078</i>	<i>0.020</i>	<i>0.041</i>	<i>0.067</i>	<i>0.445</i>	<i>0.083</i>	<i>0.284</i>	<i>0.197</i>	<i>0.020</i>	<i>0.179</i>	<i>0.135</i>	<i>0.023</i>	<i>0.103</i>		
N-NH ₄ ⁺	5.489	6.106	5.583	11.31	11.46	11.47	5.347	5.693	4.668	3.633	4.049	4.040	4.760	5.379	5.442	NS	***
	<i>2.537</i>	<i>1.130</i>	<i>2.657</i>	<i>2.408</i>	<i>0.920</i>	<i>4.953</i>	<i>2.209</i>	<i>2.589</i>	<i>1.920</i>	<i>0.603</i>	<i>1.508</i>	<i>0.660</i>	<i>0.694</i>	<i>1.008</i>	<i>0.585</i>		
P-PO ₄ ³⁻	8.251	11.33	10.35	5.554	6.988	6.605	9.419	8.367	8.701	10.69	5.654	9.670	5.133	3.913	6.467	NS	**
	<i>4.725</i>	<i>3.519</i>	<i>3.450</i>	<i>2.294</i>	<i>3.481</i>	<i>2.978</i>	<i>3.744</i>	<i>1.461</i>	<i>2.868</i>	<i>3.377</i>	<i>1.918</i>	<i>5.216</i>	<i>1.891</i>	<i>1.197</i>	<i>2.095</i>		
Moisture	13.73	16.56	15.41	21.44	18.93	21.70	8.036	8.280	10.14	14.13	12.27	14.18	17.32	14.91	37.27	NS	*
	<i>3.450</i>	<i>2.658</i>	<i>1.981</i>	<i>1.677</i>	<i>1.715</i>	<i>9.408</i>	<i>1.461</i>	<i>2.032</i>	<i>2.336</i>	<i>1.424</i>	<i>3.303</i>	<i>0.854</i>	<i>1.066</i>	<i>2.589</i>	<i>41.26</i>		
P _{total}	396.8	379.4	396.8	472.8	495.6	575.6	488.8	502.1	589.0	500.0	505.7	595.0	506.4	509.2	599.7	***	***
	<i>8.54</i>	<i>3.781</i>	<i>8.25</i>	<i>7.985</i>	<i>12.66</i>	<i>254.3</i>	<i>12.47</i>	<i>11.76</i>	<i>14.89</i>	<i>17.25</i>	<i>18.81</i>	<i>20.31</i>	<i>15.09</i>	<i>16.57</i>	<i>20.93</i>		

Table 51 Means, standard deviations (in italics) and results of the ANOVA test for the effects of treatment and time on the belowground variables in the lysimeters and field plots. NA = not available, NS = not significant. * - *** = levels of significance. All elements are expressed in [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ d.w]; biomass in [g]; protein in [$\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$]; SOD and POD in [$\text{U}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}$ protein]; and LP in [$\mu\text{M MDA}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ d.w.] (Constantinescu et al. 2019).

Variables	Lysimeter				Field experiment										
	20 months			ANOVA Treatment	4 months			5 months			10 months			ANOVA	
	C	CZ	CZTr		C	CZ	CZTr	C	CZ	CZTr	C	CZ	CZTr	Treatment	Time
As	27.58	27.75	5.479	***	21.48	24.19	23.50	14.05	12.84	11.65	8.567	8.777	9.908	NS	***
	<i>1.868</i>	<i>4.543</i>	<i>0.667</i>		<i>5.741</i>	<i>5.227</i>	<i>3.275</i>	<i>1.590</i>	<i>5.624</i>	<i>4.785</i>	<i>3.085</i>	<i>2.323</i>	<i>2.221</i>		
Cu	587.4	544.0	200.6	***	457.0	409.4	533.8	263.9	261.0	210.8	244.6	266.6	195.2	NS	***
	<i>61.94</i>	<i>52.42</i>	<i>60.04</i>		<i>97.99</i>	<i>45.65</i>	<i>82.87</i>	<i>24.54</i>	<i>57.75</i>	<i>60.91</i>	<i>21.51</i>	<i>34.89</i>	<i>13.26</i>		
Pb	57.19	57.45	19.80	***	60.40	54.87	73.20	39.58	35.47	36.30	32.59	31.83	27.78	NS	***
	<i>6.907</i>	<i>17.06</i>	<i>3.686</i>		<i>16.93</i>	<i>18.91</i>	<i>12.87</i>	<i>5.323</i>	<i>11.85</i>	<i>8.920</i>	<i>11.16</i>	<i>11.21</i>	<i>3.032</i>		
Zn	709.3	567.0	305.9	***	538.5	498.9	381.1	518.3	523.9	462.2	447.7	418.6	402.4	NS	NS
	<i>45.76</i>	<i>71.12</i>	<i>29.42</i>		<i>127.3</i>	<i>107.2</i>	<i>34.50</i>	<i>50.06</i>	<i>176.2</i>	<i>31.40</i>	<i>120.8</i>	<i>88.92</i>	<i>28.58</i>		
P	719.3	655.0	805.6	NS	653.2	660.9	824.5	603.4	614.1	801.1	635.3	615.9	844.9	***	*
	<i>24.78</i>	<i>181.9</i>	<i>125.8</i>		<i>30.85</i>	<i>11.32</i>	<i>29.44</i>	<i>12.61</i>	<i>15.23</i>	<i>32.75</i>	<i>63.63</i>	<i>14.54</i>	<i>51.84</i>		
Biomass	10.61	8.918	21.89	**	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	<i>1.265</i>	<i>3.122</i>	<i>9.553</i>		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Proteins	13.22	13.21	32.81	***	24.65	28.25	42.45	15.12	16.31	39.37	33.65	33.43	49.10	***	***
	<i>7.63</i>	<i>1.339</i>	<i>5.084</i>		<i>5.142</i>	<i>3.852</i>	<i>4.779</i>	<i>1.703</i>	<i>0.814</i>	<i>2.941</i>	<i>9.897</i>	<i>8.891</i>	<i>10.11</i>		
SOD	84.34	77.45	62.96	NS	59.05	54.91	35.06	111.4	92.86	39.30	48.15	44.80	30.86	***	***
	<i>21.94</i>	<i>8.890</i>	<i>27.41</i>		<i>6.379</i>	<i>5.747</i>	<i>1.153</i>	<i>20.99</i>	<i>7.202</i>	<i>3.089</i>	<i>13.86</i>	<i>15.94</i>	<i>5.446</i>		
POD	55.88	50.84	40.69	NS	96.24	82.90	64.45	372.4	305.0	134.6	68.75	65.71	42.34	***	***
	<i>30.28</i>	<i>16.84</i>	<i>23.42</i>		<i>13.96</i>	<i>9.718</i>	<i>6.229</i>	<i>76.59</i>	<i>83.99</i>	<i>59.84</i>	<i>30.88</i>	<i>22.34</i>	<i>8.582</i>		
LP	0.216	0.177	0.199	NS	0.252	0.291	0.295	0.262	2.269	0.320	0.243	0.289	0.421	***	NS
	<i>0.035</i>	<i>0.034</i>	<i>0.045</i>		<i>0.035</i>	<i>0.035</i>	<i>0.011</i>	<i>0.062</i>	<i>0.076</i>	<i>0.054</i>	<i>0.053</i>	<i>0.030</i>	<i>0.114</i>		

Table 52 Means, standard deviations (in italics) and results of the ANOVA test for the effects of treatment and time on the aboveground plant variables in the lysimeters and field plots. All elements are expressed in [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ d.w.]; biomass in [g]; protein in [$\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$]; SOD and POD in [$\text{U}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}$ protein]; chlorophyll a and b and carotenes in [$\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ d.w.]; and LP in [$\mu\text{M MDA}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ d.w.], NA= not available, * - *** = levels of significance, NS = not significant, (Constantinescu et al. 2019).

Variables	Lysimeter						Field experiment													
	11 months			20 months			ANOVA		4 months			5 months			10 months			ANOVA		
	C	CZ	CZTr	C	CZ	CZTr	Treatment	Time	C	CZ	CZTr	C	CZ	CZTr	C	CZ	CZTr	Treatment	Time	
As	0.637	0.551	0.093	4.082	5.610	5.312	NS	***	10.42	5.688	5.487	5.414	5.474	4.739	4.380	5.460	3.662	NS	NS	
	<i>0.274</i>	<i>0.333</i>	<i>0.024</i>	<i>0.763</i>	<i>1.978</i>	<i>1.319</i>			<i>7.899</i>	<i>1.569</i>	<i>0.784</i>	<i>1.324</i>	<i>1.833</i>	<i>1.216</i>	<i>1.585</i>	<i>0.933</i>	<i>0.802</i>			
Cu	9.554	9.856	15.28	13.00	9.856	15.28	NS	***	174.0	96.36	89.1	147.8	124.3	109.2	235.3	223.1	124.7	***	***	
	<i>0.931</i>	<i>1.557</i>	<i>5.162</i>	<i>0.931</i>	<i>1.557</i>	<i>5.162</i>			<i>113.2</i>	<i>34.31</i>	<i>23.30</i>	<i>24.55</i>	<i>21.89</i>	<i>5.848</i>	<i>36.39</i>	<i>41.03</i>	<i>24.47</i>			
Pb	4.015	4.283	2.914	24.12	21.37	18.89	NS	***	32.71	16.17	12.54	16.32	15.95	15.79	19.23	21.49	11.64	*	NS	
	<i>0.866</i>	<i>0.492</i>	<i>0.344</i>	<i>2.874</i>	<i>8.215</i>	<i>3.560</i>			<i>21.12</i>	<i>4.435</i>	<i>3.192</i>	<i>4.932</i>	<i>5.107</i>	<i>2.886</i>	<i>4.551</i>	<i>3.794</i>	<i>2.966</i>			
Zn	164.6	156.3	134.0	204.4	209.1	179.0	NS	***	325.2	204.1	191.2	254.2	209.5	181.5	194.8	204.9	146.2	*	NS	
	<i>13.22</i>	<i>23.49</i>	<i>10.44</i>	<i>30.71</i>	<i>62.32</i>	<i>36.93</i>			<i>181.4</i>	<i>48.14</i>	<i>13.72</i>	<i>26.91</i>	<i>33.04</i>	<i>33.95</i>	<i>34.94</i>	<i>30.11</i>	<i>20.94</i>			
P	1337	1496	1556	1329	1261	1477	NS	NS	1327	1324	1511	1200	1270	1702	1277	1296	1783	***	NS	
	<i>179.4</i>	<i>169.7</i>	<i>173.2</i>	<i>223.6</i>	<i>215.3</i>	<i>208.5</i>			<i>61.28</i>	<i>86.06</i>	<i>9.882</i>	<i>83.00</i>	<i>32.03</i>	<i>163.6</i>	<i>27.63</i>	<i>21.02</i>	<i>167.6</i>			
Biomass	22.32	21.49	41.43	11.05	12.60	26.22	***	***	NA	NA	NA									
	<i>1.358</i>	<i>3.665</i>	<i>13.80</i>	<i>1.679</i>	<i>2.372</i>	<i>5.94</i>			-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-			
Proteins	54.47	49.24	59.07	36.66	38.24	62.36	***	NS	87.52	97.99	202.8	49.9	53.73	104.0	118.2	130.1	182.4	***	***	
	<i>12.04</i>	<i>11.49</i>	<i>5.429</i>	<i>11.93</i>	<i>11.86</i>	<i>17.77</i>			<i>14.49</i>	<i>14.24</i>	<i>8.748</i>	<i>5.4</i>	<i>3.699</i>	<i>6.4</i>	<i>15.6</i>	<i>12.58</i>	<i>13.59</i>			
SOD	0.272	0.343	0.323	42.89	47.64	39.28	NS	***	17.90	16.75	8.125	32.22	29.04	15.42	18.90	16.55	9.876	***	*	
	<i>0.100</i>	<i>0.095</i>	<i>0.076</i>	<i>29.22</i>	<i>16.78</i>	<i>16.91</i>			<i>5.558</i>	<i>4.905</i>	<i>1.270</i>	<i>5.626</i>	<i>3/540</i>	<i>2.705</i>	<i>2.222</i>	<i>1.678</i>	<i>2.030</i>			
POD	7.707	9.041	11.08	20.88	18.99	17.22	NS	**	9.993	8.484	3.194	16.41	11.14	4.957	12.22	8.199	8.002	***	*	
	<i>1.663</i>	<i>5.504</i>	<i>4.648</i>	<i>13.82</i>	<i>8.798</i>	<i>9.065</i>			<i>2.892</i>	<i>2.036</i>	<i>0.334</i>	<i>8.862</i>	<i>1.808</i>	<i>1.864</i>	<i>0.727</i>	<i>1.453</i>	<i>1.489</i>			
Chlorophyll a	2.653	2.886	4.260	1.260	1.329	1.708	**	***	2.918	3.382	3.476	2.026	1.960	2.446	1.561	1.086	1.197	NS	***	
	<i>0.202</i>	<i>0.329</i>	<i>1.565</i>	<i>0.202</i>	<i>0.258</i>	<i>0.349</i>			<i>1.071</i>	<i>0.474</i>	<i>0.439</i>	<i>0.114</i>	<i>0.241</i>	<i>0.372</i>	<i>0.160</i>	<i>0.190</i>	<i>0.204</i>			
Chlorophyll b	0.896	1.001	1.562	0.520	0.522	1.159	***	**	1.145	1.390	1.347	0.821	0.781	1.030	0.481	0.446	0.607	*	***	
	<i>0.127</i>	<i>0.217</i>	<i>0.723</i>	<i>0.073</i>	<i>0.090</i>	<i>0.098</i>			<i>0.359</i>	<i>0.151</i>	<i>0.169</i>	<i>0.106</i>	<i>0.152</i>	<i>0.185</i>	<i>0.077</i>	<i>0.105</i>	<i>0.072</i>			
Carotenes	0.165	0.177	0.245	0.075	0.079	0.165	***	***	0.971	0.809	0.797	1.923	1.863	2.041	1.239	1.092	1.494	NS	***	
	<i>0.006</i>	<i>0.021</i>	<i>0.069</i>	<i>0.005</i>	<i>0.012</i>	<i>0.017</i>			<i>0.489</i>	<i>0.072</i>	<i>0.072</i>	<i>0.106</i>	<i>0.188</i>	<i>0.309</i>	<i>0.132</i>	<i>0.190</i>	<i>0.203</i>			
LP	0.279	0.275	0.280	0.260	0.278	0.214	NS	*	0.416	0.439	0.464	0.253	0.260	0.331	0.203	0.256	0.377	***	***	
	<i>0.014</i>	<i>0.050</i>	<i>0.040</i>	<i>0.023</i>	<i>0.044</i>	<i>0.031</i>			<i>0.041</i>	<i>0.041</i>	<i>0.033</i>	<i>0.025</i>	<i>0.027</i>	<i>0.006</i>	<i>0.031</i>	<i>0.020</i>	<i>0.044</i>			

Figure 48 General aspect of the field experiment with four blocks of nine randomized treatments and the location of the three treatments reported here in one of the blocks (Iordache et al. 2010).

Summary discussions about own results

Clay minerals and zeolites in particular have been reported to contribute to stabilization due to their high specific surface area, negative surface charge, high adsorption and ion exchange capacity, while green fertilizer is frequently used to improve the poor N and P status of tailings. The methods for improving the mine tailing nutrient status may be different and locally calibrated as a function of local conditions, plant species used and management objectives. The amendments had a positive effect on the average values of biomass recorded for CZ and especially for CZTr, as a result of ensuring by zeolites a permanent reservoir of water, so necessary on arid mining substrates. Moreover, green fertilizer mixed with zeolitic tuff seems to be an important tool for improving phytostabilization of mine tailing substrates.

The decrease in oxidative stress after the addition of amendments in the mining substrate was reported here, as well as by other experiments (Neagoe et al., 2014; Neagoe et al., 2013). What was new with respect to findings of oxidative stress is the explicit effect of the decrease both nutrient status and toxic elements on enzyme activity values, and the effects of time since sowing. This cannot easily be observed in separate, single scale studies because of the highly dynamic character of these variables, reflecting the plant development cycles, their different growth rates in time within and between years. The reported findings show the ability of *Agrostis capillaris* to minimize the element accumulation in the aboveground parts of this species, which confirmed that this species is an excluder of the elements investigated in this research, and a tolerant plant species, which could explain the low values < 1 for the transfer factors and accumulation factors found in these experiments (data can be found in supplementary material of the original article).

In this work, the method was used in an innovative way to visualize and summarize the patterns of toxic element distributions in time and across experimental scales. The lower number of replicates with leachate observed in the vegetated lysimeters is typical for any vegetated soil column compared to bare soil columns, and this effect was also found in experiments with mine wastes (Neagoe et al., 2009).

The innovative methodological point is to consider these scale-specific patterns in the remediation plan. The spatial heterogeneity across the tailing surface may lead to a stratified approach of the remediation solution, while the time-scale specific results may be used either directly or indirectly in designing the remediation. Amendments such as zeolites may have a direct, positive, measurable effect especially when the plants are young, but the effect could be confounded later by other factors. In such a case, zeolites are still useful for remediation, although at field scales in the long term, their effects are no longer statistically significant. Biological factors such as fungi inoculum may have a stronger influence, especially over the long term, but this is sometimes difficult to prove in the very short term, especially when the material carrying the spore has separate effects on soil properties (e.g., the expanded clay, Neagoe et al., 2014). Small-scale experiments can be of indirect use in the design of remediation by allowing the screening of a large set of experimental treatments at the beginning, from which only a subset is selected for larger scales and for more expensive experiments.

Conclusions

The objective of our research was to investigate at multiple space and time scales the effects of a combination of amendments aimed at improving nutrient status and decreasing the availability of toxic elements. We found some general patterns for the effects of amendments across pots, lysimeters and field plots but also many scales specific differences. Zeolites, responsible for a decrease in the availability of toxic elements, manifested their effects on the concentrations and oxidative stress to a lesser extent than the green fertilizer, reflecting the stronger limiting character for nitrogen and phosphorus macronutrients for plant growth on the tailing substrate.

We explicitly detected at the whole-dataset scale the effects of P, toxic elements and time on plant physiological variables. The novelty of this research is that it detects the effects of the treatments related to processes having different time scales and shows their potential use in the design of complex eco-remediation techniques for tailings management. The proposed experimental methodology could be of general use, with improvements, for the design of tailing dam eco-remediation technologies.

Future research directions relate to potential improvements in the methodology. Choosing the right variables for discriminating between soil/substrate conditions is important. Testing a scientific hypothesis across spatial scales with coupled experiments from pots to field would probably need a complex set of variables and a flexible frequency of sampling, reflecting the ontogenetic and ecological processes.

B5 Technological development

The phytoremediation technique that our group of researchers developed had two stages, namely the transition from TRL2 to TRL3 a first stage, and the second one, from TRL3 to TRL4. Currently, we have applied a technology transfer project to be able to reach TRL6.

Partially, these results were reported at the 14th *Symposium on Remediation, Bio-Geo-Interaction in Metal Contaminated Areas, September 30th - October 1st, 2015 Jena, Germany, in the plenary lecture “Examining the Romanian context for rehabilitation of abandoned mining areas”, at the 15th Symposium on Remediation, From "expert knowledge" to basic science to application: 15 years of bio-geo interactions, 13-14 October 2016, Jena, Germany also in a plenary lecture entitled “Optimizing a remediation method on a tailing dam”, at the Workshop “Research in the soil-water-plant-atmosphere system” - partial results INTER-ASPA, Târgoviște September 24, 2019, UEFISCDI complex partnership project 34/2018 <http://www.inter-aspa.ro>, as well as during the Bio-Geo-Colloquium of May 12, 2023, Jena, Germany, one-hour course with the title “Long-term research on a TRL4 eco-technology for the remediation of tailings dams.*

First stage - the transition from TRL2 to TRL3

To optimize the phyto remediation method, we selected the tailing dam Valea Mealu located in the Certej catchment in Hunedoara county, in the southeast of Apuseni, the Metaliferi Mountains, geographic coordinates: 45°57'38.97"N, 22°58'55.39"E (see figure 49). This tailing dam was partially colonized with vegetation in early 2014, when we began our preliminary investigations.

Figure 49 Certej catchment - left; overview of the Valea Mealu tailing dam - right (Neagoe et al. 2015).

The major problem of this tailing dam is the huge heterogeneity of the pH (range between ≈ 2 and 7) and of some toxic elements such as Pb (min. 178, max. 4500 mg kg⁻¹); Zn (min 397, max 3960 mg kg⁻¹) and Cd (min 1.86 max 26.72 mg kg⁻¹). Because the selected tailing dam was partially colonized with vegetation, we had the opportunity to study the natural succession as a basis for a more complex method of accelerating ecological succession. For this activity we used a sampling network on transects (T1-T5) and on plots delimited according to the major

type of vegetation (birch, acacia and shrubs), and in the front part of the dam where there was no vegetation, we installed an experiment at the plot scale (as can be seen in figure 50), after first performing an experiment at the pot scale and in parallel one at the scale of lysimeter. First, we characterized the mine tailing substrate from a physico-chemical point of view (number of samples: $n = 86$; variables measured from the tailing substrate: pH, EC, H, LOI, macro and microelements (table 53), after which we proceeded to the plant inventory (data not presented here, as they will be included in complementary habilitation thesis).

Table 53 Physico-chemical characterization of the mine tailing substrate (Neagoe 2023).

Variable	pH	EC [$\mu\text{s cm}^{-1}$]	H [%]
Min.	1.92±0.98	221.2±109.8	3.66±0.47
Max.	7.18±0.179	1250±305.4	13.55±0.657
Element	Pb	As	Zn
Unit	[mg kg ⁻¹]		
Min.	153.7±21.43	178.1±21.46	594.6±45.13
Max.	292.4±90.38	313.1±31.11	1029±554.7

Figure 50 Sampling network of the substrate, vegetation and invertebrates on Valea Mealu dam. The bottom left plot in red was chosen for the field-scale experiment (Iordache et al. 2015).

In the phytoremediation technologies applied to date, we have used fungi (and bacteria) as succession accelerators in metal-contaminated environments. Increased resistance of plants to toxic elements and increased uptake of macronutrients were observed, as shown in figures 41-45 (previous section) depicting *A. capilaris* biomass in pot and lysimeter experiments and plant cover of *A. capillaris* and other species in the field experimental plots.

The question we asked was to what extent the effect of the expanded clay support was reflected on the plant biomass. Thus, the answer to this question came after the application of an optimized phytoremediation methodology up to TRL3 in a first stage, that consisted, as I already stated above, in the consecutive work at three experimental scales, namely at the scale of pots, lysimeter and plot in the field. These experiments were carried out with *the aim* of establishing the most effective treatment leading to the that acceleration of the vegetative cover installation on the arid surface of Valea Mealu tailing pond. For this extensive research, the experimental approach can be seen in figure B51, and the objectives are:

Objective 1: investigating the effect of different amendments and/or inoculants on HMs transfer in plants and their oxidative stress.

Objective 2: assess of the influence of plants (coupled or not, with different treatments) on the export of HMs from the soil profile to local groundwater.

Figure 51 Experimental approach at three spatial scales (Neagoe 2023).

Preliminary pot experiment as a basis for field experimental design where we showed that inoculation with 1% fungi is better than with 7% fungi

Measured variables from the mining substrate at time t_0 from $n = 10$ composite sub-samples were: pH (H_2O), electrical conductivity (EC), humidity (mine tailing moisture, H), loss on ignition (LOI), ammonium ($N-NH_4^+$), nitrate ($N-NO_3^-$), nitrite ($N-NO_2^-$), available phosphate ($P-PO_4^{3-}$), and heavy metals (HMs).

Variable measured from mine tailing substrate at t_{final} from all 65 pots were: pH, EC, substrate respiration, H, LOI, $N-NH_4^+$, $N-NO_3^-$, $N-NO_2^-$, $P-PO_4^{3-}$, and HMs.

Variable measured from plants (roots and aboveground parts from all 65 pots) were: biomass by plant part / cover by vertical layer, N, P, pigments, HMs, oxidative stress variables (SOD, POD and LP), mycorrhization degree and soil invertebrates.

In the tables 54 are presented the physico-chemical characterization of the mine tailing substrate including heavy metals, used into the pot experiment. After inspecting these results, we took the decision to use amendments and inoculants to improve the mine tailing substrate. Therefore, we amended the substrate with 20% top soil (code Ts), 5% fresh clover (*Trifolium pratense* + *Trifolium repens*) (cod Tr), 7% mycorrhizal fungi (*Glomus intraradices*), and 1% mycorrhizal fungi + 6% expanded clay, establishing 13 treatments which can be seen in figure 52 (left).

Table 54 Measure variables in the mine tailing substrate used in the pot experiment (Neagoe 2023).

Variable	pH	EC	H	LOI	N-NH ₄ ⁺	N-NO ₃ ⁻	N-NO ₂ ⁻	P-PO ₄ ³⁻
Units		[μS cm ⁻¹]	[%]		[mg kg ⁻¹]			
Average	6.58	1546	3.45	2.35	7.803	5.797	0.047	30.52
StDev	1.02	504.5	0.38	0.31	3.131	2.135	0.015	2.34
Variable	Ca	K	Mn	Fe	Ni	As	Pb	Zn
Units	[mg kg ⁻¹]							
Average	3207	13290	1078	14767	84.01	293.1	206.3	872.8
StDev	816.9	2529	275.6	1545	12.65	30.72	26.65	200.1

The tested hypotheses can be seen in figure 53. We sowed the the mine tailing substrate with *A. capillaris*, cv. *Metallica*, the time of the experiment being 30 days and it run in a growth chamber under fully controlled conditions: 70% relative humidity and a light/dark cycle regime of 16 hours light / 22 °C and eight hours night / 16 °C with Sylvania cool white incandescent lamps, 11W m⁻². All pots (13 treatments x 5 replicates each= 65 pots). The pots were placed randomly (as can be seen in figure 54) and redistributed randomly every day, at the time of their irrigation with a volume of water calculated to maintain the humidity of the substrate found after the water retention capacity test.

Figure 54 Pots randomly distributed into the growth chamber (Neagoe 2023).

The purpose of the experiment was to **obtain a larger biomass production** on the barren mine tailing substrate under the various treatments, capable to *phytostabilize* the toxic element.

Selected findings

- The inoculation with 7% fungi did not increase the biomass of the plants compared to 1% fungi as can be seen in figure 55.
- The inoculation with 7% fungi in one case decreased the P concentration in shoots compared to 1% fungi and decreased the Cd in roots of plants ($\mu\text{g} \times \text{g}^{-1}\text{d.w.}$) grown without topsoil or green fertilizer (figure 56).
- The inoculation with 7% fungi did not increase the N concentration in roots compared to 1% fungi (figure 57).
- The inoculation with 7% fungi did not increase the relative abundance of arbuscules and the relative mycorrhizal frequency (% , average, ANOVA, figure 58).

Legend: C = contaminated mining substrate; E = expanded clay; Ts = Top soil ; F= mycorrhizal fungi; Tr = *Trifolium*

Figure 52 Design for running the experiments at three scales (Neago 2023).

Figure 53 Working hypotheses of the experiments at three scale (Neagoe 2023)

Figure 55 Biomass dry roots (BDR) and biomass dry shoots (BDS) [g d.w., average, ANOVA] of *A. capillaris* (Iordache et al. 2016).

Figure 56 P concentration in shoots (P_S) and Cd concentration in roots (Cd_R) ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ d.w., average, ANOVA), of *A. capillaris* (Iordache et al. 2016).

Univariate Results for Each DV (Plants_PotsOct2016_Repe)				
Sigma-restricted parameterization				
Effective hypothesis decomposition				
Exclude condition: v1=1				
Effect	N[%]R SS	N[%]R MS	N[%]R F	N[%]R p
Intercept	171.931	171.931	3663.19	0.00000
Amendment	0.892	0.892	19.011	0.00021
Fungi	1.218	0.609	12.97	0.00015
Amendment*Fungi	0.329	0.164	3.511	0.04600
Error	1.126	0.046		

Univariate Results for Each DV (Plants_PotsOct2016_Repe)				
Sigma-restricted parameterization				
Effective hypothesis decomposition				
Exclude condition: v1=1				
Effect	Chl Total SS	Chl Total MS	Chl Total F	Chl Total p
Intercept	490.049	490.049	495.775	0.00000
Amendment	87.608	87.608	88.631	0.00000
Fungi	20.548	10.274	10.394	0.00056
Amendment*Fungi	5.633	2.816	2.849	0.07755
Error	23.722	0.988		

Figure 57 Total Keldahl nitrogen in roots (N%R) and total chlorophyll (Chl Total) in shoots (average, ANOVA) of *A. capillaris* (Iordache et al. 2016).

Figure 58 Relative mycorrhizal frequency (M%) and relative abundance of arbuscules (A%) of *A. capillaris* (Iordache et al. 2016).

Conclusions after performing the pot scale experiment

- We found that there is no reason to apply in the field, 7% fungi. These pot experimental results confirm previous results from Neagoe et al. 2014 with substrate from another tailing dam.
- We decided to compare in the field 1% fungi with 2% fungi. The operational hypothesis was that no effects will not be observed, and that 1% will be the low-cost option for accelerating the ecological succession

Plot experiment where we showed that inoculation with 1% fungi is better than with 2% fungi.

In chronological order, the second experiment was the one on the plot scale in the field with two tested hypotheses (see figures 52 and 53 in the middle).

Variables measured from mine tailing substrate were: physico-chemical pH, EC, LOI, N-NH₄⁺, N-NO₃⁻, N-NO₂⁻, P-PO₄³⁻ and HMs.

Variables measured from plants were: vegetation cover for each sampling moment, both with *A. capillaris* L. and with other plant species, HMs, Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen (TKN); oxidative stress (non-enzymatic and enzymatic variables), LiDAR measurements and the following functional traits of plants: from roots - root length (RL), root length density (RLD), root diameter (RD) by thickness class, tensile strength (TS); from aboveground part: height of individuals, leaf surface, stomatal conductance, chlorophyll. For functional traits were sampled n = 3 subprobe/parcelă x 5 fragmente de rădăcină = 15 replicate x 35 parcele = 525 analysed samples.

Physico-chemical variables and element concentrations at the beginning of the plot experiment are presented in the table 55. After inspecting these results, we concluded that the pH of the mine tailing substrate is acidic and it presented N and P deficiency (values in red color in the table). As in the case of the pot scale experiment, it was necessary to correct the pH and improve the nutrition of the substrate, using the same amendments.

Table 55 Measured variables in the mining substrate at the time t₀ (n = 50), Legend: pH of the substrate solution (H₂O), EC - electrical conductivity H - humidity (mine tailing moisture), LOI - loss on ignition, N-NH₄⁺ - ammonia, N-NO₃⁻ - nitrate, N-NO₂⁻ - nitrite, P-PO₄³⁻ = phosphate, HMs = heavy metals (Neagoe 2023).

Variable	pH	EC	H	LOI	N-NH ₄ ⁺	N-NO ₃ ⁻	N-NO ₂ ⁻	P-PO ₄ ³⁻
Units		[μS cm ⁻¹]	[%]		[mg kg ⁻¹]			
Average	4.14	1132	1.85	2.50	7.660	5.407	0.231	5.082
StDev	1.60	628.4	0.63	0.43	3.158	2.204	0.219	1.630
Variable	Al	As	Cd	Co	Cr	Ni	Pb	
Units	[mg kg ⁻¹]							
Average	8491	258.1	7.836	6.962	14.12	105.0	162.7	
StDev	696	41.22	0.342	0.684	2.197	46.29	45.36	
Variable	Ca	Cu	Mn	Mg	P	V	Zn	
Units	[mg kg ⁻¹]							
Average	768.7	37.74	945.9	14171	168.1	0.533	796.2	
StDev	60.39	9.699	37.46	1436	34.06	0.276	52.2	

From the 13 experimental treatments used in the pot experiment, we chose only 7, the most effective plus controls, for the experimental plots, as can be seen in figure 59, these being: 1. C (Control), 2. CTs (Control + Top soil), 3. CTsF1% (Control + Top soil + fungi 1%), 4. CTsF2% (Control + Top soil + fungi 2%), 5. CTsTr (Control + Top soil + *Trifolium*), 6. CTsTrF1% (Control + Top soil + *Trifolium* + fungi 1%), 7. CTsTrF2% (Control + Top soil + *Trifolium* + fungi 2%).

Bivariate experiment		Inoculum effect	Variable amount of inoculum	
Field plots 2x2 m, 5 replicates for each treatment		0% inoculum	Expanded clay with 1% fungi and without 1% fungi	Expanded clay with 2% fungi
Amendment type variable	Mine tailing substrate	X (control)		
	Mine tailing substrate + top soil	X	X	X
	Mine tailing substrate + green fertilizer	X	X	X

- 35 plots size: 2x2 m.
- 5 subplots of each of the 7 treatments.
- Placed randomly into 5 blocks having a width of 10 m and a length of 50 m.
- Randomized method (in the range of 1 to 7) obtained from : <http://www.random.org>

Figure 59 Experimental design of field plot experiment (Neagoe 2023).

The number of sampling campaigns was 8 (from which the first 4 were seasonal and the last 3 were annual), these being carried out in the following times: September 2, 2015 - only amended

mine tailing substrate, November 5, 2015, April 5, 2016, August 16, 2016, November 10, 2016, June 25, 2017, October 10, 2018, May 15, 2019. Mine tailing substrate and plants (roots plus aboveground parts) were sampled from each plot following the design depicted in figure 60.

Aspect of the plots after two years of plant development.

Figure 60 Sampling design of mine tailing substrate and plants (Neagoe 2023).

Selected findings

- Variation of the *total cover* between treatments at seven sampling moments (can be seen in figures 61-63).

Morphometric properties - roots functional treats

- Statistical differences in fresh root biomass between treatments and correlation between fresh roots measured after sample processing and root volume measured with WinRhizo (figures 64 and 65).
- Pattern of variation of root length (RL) by root diameter (RD) classes (0.3-0.4 and 0.4-0.5 mm). (figures 66 and 67).

Mechanical properties

- The effect of amendments and percentage of fungi on tensile strength (TS) and elasticity of roots (figures 68-70)

Chemical and biochemical variables

- Variation of TKN (Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen) in roots and a aboveground biomass of *A. capillaris* in all 7 sampling times (figure 71).
- P concentration in roots and aboveground biomass of *A. capillaris* in all 7 sampling times (figure 72).
- Chlorophyll and carotene of *A. capillaris* in all 7 sampling times (figure 73).
- Pb in roots, Pb and Cd in aboveground biomass, Cu in roots, and Cu and Zn in aboveground biomass of *A. capillaris* in all 7 sampling times (figure 74).
- Relative frequency of mycorrhization - M and relative abundance of arbuscules (A) in all 7 sampling times, and correlations between mycorrhization degree and pH, P- PO_4^{3-} , N- NH_4^+ and N- NO_3^- (figures 75 and 76).
- Correlations between POD, P- PO_4^{3-} , N- NH_4^+ and N- NO_3^- (figure 77).

Figure 61 Total cover on the three experimental treatments (control- amendment 1, control + top soil - amendment 2, and control + top soil + *Trifolium* - amendment 3) (average of 5 plots each) in all the 7 sampling campaigns (Neagoe et al. 2019).

Figure 62 Variation of the total percentage cover with accumulated vegetation at all layer (0-5, 5-10, 15-20, >20cm) during two sampling times (developed by Onete), (Neagoe et al. 2019).

Figure 63 Variation of natural fertilizer (rabbits droppings) in time (observed phenomenon in the last sampling moment) (Neagoe et al. 2019).

Figure 64 Variation of root wet weight of *A. capillaris* between treatments and fungi percentage (Neagoe 2023)

Figure 65 Correlation between root wet measured after sample processing and root volume measured with WinRhizo (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 66 Root length (RL by diameter classes (RD)); from diameter class: 0.3-0.4 mm (average and standard deviation) right up and 0.4-0.5 mm left down (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 67 Root length density (RLD) left, and root volume (RV) right. Amendment 1 - Control + top soil (Ts), amendment 2 - Control + Ts + *Trifolium* (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 68 Tensile strength (TS) and Young module (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 69 Variation of root diameter between treatments and fungi percentage (Neagoe 2023).

	Degr. of	RezidLgRezTr	RezidLgRezTr	RezidLgRez	RezidLgRez	RezidLgElast	RezidLgElast	RezidLgElast	RezidLgElast
Intercept	1	0.00820	0.008201	0.11466	0.735067	0.00018	0.000177	0.002759	0.958138
Amendam	1	1.08526	1.085256	15.17381	0.000114	0.59231	0.592312	9.209777	0.002558
Fungi	2	0.17078	0.085389	1.19389	0.304071	0.71116	0.355581	5.528875	0.004266
Amendam	2	0.28202	0.141012	1.97160	0.140527	0.00926	0.004630	0.071999	0.930544
Error	418	29.89607	0.071522			26.88301	0.064313		
Total	423	31.50698				28.21117			

Figure 70 Tensile strength (TS) and Young module - residuals Amendment 1 - Control + top soil (Ts), amendment 2 - Control + Ts + *Trifolium* (Neagoe 2023).

Legend:

Amendment 1 = contam. substrate + top soil (CTs)

Amendment 2 = contam. substrate + top soil + trifolium (CTsTr)

Univariate Results for Each DV (ExpT erenOct2016)								
Sigma-restricted parameterization								
Effective hypothesis decomposition								
Exclude condition: v1=1								
Effect	N[%]R SS	N[%]R MS	N[%]R F	N[%]R p	N[%]S SS	N[%]S MS	N[%]S F	N[%]S p
Intercept	98.5942	98.5942	1421.53	0.00000	345.875	345.875	4981.12	0.00000
Amendment	1.4918	1.4918	21.50	0.00001	5.983	5.983	86.17	0.00000
Fungi	0.5296	0.2648	3.81	0.02654	2.527	1.263	18.19	0.00000
Time	8.5935	4.2967	61.95	0.00000	5.936	2.968	42.74	0.00000
Amendment*Fungi	0.4518	0.2259	3.25	0.04424	0.659	0.329	4.74	0.01157
Amendment*Time	0.0296	0.0148	0.21	0.80801	0.838	0.419	6.03	0.00377
Fungi*Time	0.1744	0.0436	0.62	0.64354	0.624	0.156	2.24	0.07213
Amendment*Fungi*Time	0.0457	0.0114	0.16	0.95545	0.821	0.205	2.95	0.02537
Error	4.9937	0.0693			4.999	0.069		

Figure 71 TKN in roots (left) and aboveground biomass (right) of *A. capillaris* in all 7 sampling times (Neagoe 2023).

Legend:

Amendment 1 = contam. substrate + top soil (CTs)

Amendment 2 = contam. substrate + top soil + trifolium (CTsTr)

Univariate Results for Each DV (ExpTerenOct20)				
Sigma-restricted parameterization				
Effective hypothesis decomposition				
Exclude condition: v1=1				
Effect	P_R SS	P_R MS	P_R F	P_R p
Intercept	5077762	5077762	3200.10	0.00000
Amendment	12470	12470	7.85	0.00649
Fungi	24058	12029	7.58	0.00102
Time	1150014	575007	362.38	0.00000
Amendment*Fungi	12341	6170	3.88	0.02490
Amendment*Time	108305	54152	34.12	0.00000
Fungi*Time	13616	3404	2.14	0.08391
Amendment*Fungi*Time	11582	2895	1.82	0.13337
Error	114245	1586		

Univariate Results for Each DV (ExpTerenOct20)				
Sigma-restricted parameterization				
Effective hypothesis decomposition				
Exclude condition: v1=1				
Effect	P_S SS	P_S MS	P_S F	P_S p
Intercept	14247171	14247171	3824.26	0.00000
Amendment	278	278	0.07	0.78531
Fungi	8471	4235	1.13	0.32649
Time	3069560	1534780	411.97	0.00000
Amendment*Fungi	27958	13979	3.75	0.02817
Amendment*Time	26710	13355	3.58	0.03280
Fungi*Time	358625	89656	24.06	0.00000
Amendment*Fungi*Time	167321	41830	11.22	0.00000
Error	268233	3725		

Figure 72 P concentration in roots (left) and a aboveground biomass (right) of *A. capillaris* in all 7 sampling times (Neagoe 2023).

Legend:
 Amendment 1 = contam. substrate + top soil (CTs)
 Amendment 2 = contam. substrate + top soil + trifolium (CTsTr)

Univariate Results for Each DV (ExpT erenOct2016)								
Sigma-restricted parameterization								
Effective hypothesis decomposition								
Exclude condition: v1=1								
Effect	Chi Total SS	Chi Total MS	Chi Total F	Chi Total p	Caroten SS	Caroten MS	Caroten F	Caroten p
Intercept	855.226	855.226	775.229	0.00000	186.573	186.573	2268.18	0.00000
Amendment	0.702	0.702	0.636	0.42758	0.056	0.056	0.68	0.41076
Fungi	10.812	5.406	4.900	0.01010	0.858	0.429	5.21	0.00765
Time	107.342	53.671	48.650	0.00000	23.958	11.979	145.63	0.00000
Amendment*Fungi	6.894	3.447	3.124	0.04995	1.626	0.813	9.88	0.00016
Amendment*Time	1.651	0.825	0.748	0.47680	0.137	0.068	0.83	0.43878
Fungi*Time	24.133	6.033	5.469	0.00066	1.585	0.396	4.81	0.00168
Amendment*Fungi*Time	2.073	0.518	0.469	0.75771	1.226	0.306	3.72	0.00818
Error	79.429	1.103			5.922	0.082		

Figure 73 Chlorophyll (left) and carotene (right) of *A. capillaris* in all 7 sampling times (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 74 Pb in roots, Pb and Cd in aboveground biomass (in the graph above from left to right) and Cu in roots, Cu and Zn in aboveground biomass (in the graph below from left to right) of *A. capillaris* [$\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ d.w.], in all 7 sampling times (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 75 The relative frequency of mycorrhization - M (left), and relative abundance of arbuscules (A) in all 7 sampling times (Neagoe 2023).

	pH	U	LOI	LgEC	LgN-NH ₄ ⁺	LgN-NO ₃ ⁻	LgP-PO ₄ ³⁻
LgM%	-0.2759	.2970	.1259	.2336	.4212	.3385	-.3582
	p=.000	p=.000	p=.104	p=.002	p=.000	p=.000	p=.000
LgA%	.1100	.0922	-.2028	-.0811	-.0672	-.0307	.0448
	p=.156	p=.234	p=.008	p=.296	p=.386	p=.693	p=.564

Figure 76 Correlation between mycorrhization and physico-chemical variables of the mine tailing substrat (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 77 Variation of POD over time (1 to 7 are sampling times) - left; variation of POD between fungi percentage (0, 1 and 2%) - right (Neagoe 2023).

Conclusions

- The degree of *plant cover* was higher on the experimental treatment F2%. There were important effects on species richness, plant variables and soil variables.

Morphometric properties

- Inoculation with fungi statistically significantly increased the fresh root biomass, the highest being for the experimental treatment F2%.
- Root length (RL) increased statistically significantly for the 0.3-0.4 cm and 0.4-0.5 cm root diameter (RD) classes, being greater in the case of the treatment F2%. For all other length classes, the same pattern of variation occurs, so the phenomenon exists.
- There are no statistically significant differences for other measured morphometric variables under the conditions of this experiment.

Mechanical properties

- There is a statistically significant effect of amendments and percentage of fungi on the tensile strength (TS) and elasticity of roots, being greater for the experimental treatment F1%.
- *Chemical and biochemical variables* were positively influenced by the percentage of fungi, but also by the amendment with green fertilizer. In all cases, the time variable led to slight changes, as a result of a decrease in the nutrient stock, which cannot be compensated by the organic matter that forms from one year to the next.

Lysimeter-scale experiment was installed after the plots to verify to what extent the leachate reaches the columns with polluted mining substrate, thus the transfer of pollutants in the groundwater.

Measured variables in the mining substrate at time t_0 for a number of samples $n = 10$, were: pH, EC, H, LOI, N-NH₄⁺, N-NO₃⁻, N-NO₂⁻, P-PO₄³⁻, and HMs.

In the table 56 the physico-chemical characterization of mine tailing substrate can be seen. After characterizing the mine tailing substrate and establishing the hypotheses (see figures 52 and 53 right) that were to be tested, only selected treatment 1 (F1%) and treatment 2 (F2%) were randomly installed in lysimeters system in 5 replicates each, as can be seen in figure 78.

Table 56 Physico-chemical characterization of mine tailing substrate (Neagoe 2023).

Variable	pH	EC	H	LOI	N-NH ₄ ⁺	N-NO ₃ ⁻	N-NO ₂ ⁻	P-PO ₄ ³⁻
Units		[$\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$]	[%]				[mg kg^{-1}]	
Average	5.95	1125	3.10	2.736	26.35	24.19	1.138	7.221
StDev	0.58	368.0	0.236	0.326	7.87	12.14	1.498	0.178

Variables measured from plants

During the four consecutive cultures of *A. capillaris*, the following variables were measured: plant height, inflorescence length, chlorophyll and stomatal conductance in 10 individuals from each lysimeter, every two weeks, after the development of the plants (from the moment the above-ground biomass allowed these measurements).

At the end of each culture, the following variables were measured:

- *From plants:* plant biomass (aboveground, underground), HMs concentration, Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen (TKN), oxidative stress (non-enzymatic and enzymatic variables), mycorrhization degree, and functional traits of roots (root length (RL), root length density (RLD), root diameter (RD) by thickness class, tensile strength (TS), etc.) and aboveground parts (plant height, inflorescence length, chlorophyll, stomatal conductance).
- *From mine tailing substrate:* physico-chemical variables (pH, U, EC, LOI, N-NH₄⁺, N-NO₃⁻, N-NO₂⁻, P-PO₄³⁻, HMs) and respiration.
- *From leachate:* volume and physico-chemical variables (pH, U, EC, N-NH₄⁺, N-NO₃⁻, N-NO₂⁻, P-PO₄³⁻, HMs).

Selected findings for the plants growth in the first two culture

- Pattern of variation for *A. capillaris* L wet biomass between the two treatments (F1% and F2%) in culture 1 (C1) and culture 2 (C2) (analysis of variance one-way ANOVA) (figure 79).

Morphometric and biochemical variables

- Variation of *A. capillaris* L inflorescence length and chlorophyll content between the two treatments and in time (see figure 80).
- Statistical differences of stomatal conductance between the two experimental treatments, for a single time point (see figure 81).
- Pattern of variation for lipid peroxidase content between treatments (see figure 82).

- Assimilatory pigments concentrations in both cultures C1 and C2 treatments (see figure 83).

Chemical variables

- Pattern of variation for TKN between experimental variants in both cultures C1 and C2 and treatments as can be seen in figure 84.
- Concentrations of toxic elements in both cultures C1 and C2 and treatments, as can be seen in figure 85.

Selected findings for the leachate in the first 10 sampling moments

- Variation of pH, EC, and stocks of elements in both cultures C1 and C2 and treatments (figure 86).

Figure 78 Randomized distribution of lysimeters system and images of the 4 cultures of *A. capillaris* (Neagoe 2023).

Figures 79 Fresh biomass of *A. capillaris* from cultures 1 and 2 (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 80 Variation of inflorescence length (left) and chlorophyll content (right) in *A. capillaris* between the two experimental variants, and over time (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 81 Variation of stomatal conductance between the two experimental treatments, a single time point (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 82 Variation of lipid peroxidation in culture 1 and 2 (aboveground part of plants) (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 83 Variation of assimilating pigments (chlorophyll and carotenoids) in aboveground part of plants in culture 1 and 2 (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 84 Variation of Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen (TKN) in aboveground biomass from culture 1 and 2 (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 85a Element concentration of As, Cd, Cu, Pb, Zn and in aboveground biomass of *A. capillaris L.* culture 1 (left) and culture 2 (right) (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 85b Element concentration of P, Ca, Mg and V in aboveground biomass culture 1 (left) and culture 2 (right) (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 86 Variation of pH, EC (up) and stocks of Cu, Pb, Cd Zn (down) in leachate (processed by Nita 2022, from Neagoe 2023).

Final conclusions about pot experiment

- Inoculation with 1% fungi would be the ideal option for obtaining a lower cost in order to accelerate ecological succession
- The pot experiment confirmed that inoculation with 7% commercial fungal inoculum did not lead to better plant development. This is probably due to the effect of expanded clay on the properties of the substrate alone or mixt with various amendments. Consequently, there is no reason to apply 7% fungi on the field, given the desire to develop a cost-effective remediation method.
- We found a significant effect of fungi in the presence of green fertilizer. Presumably the release rate of phosphate from the green fertilizer was counterbalanced by the rate of uptake into the plants, preventing concentrations so high as to inhibit the fungi.
- After obtaining these results, we decided to compare in the field, the inoculation with 1% fungi with the one with 2% fungi.

Final conclusions about plot experiment

- The patterns of plant community and individual plant development are consistent under fungi inoculation are consistent with the idea that an acceleration of ecological succession occurs. Supplementary investigations are needed in order to assess the biogeochemical closure of the substrate – plants systems.
- The results from the field experiment pointed out the dynamic nature of the phenomena. Monitoring in the long term with seasonal sampling seem to be a must for assessing the most efficient bioremediation solutions. In our case the addition of green fertilizer beside top-soil could be useful only in the first months of plants development compared with simple top-soil amendment combined with 2% fungi inoculation.
- Where we show that innoculation with 2% fungi is better than with 1% fungi. Also, that addition of green manure beside top-soil makes a difference only in the short time scale
- Some variables did not worth the effort to be measured each sampling time, such as mobile forms of N, P and toxic elements. It could be that their dynamic is much faster. Other monitoring techniques such as DGT technique or electrodes coupled with data loggers will be tested.

Final conclusions about lysimeter experiment

- Wet biomass, assimilating pigments, TKN, P, Ca, Mg, and V content were statistically significant higher in F2% treatment.
- Functional traits of *A. capillaris* showed that the experimental treatment F2% is more effective than the one with F1%.
- Plant height, in-situ chlorophyll, inflorescence length and stomatal conductance varied statistically significant over time and were also statistically significant higher in F2% treatment.
- Lipid peroxidation, stomatal conductance and As, Cd, Cu, Pb, Ni and Zn content were statistically significant lower in F2% treatment.
- Output of leachate showed a decrease in the concentration of most elements over time, but also significant differences for pH, EC, Mn and Mg (not all data were sown).
- Other results obtained are still in processing phase.

Second stage - the transition from TRL3 to TRL4

Over the years, we have come to the conclusion that we need to develop a general methodology and experimental design applicable for the management of the stabilization of mine tailing ponds. Thus, we developed a methodology that comprised work at several spatial scales (pots, lysimeters and experimental plots) taking into account the spatial geochemical variability. For a successful management, we connected the three spatial scales, as can be seen in figure 87.

Figure 87 Synthesis of the findings from the works at the Valea Mica tailing pond in Zlatna, Alba county (taken from Constantinescu, Neagoe et al., 2019).

In the experiments reported in Phase I of the transition from TRL2 to TRL3, we attempted to extend plant life with sampling times over multiple growing seasons. This was a method of remediation of a tailings pond where we had 8 sampling campaigns over several seasons and years, as I have already described. We then decided that these rules should be applied as part of a general framework for the remediation of sites located in mining areas. In a later stage, on the same Valea Mealu pond, we made the transition from TRL3 to TRL4 by increasing the spatial scale from 2 x 2 m x 35 plots (total area of 140 m²) to 5 x 5 m x 10 plots (total area of 250 m²) using the same eco-remediation technology with a single plant species (5 plots) and with a mixture of two plant species (the other 5 plots).

This upscaling was possible in the project no. 453/2020, code PN-III-P2-2.1-PED-2019-2584 (<https://resetbiogeochemistry.wordpress.com/>) "TRL 4 Remediation Eco-technology of tailing dams in function of geochemical, geomorphological and ecological SETting (RESET), partial results being presented at the *Bio-Geo-Colloquium on 12 May 2023, Jena, Germany, one-hour course entitled "Long-term research on an eco- TRL4 technologies for the rehabilitation of tailings ponds"*

For this research we proposed the Pert diagram of the project presented in figure 88, which shows the relationships between the activities. As can be seen in the Pert diagram, it was a team work carried out by three partners: University of Bucharest (UB, coordinator), Ovidius University of Constanta (UOC) and Institute of Biology Bucharest (IBB). In this section I present only the personally developed methodology.

Figure 88 Pert diagram of the project. The yellow line on Valea Seşii tailing dam photo is about 1 km long. Arrows on Valea Seşii tailing dam photo show directions of potential transects (lines of stations) for abiotic and biotic investigations in project activities. A detailed plan will be set up after the eventual contracting (Neagoe 2023).

To upscale our developed eco-technology from 140 m² to 250 m² we selected and delimited the most arid and acidic area, very close to the area where the mining waste was dumped in the Valea Mealu tailing pond, as can be seen in figure 89. From this area, we sampled 70 samples to physico-chemically characterize this substrate, taking into account the huge heterogeneity of the pond. From this samples we measured the following mine tailing samples variables: pH, EC, macro- and microelements, both in the field and in the laboratory. We obtained an average pH = 3.16 (StDev = 0.34) and average EC = 609.5 µS cm⁻¹ (StDev = 782.8), the variation of these two variables can be seen in figure 90, and we found correlations field-laboratory, as exemplified in figure 91.

After the delineation of the 10 plots, the following *variables from the mine tailing substrate at time t₀* from n = 50 samples were measured: humidity (mine tailing moisture, H), LOI, N-NH₄⁺, N-NO₃⁻, N-NO₂⁻ and P-PO₄³⁻, in order to establish the need for acidity correction and the necessary amendments for the functioning of the eco-technology (see table 57).

Figure 89 Selected area (the most arid one, where the mining waste was dumped) for the plot experiment at 240 m² (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 90 Variation of pH and EC into the 70 analyzed samples (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 91 Correlations field-laboratory for Pb and As (Neagoe 2023).

Table 57 Physico-chemical characterization of the mine tailing substrate (Neagoe 2023).

Variable	H	LOI	N-NH ₄ ⁺	N-NO ₃ ⁻	N-NO ₂ ⁻	DIN	P-PO ₄ ³⁻
	[%]		[μg g ⁻¹] d.w.				
Sample 1 (average of 10)	2.373	2.071	4.225	3.261	0.037	7.524	2.922
Sample 2 (average of 10)	2.447	2.303	6.898	5.523	0.038	12.46	7.01
Sample 3 (average of 10)	2.228	2.009	5.414	3.688	0.062	9.164	5.006
Sample 4 (average of 10)	2.075	2.155	3.461	5.736	0.050	9.247	6.28
Sample 5 (average of 10)	1.132	2.188	5.055	5.279	0.034	10.37	4.191
Average	1.85	2.15	5.011	4.697	0.044	9.752	5.082
StDev	<i>0.63</i>	<i>0.11</i>	<i>1.298</i>	<i>1.138</i>	<i>0.011</i>	<i>1.822</i>	<i>1.630</i>

After this physico-chemical characterization we decided to use the following amendments: top soil, fresh clover (*Trifolium pratense* mixed with *Trifolium repens*) and AMF inoculum (*Rhizophagus irregularis*). This experiment originally proposed with 5 experimental plots with a size of 10 x 10 m was transformed into an experiment with 10 plots (two variants x 5 plots each) with a size of 5 x 5 m, for statistical reasons. In the summer of 2021, the installation works of the experiment were started, and the activities were carried out in collaboration with the local authorities, respectively with the staff of the municipality of Certeju de Sus, Hunedoara county, who participated with both manpower and the necessary equipment, as can be seen in the images in figure 92 (summer), figures 93 and 94 (autumn - inoculation with AMF and sowing), and figures 95 and 96 (monitoring - germination stage).

Figure 92 Images from the installation of the experiment in the field (summer) (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 93 Works carried out for the installation of the experiment at the plot scale on the Valea Mealu mining pond, Certeju de Sus (inoculation with AMF, sowing and irrigation campaigns in the warm autumn of 2021) (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 94 Germination sp. *Melilotus albus* L. after 10 days from sowing (left photo) and sp. *Agrostis capillaris* L. (right photo), after 20 days from sowing (Neagoe 2023).

Although the germination in the autumn seemed promising, in the spring, the degree of plant cover of the plots was not satisfactory, which is why we decided to measure EC and pH, as well as H, LOI, N-NH_4^+ , N-NO_3^- , N-NO_2^- , P-PO_4^{3-} , at a scale of 1.25 x 1.25 m inside each of the 10 plots, thus totaling a number of 160 samples, to verify the internal heterogeneity of the plots. After measuring these substrate variables, we concluded that the plants started the growing season (spring) with a slow growth, conditioned by the low pH of the substrate, which we had

initially observed but hoped to be neutralized by the amendments used, just like in the experiment at 2 x 2 m scale.

Figure 95 The stage of the germination phase of the two plant species (*Agrostis capillaris* L. and *Melilotus albus* L.), **45 days after sowing** (Neagoe 2023).

In figure 96 it can be seen that there is a close relationship between EC and pH (logarithmic forms, left) at the scale of 1.25 x 1.25 m in each plot and between pH and the degree of plant coverage (right), in early May 2022. In conclusion, our decision was to apply CaCO_3 to areas with very low pH, where no vegetation has grown. Supplementary, the entire surface of the 10 plots was fertilized twice (seasonally) with urea. This action was very effective and led to an increase in the degree of plant coverage of the experimental plots until August 17, 2022, over 50%, and until October 2022, over 70%, as can be observed in figure 97.

Monitoring based on satellite images (shown here), confirmed the trends observed in the field and the fact that a peak of plant development was achieved in October 2022 (details on the distribution of plants analyzed by downscaling at the scale of 1 m)

To patent this phyto-myco-technology, we proposed a block diagram of the demonstrated technology on a scale of 5 x 5 x 10 m (figure 98) embedded in an eco-technological approach at the scale of the landscape surrounding the tailing dam. The analysis of the literature allowed the creation of the other two block diagrams, one corresponding to a potential scenario of land structure on the Valea Seșeii pond to ensure a diversity of habitats and microhabitats compatible with the surrounding area (for which the demonstration was made on the pond on Valea Mealu) (see figure 99).

Figure 96 The relationship between EC and pH (logarithmic forms, left) at the scale of 1.25 x 1.25 m into each plot, and the relationship between pH and the degree of plant cover (right), at the beginning of May 2022 (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 97 Images of experimental plots in October 2022 (Neagoe 2023).

The other diagram is proposed for the transition from TRL4 to TRL6 (see figure 100). The structure specified in all details at higher TRL levels could be applied in the pond closure stage in 2030-2040.

This technology integrates into the toolbox for the management of river basing with mining areas in their structure associated with Critical Zone Observatories presented in the complementary habilitation thesis of Dr. Virgil Iordache and is a development of the concept for accelerating succession presented in Iordache (2020).

Figure 98 Bloc diagram of the demonstrated phyto-myco-technology at site scale (Neagoe 2023).

Figure 99 The block scheme eco-technology at the landscape scale (from www.reset.biogeochemistry.ro and the final project report available on this page).

Figure 100 Bloc diagram proposed to be used for the transition from TRL4 to TRL6 (from the applied project under evaluation PTE application, 2024, “Eco-technology TRL6 for the remediation of tailings ponds according to the geochemical, geomorphological and ecological settings of the area” no. PN-IV-P7-7.1-PTE-2024-0762).

C Plans for scientific and teaching career evolution and development

Introduction

There is a natural connection between the activities carried out in the three decades since I have been working in research, those in which I am involved now and the strategic directions in which I intend to develop my career in the future.

I will provide an overview of this evolution from several perspectives:

- From the perspective of research results.
- From the development of managerial skills at the project and functional unit level of the institution where I work.
- From the point of view of my involvement in the training of human resources at the bachelor, master and informal at doctoral level within the research projects or independently of them as associate lecturer.

As most of my work is related to research, I chose to present from the beginning an overview of past, current and future research directions in figure 101. It can be seen that throughout my career I have worked in three different methodological approaches:

1. I started with the approach characteristic of the classical school of systemic ecology of the University of Bucharest, as a member of this team. The key concept of this school from the perspective of my research interest was the biogeochemical cycle. The approach was carried out in well-specified ecological organization units, and I worked with a model of maximum complexity, with numerous compartments. I started to distance myself from this approach with the doctoral research program carried out in Germany, and definitively with my departure for a post-doc in Germany in 2003.
2. I continued with a more analytical approach, by researching the well-defined processes of heavy metal circulation and their effects on the development and physiological state of plants, as well as by investigating of the exposure of the human population to metal fluxes from contaminated areas, both as part of my PhD program from Germany. In this direction, I have developed my career primarily in terms of fundamental research, but through cooperation with other researchers, also in terms of applied research, technological transfer and assisting decisions on the management of contaminated areas - all this assuming integration in various degrees of knowledge obtained regarding different types of natural and socio-economic processes relevant to the respective areas.
3. In recent years, I have been directly involved in the development of a new innovative research methodology that takes elements from both directions mentioned above, proposing an approach in which research is also organized based on structural models, as in classical systemic ecology, but of greater small complexity, having as immediate object not the direct characterization of the cycles of the elements in the entire ecological system, but highlighting the role of some populations (in the case of my studies, those of plants) on which my interest is focused, in the production of certain well-defined ecosystem services. Recently, I have been concerned with the integrated effects of climate change and elements on the functional traits of grassland and wetland plants.

In the following, I will give a brief overview of past activities and current concerns, and then I will detail the main directions of development that I have in mind for the future.

Figure 101 Research directions in which I was involved over my career as coordinator (green cells and text) or collaborator (white cells), and strategic priorities for running of research in the future (with red bold characters).

C1 The development coordinates of the research activities carried out until now

Formation of personal capacity to perform research activities

In my development as a researcher, the key elements are the following:

- I started the research activity in a complex team that, since the 90s, was running numerous international research contracts with European funding, which allowed me to participate in the implementation of work packages designed to European standards (University of Bucharest, Department of Systemic Ecology).
- Within this team I had the opportunity of a Tempus scholarship as a master's student and thus came into contact with Professor Manfred Anke at the Friedrich - Schiller University in Jena, Germany. He became the coordinator of my PhD thesis, which I carried out at the standards of the University of Jena in that time (immediately after the reunification of Germany, years 1996-1999).

After my reintegration into the Bucharest team, I won a Marie Curie post-doc (January 2003-January 2005) and another BMBF post-doc (January-August 2005) also at the University of Jena, Germany, this time working by Western standards, the coordinators Prof. Kothe and Prof. Büchel, as well as other numerous professors came to the University of Jena in the period immediately before the start of my post-doctoral activities, from the West German universities. As a result, at the time of my final reintegration in Romania (2005), I had the experience of knowing some far-reaching European projects (through the school in Bucharest), as well as the experience of narrower approaches, but at a consecrated level of international publication (achieved in Germany).

Research groups in which I was involved

The research groups, some of them already mentioned, are the following:

1. The research team of the Department of Systemic Ecology of the University of Bucharest;
2. Institute of Environment and Nutrition Sciences, Faculty of Biology and Pharmacy, Friedrich - Schiller University of Jena, Germany;
3. Department of Applied Botany, Faculty of Biology and Pharmacy, Friedrich-Schiller University of Jena, Germany;
4. Department of Applied Geology, Faculty of Geology, Friedrich-Schiller University of Jena, Germany;
5. Research Centre for Environmental Protection and Waste Management - PROTMED of the University of Bucharest;
6. Research Centre for Ecological Services - CESEC of the University of Bucharest;

The full list of research projects can be found in my CV, which is part of this habilitation program. I will only mention that within group 1, I coordinated a youth grant type At with CNCISIS funding in Germany I did not coordinate research grants; within the PROTMED center I coordinated two reintegration grants (UEFISCDI and NATO), and I ran my main Marie Curie reintegration grant under the coordination of Dr. Iordache. Within CESEC I coordinated a sub-project from a complex partnership, a PED project, several partnership projects, two Ideas and an FP7 grant (as coordinator for Romania).

Managerial experience

I gained project management experience step by step, from 2000-2002 until now, starting from

a CNCSIS type youth grant to highly complex Complex Partnership type projects with a very consistent budget. The main challenge after reintegration in Romania was the coupling between the rigor of German research and the large-scale interdisciplinary research specific to environmental projects in partnership with various Romanian institutions. From a formal point of view, I consolidated this competence through a project manager course with a graduation certificate recognized by the relevant ministries.

At the organizational level, I have been the coordinator of the biogeochemistry and bioremediation laboratory of the CESEC centre since 2007, and since 2010 I have also been the scientific coordinator of this research centre.

The most important scientific published results

Until I worked under the guidance of researchers in West Germany, I did not publish results in ISI-quoted journals. This situation is characteristic of all those active in the research since 1995 within the Department of Systemic Ecology, as well as those who did their PhD at the University of Jena (part of the former GDR) immediately after 1990. The results from that period, however, without being at the level required for publication at the international standards accepted now and in Eastern European countries, are at a level considered good at that time. These articles reflect intense personal and team work and have supported decision-making on environmental issues.

Regarding the Bucharest school, I have published numerous papers as a co-author on the process involved in the retention of metals in floodplains and their distribution in abiotic and biotic compartments. The most important result in terms of international impact is the course held by me in Germany in May 2023 as an invited researcher in the "BioGeoKolloquium" organized by BGI Jena, Germany, entitled "Long-term research for a TRL4 myco-phytoremediation technology of tailing dams". In this course I have described in detail my and the extended team's contribution to the fundamentals of mining area management from the tailing pond scale to the catchment scale, these activities taking place in several simple or complex partnership projects and in an experimental demonstrative project (PED) in which we managed to switch from TRL3 to TRL4 (activity described in details in subchapter B5).

Shortly after I defended my PhD thesis, my supervisor Prof. Manfred Anke invited me to contribute a chapter to a treatise dedicated to macro- and microelements published by the prestigious Wiley publishing house (Neagoe 2004). This was my first publication at the highest standards, briefly described in the first chapter of this habilitation thesis. Since 2005, I have regularly published good results from post-doctoral programs and from my own projects or collaborations, in ISI-quoted journals. The directions covered by these publications are the following:

- I. *Interactive effects of multiple stressors on plant ecophysiology;*
- II. *Complex ecotechnologies for the remediation of tailing dams.*

I. Interactive effects of multiple stressors on plant ecophysiology

In basic research

- Distribution of metals in plants and physiological effects (Neagoe et al. 2013, Păun et al. 2015a, b, Neagoe et al. 2017) ;
- The role of mycorrhizal plants and fungi in large-scale ecological processes (Iordache et

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- al. 2011, Neagoe et al. 2012, Neagoe et al. 2013);
 - Coupling processes of different scales involved in the biogeochemical cycles of metals (Iordache et al. 2011);
 - Metal accumulation mechanisms in yeasts (Ofițeru et al. 2012, Oprea et al. 2014, Ruță et al. 2018, Ruță et al. 2017a and b, al. 2014, Ene et al. 2015);
 - Distribution of microorganisms in polluted soils (Sprocati et al. 2014);
 - A conceptual methodological framework for the resilience of biogeochemical services to heavy metal stress (Iordache and Neagoe 2023) ;
 - Effect of vegetation on evapotranspiration and water quality (Dunea et al. 2021).

In applied research

- Reducing the oxidative stress of plants by amending with macronutrients (Mascher et al. 2005a, 2005b, Constantinescu et al. 2019, Neagoe and Iordache 2023).

II. Complex ecotechnologies for the remediation of tailing dams

- Bioremediation techniques (Neagoe et al. 2005, Neagoe et al. 2009, Păun et al. 2012a, 2012b, Fărcășanu et al. 2012, Neagoe et al. 2014, Nicoară et al. 2014, Wernitznig et al. 2014, and Neagoe and Iordache 2021).
- Assessment of the danger and risk associated with pollution sources in mining areas (Jianu et al. 2012).
- Agricultural ecotechnologies (Mladin et al. 2011).
- Ecotechnologies of mining areas (Neagoe et al., 2011, Neagoe and Iordache 2021).

Other articles associated with heavy metal pollution of water, soils and tailings substrate have been published as follows:

- Distribution of microorganisms in mine tailing substrate (Manu et al., 2019)
- Assessing the exposure of environmental and human populations to metals (Neagoe et al. 2000, Neagoe 2008, Nedelescu et al. 2017).
- Water pollution (Paltineanu et al. 2021, Dunea et al. 2021).

All the works mentioned are only articles in ISI-listed journals, chapters in international books or books published in Romania (Mladin et al. 2011, Neagoe et al., 2011, Neagoe and Iordache 2021).

C1.1 Ongoing activities

Not yet published results

Due to the turbulence in the research funding system, relatively many good quality datasets have accumulated that are not yet published, thus a large number of manuscripts are in various stages of preparation:

- An article for the journal "***Plant and Soil***" reporting effects of some amendments on the oxidative stress in *Helianthus annuus* evaluated by a lysimeter experiment in an undisturbed structure (COBIOGEO BMBF project, contract no. 02S8294);
- One article for "***New Phytologist***" reporting coupled pot-scale and lysimeter experiments with the species *Lupinus angustifolius* (MIRACLE project, contract no EVK1-CT-2001-56001-FP5, 2001-2005).
- One article in "***Nature Plants***" reporting a combined laboratory and field experimental

research and aiming statistical modeling of N and P effects on Pb, Zn and Cu bioaccumulation in *Agrostis capillaris* and other grassland plants (ASPABIR project, contract no. 50-2012- PNII).

- An article in the "**STOTEN**" experiment with the results of an experiment using lysimeters in an undisturbed structure sampled from the Pantelimon area ((MECOTER project, PNII contract no. 291, Ideas/2007, UEFISCDI, and NATO PDD (CP)-(ESP. RIG 982571).
- An article in "**Nature Plants**" with the production of two experiments carried out at the scale of pots in which the influence of temperature on the development of plants under stress conditions due to pollution with heavy metals was investigated (METTELFLUX project, contract no. 156/2021 PN).-III-P4-ID-PCE-2020-0494 , funder UEFISCDI).
- An article in "**Plant and Soil**" that will report an experiment at the pot scale carried out on the mining substrate of a still active tailing pond ((contract no. 453/2020, PN-III-P2-2.1-PED- 2019-258, UEFISCDI funder).
- An article in "**Applied Vegetation Science**" that will contain preliminary data and mapping of knowledge in the field of error estimators associated to vegetation cover structure associations in meadows (METTELFLUX project, contract no. 156/2021 PN-III-P4-ID-PCE).2020-0494, UEFISCDI funder).
- An article in "**Remote sensing Environment**" that will include matrices for LIDAR processing based on data obtained in vegetation plots (METTELFLUX project, contract no. 156/2021 PN-III-P4-ID-PCE-2020-0494, financier UEFISCDI).
- An article in "**Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment**" about the pedological and geochemical characterization in four large-scale plots by the method of sampling networks and ten rain simulation experiments in each plot (METTELFLUX project, contract no. 156/2021 PN- III-P4-ID-PCE-2020-0494 , UEFISCDI funder).
- Publication of an article in "**Catena**" of data from the monitoring of some slope lysimeters with sensors, leachate, surface runoff and vegetation (METTELFLUX project, contract no. 156/2021 PN-III-P4-ID-PCE -2020-0494 , UEFISCDI funder).
- Publication of an article in "**Environmental Science and Pollution Research**" - Screening of stable pollutants in Arieş and Mureş meadows (METTELFLUX project, contract no. 156/2021 PN-III-P4-ID-PCE-2020-0494, financier UEFISCDI).
- Publication in "**Water resources**" of an experiment heavy metals and nutrients percolation through columns (INTER-ASPА project, contract no. 34/2018, PNIII Complex Partnership, UEFISCDI 2018-2021)

These manuscripts will become the first priority for submission to the mentioned journals. Numerous preliminary results disseminated at scientific conferences, can be partially seen on the page https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Aurora_Neagoe/publications and in the scientific reports available on the web pages of the ongoing research projects whose addresses can be found in my CV, which is part of this habilitation thesis.

Applied projects

At the moment, I am involved in the following projects in the evaluation stage:

1. PCE application, 2023. Title: "Resilience of biogeochemical services to climate stress in a critical observatory areas: upscaling in space and time".
2. Biodiversa+ application, 2024 Call for proposals "Better knowledge for the development, implementation and evaluation of nature-based solutions (BiodivNBS)" Project number : Biodiversa2023-522 Project acronym : QUANTUM ; Project title "Appropriate and easy-

to-use monitoring and evaluation framework for integrated ecosystem restoration strategies".

3. PTE application, 2024, "Eco-technology TRL6 for the remediation of tailings ponds according to the geochemical, geomorphological and ecological settings of the area" no. PN-IV-P7-7.1-PTE-2024-0762
4. PED application, 2024, "TRL3 technology for the assessment of aboveground VEgetation functional Traits and of the Roughness And Porosity of plant cover - LIVETRAP", no. PN-IV-INO-PED-2024- 2382
5. CoEx application, 2024, Optimizing the circular bioeconomy through integration technological platforms with creative laboratories from real life environments, PN-IV-P6-6.1-CoEx-2024-0216

C1.2 Strategic career development directions

If until now I have made a historical account of the premises of career development, in this sub-chapter, considering the level at which we work in the team whose coordination I also contribute, I will adopt an organizational approach to the development strategy. It is obvious that conducting research at high standards is inseparable from integration into an appropriate institutional infrastructure, from connecting to human resource training programs in universities able to permanently ensure the new generations of young people who want to work in research teams and the continuous transfer of the research results not only to the public approved by ISI-quoted journals, but also to powerful economic partners.

In this context, as important as detailing the strategic research directions already mentioned in Figure C1 is also clarifying how I intend to approach the stability problems of the functional unit of which I am a part, ensuring the quality of young people's human resources, technological transfer, and decision support.

Institutional development

The CESEC center that I scientifically coordinate has a fairly small size in terms of human resources, which gives it the advantage of rapid mobility and adaptability but also a certain vulnerability to turbulence in the research environment. As a result, the strategic direction I support is the integration into a wider structure of the University of Bucharest. I have in mind either the Research Institute of UB (ICUB), or the Botanical Garden (GB) of UB, in the premises of which we are currently carrying out our research activity, which also includes two experiments with lysimeters installed in the GB spaces.

I also support strengthening institutional collaboration with the Faculty of Geology and its doctoral school, within which some young people with whom I have collaborated closely defended their doctoral theses. In fact, recently, I was involved in the development of some activities of a project that run at the Faculty of Geology, PNRR project "Paleotopography and Crustal Evolution - PACE" coordinated by Prof. Dr. Mihai Ducea m.c. of the Romanian Academy. It is also natural to continue or resume collaborations with research groups from the Faculty of Biology with whom we have carried out projects in previous stages. I will also want to continue the collaboration with research groups from the Faculty of Biology with whom we ran projects in the previous years. I will continue collaborating with the Department of Botany and Microbiology, a collaboration I started in 2019.

Among the companies in the country, I have already tried to build a partnership with the CEPROMIN Deva company (PTE applied project already mentioned in the section C1.2). In the future I will also try a partnership with Cupru Min Abrud. Both companies appear to be interested in the ecotechnologies developed by our research group, and we are also looking for other companies interested in acid mine water treatment technologies.

Main future research directions

On the European level, I will strengthen with new applications and bilateral relations, the strategic partnership with the universities involved in the FP7 Umbrella project, especially with University of Jena, Germany through the coordinator of the FP7 Umbrella project (Professor Erika Kothe), on issues of integrated management of areas with mining activities. With University of Örebro, "School of Science and Technology" from Sweden through Professor Stefan Karlsson, I intend to collaborate for the development of new methodologies for the analysis of the chemical forms of metals in water and with the University of Cagliari, Sardinia through Professor Giovanni deGiudici, I intend to use integrated tools for the support and transfer to a larger (bio)agricultural scale of some zero-pollution practices, in an international PED type project.

Other research directions will be:

- Characterization of the exposure of human populations to metals. It is a direction in which I developed my doctoral thesis. For several years, we started a collaboration with the University of Medicine and Pharmacy Bucharest, which ended with the publication in SOTEN of the international article "Environmental contamination with metals and the assessment of the impact on health in two industrial regions of Romania (2017)". Thus, we intend to apply a project to the first competition that will be launched in this field, for coupling biogeochemical research in contaminated areas with risk assessment for the health of human populations.
- Stoichiometry of elements in plants and their physiological effects. Our research group has important preliminary data in preparation for publication on the effects of N and P on heavy metal bioaccumulation and oxidative stress in plants (communicated in 2014 at a conference held at the University of Jena), as well as on the effects of plant community structure and heavy metal contamination on leachate element output and plant functional traits (communicated in 2022 at the same conference held at the University of Jena).
- Bioremediation technologies optimized in terms of costs and user needs. I intend to continue:
 - Adaptation of technological solutions to ponds with a different type of substrate;
 - Resuming the idea of coupling the phytoremediation with the inoculation of the substrate with bacteria identified even from the dumped material.

In the application of the PTE project mentioned in the subsection C1.2, we have already proposed the transition to a time scale of field experiments greater than the one practiced so far (from TRL4 to TRL6), through a partnership with the CEPROMIN Deva company. Field experiments conducted to date have lasted no longer than 5 years, or accelerated succession processes on a substrate contaminated by a tailings pond or tailings dump take place on the scale of a decade. The still active experiment at Certeju de Sus Hunedoara county benefits from good institutional conditions (both with the pond owners and the local municipality) and we aim to turn it into a longer-term research site for the mentioned processes.

C2 The development coordinates of the didactic activities carried out until now

Courses and practical works and/or seminars

Master's level courses previously held were:

1. "*Remediation of polluted areas*", for three years (2007 - 2009), in the frame of a multidisciplinary master with the name: "Assessment and Integrated Control of Environmental Pollution", Department of Technologies (CREDIS), Faculty of Chemistry, University of Bucharest.
 - The teaching contribution included course notes and practical work that were personally designed, held and published (Neagoe et al. 2011 and Neagoe and Iordache 2021).
2. "*Methodology of scientific research*" for three years (2015 - 2017), in the framework of a master's degree in *Environmental Quality Control and Evaluation Systems*, Faculty of Environmental Engineering and Food Science, Valahia University, Târgoviște.
 - The teaching contribution consisted in course notes and seminar work that were personally designed and held.

Practical works

1. In the field of *plant nutrition*, at bachelor level, Department of Applied Botany (second year of studies, summer semester 2003 taught in German, summer semester 2004, taught in English), Faculty of Biology and Pharmacy, Friedrich Schiller University Jena Germany.
 - The practical works were organized in my own conception, in accordance with the course notes given by the botanist Professor Hans Bergmann
2. In the field of organic chemistry - *organic compounds with simple functions* for third-year students of the Biochemistry Department, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Bucharest (one semester, 2010).
 - The practical works were supported by me according to the work reports established at the biochemistry department and in accordance with the course with the same name, given by the chemist lecturer Eliza Oprea.
3. In the field of *plant physiology*, for second-year students of Biochemistry, Biology and Ecology Departments, Faculty of Biology, University of Bucharest (one semester, 2020).
 - The practical works were organized in my own conception, in accordance with the course notes given by the botanists lecturers Dana Lazăr and Gentiana Predan.

C1.2 Training of human resources

Contribution to human resource training

- I scientifically coordinated 16 bachelor theses from the Departments of Ecology, Biochemistry and Biology, Faculty of Biology, and from Biochemistry, Faculty of Chemistry and other 3 dissertation theses also from the Faculty of Chemistry (2007-2023).
- I coordinated professional internships for students from the Department of Ecology and Biochemistry, Faculty of Biology, University of Bucharest (2008, 2021 and 2022).
- Since 2009, I have been informally involved in coordinating doctoral theses. Thus, the young researchers carried out their research activities working alongside me for their doctoral theses (Stancu P., Nicoară A., Păun A., Cicîrma M.) coordinated by people who are part of the doctoral schools in Romania or Germany. The collaboration also led to collaborative scientific articles.

I also collaborated with other researchers in specific research activities (Gheorghe R., Păun M., Manu M., Ion S.). It can be concluded that the research activity carried out was significantly coupled with the training of human resources of future researchers.

Together with my colleagues from the Department of Botany and Microbiology, I will support the finalization of the documents for the organization of a new master in “**Applied Botany**”.

Also, with colleagues from other faculties, I will support the creation of an interdisciplinary master’s degree for coupled biological, chemical and hydrogeological processes. This program will be adapted from the one at the University of Jena (Bio-Geo-interactions) in which I am involved and will benefit from managerial assistance and professional visits by professors from Germany. Once created, it can also constitute an inter-academic exchange bridge for young people between partner universities in the already mentioned European consortium. This is one of the main reasons why I want to defend my habilitation thesis, as it is an important condition for attracting young researchers motivated to know the secrets of science, thus being able to be involved in research activities at European standards.

This is one of the main reasons why I want to defend my habilitation thesis, as it is an important condition for attracting young researchers motivated to know the secrets of science, thus being able to be involved in research activities at European standards.

Conclusions

I showed my career development skills from relatively simple projects to extremely complex projects, from integration as a team member to coordination of consortia with many national organizations and participation in European projects.

It is clear that further development above this level, or even the maintenance of current performance, also depends on an appropriate institutional and economic climate for researchers' activity. To compensate for the shortcomings of this climate, I will focus on obtaining resources from European sources, which are often more stable than those from national sources, even if they are more difficult to access.

Good premises exist for the development of my work and that of partners, leading to the creation of a tradition in this field of research following the model of the schools in Germany where I was educated.

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